

Description of a new specimen of the Late Cretaceous allodaposuchid crocodile *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869), with stratigraphic and palaeogeographic comments

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Abstract: An unpublished crocodylian specimen is assigned to *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869a), family Allodaposuchidae Narváez *et al.*, 2015. The specimen is relocated to its original site, the Campanian Fuveau lignite Mining Basin of the Arc syncline (Provence, France), thanks to a preliminary examination of the palynoflora of its matrix, which appears to be that of the site of the syntype of “*Crocodylus*” *affuvelensis* Matheron. The discoveries of the Cretaceous reptiles by Matheron (1862–1878) in the area are presented, following his original stratigraphic and lithologic presentation, updated by more recent studies of the Basin including of palaeomagnetism, and confirming the early Campanian age of the type locality. The study of the morphology of this specimen (a dentary with preserved teeth) consists of a detailed analysis of the characters of the dentary and its dentition, in comparison with other allodaposuchids and some other crocodiles as external witnesses, significantly broadening the knowledge of this taxon. The belonging to the family is confirmed, the relative primitiveness and antiquity of the species are addressed. The presences of the Cretaceous crocodiles including those of Matheron – and of the turtles having shared the same possible dispersal mode in the Western and Central Cretaceous European Archipelago are compared, re-evaluating the possibilities of inter-island relationships by these freshwater reptiles.

Keywords: Allodaposuchidae, Teeth characters, Geological context, European Cretaceous Archipelago

Résumé : Description d'un nouveau spécimen du crocodile allodaposuchidé *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869) avec commentaires stratigraphiques et paléogéographiques – un spécimen inédit de crocodile est attribué à *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869a), de la famille des Allodaposuchidae Narváez *et al.*, 2015. Le spécimen est resitué dans sa localité d'origine, le Bassin de lignite de Fuveau, du synclinal de l'Arc (Provence, France), Campanien, grâce à un examen préliminaire de la palynoflore fournie par sa matrice, révélée comme étant celle de la localité type du syntype de « *Crocodylus* » *affuvelensis* Matheron, 1869. Sont rappelées les découvertes de reptiles crétacés par Matheron (1869-1878) dans la région, en suivant sa présentation stratigraphique et lithologique, réévaluée par les études plus récentes sur le Bassin, dont celles de paléomagnétisme, et l'âge Campanien inférieur de la localité type est conforté. L'étude morphologique du spécimen (un dentaire muni de ses dents) est menée par l'analyse détaillée des caractères du dentaire et de sa dentition, par comparaison avec les allodaposuchidae et quelques autres crocodiles comme témoins externes, améliorant grandement la connaissance du taxon. Son appartenance à la famille est confortée et sa position relativement primitive et ancienne y est considérée. Sont comparées les présences des crocodiles crétacés dont ceux de Matheron – et des tortues pouvant partager avec eux les mêmes possibilités de dispersion –, dans les régions occidentales et centrales de l'Archipel Européen crétacé, réévaluant les possibilités de relations entre les îles par ces reptiles d'eau douce.

Mots clés : Allodaposuchidae, paramètres dentaires, contexte géologique, Archipel européen crétacé

1. INTRODUCTION

An unpublished crocodile specimen was deposited in the Museum of the Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Mines of Alès, Gard, France, an important area of the Carboniferous Coal Mining Basin of Cévennes

mountains (South of France). It is shown the specimen does not come from the Alès basin. It belongs to the crocodylian “*Crocodylus*” *affuvelensis* Matheron, 1869a (Matheron, 1869b), which became *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869) in Martin & Buffetaut (2008): this is an allodaposuchid crocodile from a Late

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Cretaceous Mining Basin, the Fuveau-Gardanne Basin (HBCM), located in the Arc syncline, Aix-en-Provence area (Bouches-du Rhône, south-eastern France) (Fig. 1); the type-level of the taxon is the lower level, that with “Reptiles”, of the “Étages de Fuveau” of the geologist Matheron (1869a) (Fuvelian Matheron, 1878). The Arc synclinal basin is a famous area, known by the discoveries of Cretaceous Reptiles by Matheron, at the end of the 19th century, and having provided famous dinosaurs, crocodiles, and turtles. A preliminary examination of the palynoflora of the specimen was carried out (D. Pons), confirming its origin and age. It gives the opportunity to review the Matheron’s discoveries, following his geological sequence throughout the local Cretaceous times, including the Fuveau lignite and other superposed Arc syncline layers, showing the successive association of reptiles among which other crocodiles (Matheron, 1869a, b) (Tabl. 1). The stratigraphic position of the Fuveau lignite series is recorded and considered on the base of the known lithology since the first discoveries of Matheron in the region and beyond (Cavelier & Roger, 1980; Babinot & al. 1983; Matheron, 1832, 1862, 1869a, b, 1878–1880; Villot, 1883), and in view of the palaeomagnetic and stratigraphic successive results of

Westphal (1989), Westphal & Durand (1990), Garcia & Vianey-Liaud (2001) and Benammi *et al.* (2006) in South of France.

The new specimen of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron) (MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1) consists of a dentary provided with its teeth. It provides several morphological characters which complete the knowledge of the taxon. The reason for assigning the new specimen to this taxon of the family Allodaposuchidae is explained (Narváez *et al.*, 2015). A detailed examination of the morphology of each element of the dentary (bony and dental characters) is carried out. Its dentition is compared with that of the Allodaposuchidae listed in Table 1, and with that of other crocodylian taxa, taken as external controls.

The family name is derived from the genus name of a crocodylian coming from the Hațeg basin (Romania), Maastrichtian Densuș-Ciula Formation, Vălioara type locality, and surrounding areas: Nopcsa (1915–1916) attributed this crocodylian to “*Crocodylus affuvelensis?*” by reference to the crocodile of Matheron (1869a). Later, Nopcsa (1928) erected the genus *Allodaposuchus*, from the Hațeg basin, Transylvania (Romania) (early to middle Maastrichtian: Panaiotu & Panaiotu, 2010), and

Fig. 1. Map of South-east of France, with late Cretaceous localities of the Arc Syncline and surroundings areas: Fuvelian mining basin sites (blue stars) and Begudo-Rognacian sites (red circles), which yielded reptiles discussed in the article.

Tabl. 1 A-1B. Crocodiles mentioned by Matheron (1869a) from Fuveau Basin, and main recorded taxa attributed to Allodaposuchidae, with mention of the dentary and teeth. Abbreviations: ant, anterior; coll., collection; figs, figures; Fm, formation; mx, maxillary; mediopost, medioposterior; morpho, morphotype; pmx, premaxillary; post, posterior.

Tabl. 1A.

<i>Ischyrochampsia meridionalis</i> Vasse, 1995: <i>Allodaposuchus</i> sp. in Martin <i>et al.</i> , 2015.	Late Campanian (early Rognacian)	Sandstones and clays with reptiles (correlated to Grès et argiles à Reptiles - Rognac station level)	Saint-Estève- Janson (Bouches du Rhône, SE France)	1 Premaxilla with 1 pointed tooth- dentary with preserved tooth 7 ; isolated teeth specimens, of which 2 magnified - > diastema 7//8 + group morpho 1c
<i>Allodaposuchus</i> cf. <i>precedens</i> Nopcsa, 1928 in Martin, 2010, <i>Lohuecosuchus mechinorum</i> Narváez <i>et al.</i> , 2015	Late Campanian (early Rognacian)	Sandstones and clays with reptiles (correlated to Grès et argiles à Reptiles - Rognac station level)	Fox-Amphoux (Var, SE France).	Skull - Some MNHN.F.Fox coll. inedited isolated teeth and skull bones
<i>Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti</i> Buscalioni, Ortega, Vasse 1997 (Buscalioni, Ortega, Vasse, 1999)	Late Campanian C32n	below a marine early Maastrichtian level	Laño, Castilla y Leon: Condado de Treviño (enclave (in Burgos province) (Spain)	Mx with teeth and dentary with 16 teeth - not magnified - two drawn posterior dentary Teeth - > diastema 7//8 + group morpho 1b
<i>Allodaposuchus. precedens</i> Nopcsa, 1928 (in Martin <i>et al.</i> , 2015) = <i>Al. iberoarmoricanus</i> (Blanco, 2021),	Begudian (Fuvelian upper part) Late Campanian C32n–C32r	15 m below the “Rognac station” of lower Rognacian part	Velaux-La Bastide Neuve (Bouches du Rhône, SE France)	Bones, Skull with some teeth - one 4th mx enlarged view - Dentary without symphysis and teeth - > diastema 7//8 + group morpho 1b
« <i>Crocodylus blavieri</i> » Gray, 1831 (nomen dubium)	Fuvelian s.s. – (Fuvelian lower part), early Campanian below the Begudian. C33, inferior part, above the Valdonnian (C34 superior).	Fuveau lignite Formation - 4th lignite bed «Mène de quatre pans»	HBCM, Fuveau-Gardanne-Valdonne area (Bouches du Rhône, SE France)	1 Bone - distinguished from <i>Ma. affuvelensis</i> by Matheron 1869a - no teeth. Holotype femur part recovered
<i>Massaliasuchus affuvelensis</i> (Matheron, 1869a) in Martin & Buffetaut, 2008.	Fuvelian s.s. – (Fuvelian lower part)- early Campanian below the Begudian. C33, inferior part. Above the Valdonnian (C34 superior).	Fuveau lignite Formation - type in basal 1st lignite bed “La Grande Mène” (Mine)	HBCM, Fuveau basin : Fuveau-Gardanne-Valdonne area (Bouches du Rhône, SE France)	Partial skulls, dentary parts, teeth. Partial dentaries: (1) one left dentary, full tooth series of 16 alveoli with preserved 1, 8, 11-15, + partial 2, 10 (2) (3) Fragmentary dentaries with some post. teeth. (4) Fig. syntype dentary + teeth 4, 8-15. - Some isolated skull and dentary teeth. Heterodonty, teeth: Pointed 1-10. Highest 4th fluted on one side and pointed. Not pointed: 11- 12, short, 13-15 even shorter and “blunt”; mediopost 11-15: cylindrical roots, no marked collar, wrinkled network enamel- magnified views - > diastema 7//8 + morpho 1 a. Figs. this opus, Matheron 1869a, M&B 2008. [Syntype postcranial with vertebrae, coracoid and femur part]

Indetermined crocodile Buffetaut <i>et al.</i> , 1996 (Garcia <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	Early Campanian C33.1r	Villeveyrac/Mèze basin. L'Olivet.	Villeveyrac (Hérault, Occitanie)	Mentionned teeth comparable to <i>Mu. buffetauti</i> - no figure
“Hylaeochampsidae gen, and sp. Indet.”, “ <i>Allodaposuchus</i> like” compared to Allodaposuchidae in Rabi & Delfino, 2012	Santonian	Csehánya Formation	Iharkút, Hungary	Cranial, lower jaw, isolated teeth (no figure)

Tab. 1B.

<i>Agaresuchus subjuniperus</i> (Puértolas-Pascual <i>et al.</i> , 2014b) - Puértolas-Pascual <i>et al.</i> , 2018, 2020, 2022	Upper most Maastrichtian within chron C29r	Tremp group Conqués Fm upper part of the ‘Lower Red Garumnian’ succession	Beranuy and Serraduy del Pon, Huesca, (Aragon, Spain) ‘Amor 3’ site	Skull with some mx teeth, not magnified views- + not magnified views isolated teeth
<i>Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum</i> Puértolas <i>et al.</i> , 2011, 2022	Late Maastrichtian transition between chrons C30n & C29r	< Tremp Fm Unit 2 - Lower Red Garumnian	Ellias site, Huesca (Aragon, (Spain)	Skull with some pmx and mx teeth, not magnified views
<i>Allodaposuchus precedens</i> Nopcsa, 1928 type species - figs in Buscalioni <i>et</i> <i>al.</i> , 2001, Delfino <i>et al.</i> , 2008, Martin <i>et al.</i> , 2010, Narvaez <i>et al.</i> , 2019	ca Early to Middle Maastrichtian C31r	Vălioara (Densuş- Ciula Formation), and Pui (Sânpetru Formation).--- Oarda do Jos (Sard Formation)	Haţeg basin, NW and Central.- Northeast to Haţeg basin.. Transylvania (Romania)	Bones - several Skulls with part of teeth - magnified presented teeth: 2 pmx-mx and 1 isolated teeth - no dentary teeth- Isolated teeth from Pui (Haţeg) in Solomon & Codrea, 2015.
<i>Allodaposuchus hulki</i> Blanco <i>et al.</i> , 2015	Early Maastrichtian	Trempe Fm lower red unit	Casa Fabia site, Catalonia (Spain)	Bones - Premaxilla + 4 rounded tooth section in alveoli. Fragment dentary + teth 3d pointed, +4th caniniform ridged on visible lingual side (apex cut).
« <i>Allodaposuchus</i> » <i>palustris</i> Blanco <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Early Maastrichtian C31r	Trempe Fm basis	Fumanya S, Catalonia (Spain)	Bones - Skull parts, Fragment ant. dentary +7 ant alveoli+ special group , present dentary morphotype 2. magnified mediopost. mx + dent teeth with wrinkled enamel- or not network. Several tooth morphotypes: ridged narrow teeth, post. teeth pointed top, and others, attributed to <i>Al. palustris</i> and cf. in Blanco <i>et</i> <i>al.</i> , 2018, 2020.
“ <i>Crocodylus vetustus</i> Matheron, 1869a” (nomen dubium) “ said differing from <i>C. affuvelensis</i> . Possible <i>Acynodon</i> sp.?”	Latest Campanian (Rognacian) ca C30n	Marls of «Calcaires supérieurs » with Reptiles. Rognac station limestones level	Nerthe tunnel, Rognac (Bouches du Rhône, SE France)	Bones: without figures - heterodonty, said as: teeth = pointed + obtuse with collar and wrinkled enamel, particular shape possible <i>Acynodon</i> morphotype?
<i>Agaresuchus fontisensis</i> Narvaez <i>et al.</i> , 2016	Late Campanian - Early Maastrichtian	Villalba de la Sierra Formation - upper part, mudstones	Lo Hueco, Cuenca (Spain)	2 Skulls - holotype + right dentary + 16 alveoli most preserved teeth (10 on 16) > diastema 7//8 + group morpho 1c- not magnified views
<i>Lohuecosuchus megadontos</i> Narvaez <i>et al.</i> , 2015	Late Campanian- Early Maastrichtian	Villalba de la Sierra Formation - upper part, mudstones	Lo Hueco, Cuenca (Spain)	Skulls with some preserved teeth - not magnified - 3 figured dentaries with 14 preserved teeth - not magnified- diastema 7//8 + group morpho 1b

attributed this crocodylian material to *Allodaposuchus* cf. *affivelensis*, suggesting that if “in future a specific difference should ever be established between the French and the Transylvanian species, I think the latter might be named *Allodaposuchus precedens*”. This specific new name was adopted by the scientific community (Steel, 1973; Buscalioni *et al.*, 2001) and followed by Blanco (2021), Codrea *et al.* (2002), Delfino *et al.* (2008a), Martin & Buffetaut (2008), Narváez *et al.* (2015) among others. Matheron’s syntype included a dentary, a fragment of maxillodentary, teeth and some postcranial bones. But it lacks a complete skull allowing a positive comparison with the Romanian type material of *Al. precedens*, itself lacking the dentary. But new material from the type-locality of *Ma. affivelensis* has been added to the syntype of “*Crocodylus*” *affivelensis* allowing the designation of a neotype (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008). Its family identity was gradually confirmed, after the original description of *Al. precedens* had been completed.

The family Allodaposuchidae includes several genera spanning the time interval between the early Campanian and the late Maastrichtian (Narváez *et al.*, 2019) of Western and Central-Eastern Europe (Tabl. 1). After “*Crocodylus*” *affivelensis* Matheron, 1869a and *Allodaposuchus precedens* Nopcsa, 1928, *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis* Vasse, 1995 was erected on a half-lower jaw and a premaxillary of one specimen, from the late Campanian of Saint-Estève-Janson (Durance basin, Bouches-du-Rhône) (Fig. 1) (considered as Maastrichtian at that time). Although first considered as a “Trematochampsidae”, it was then regarded as an allodaposuchid. In Spain, Buscalioni *et al.* (1997) erected *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* based mostly on a dentary (thus comparable with the figure of the “*Crocodylus*” *affivelensis* Matheron’s syntype dentary), coming from the late Campanian – Maastrichtian boundary of Laño (Spain). They examined the possible attribution of “*Cr.*” *affivelensis* to *Mu. buffetauti*, before the erection of the Allodaposuchidae family by Narváez *et al.* (2015) and without making comparisons with *Ischyrochampsia*. They considered the Fuveau taxon as a *nomen dubium*. They located *Mu. buffetauti* in “Alligatoroidea Gray, 1844 sensu Norell *et al.*, 1994)” without family rank (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997, 1999, 2001; Corral *et al.*, 2016). Martin & Buffetaut (2008) erected the genus *Massaliasuchus* for “*Cr.*” *affivelensis*, Matheron, 1869a, based on a well-preserved partial skull and another new skull fragment, in addition to the preserved Matheron’s syntype elements. They also attributed it to the Alligatoroidea (also before the erection of the Allodaposuchidae family). They compared *Ma. affivelensis* with *Mu. buffetauti* and *Al. precedens* showing their clear generic differentiation, but not integrating these two former forms in a cladistic analysis. Similarly, Martin *et al.* (2015) did not integrate *Ma. affivelensis* in the phylogenetic analysis done for a new specimen of *Al. precedens* from the late Campanian

(Begudian) of Velaux – La Bastide Neuve (Bouches-du-Rhône) (Fig. 1). Martin *et al.* (2015) considered *Allodaposuchus* to belong to Hylaeochampsidae Andrews, 1913, a family already considered for this taxon. They considered that *Musturzabalsuchus* and *Ischyrochampsia* “could reasonably represent junior synonyms of *Allodaposuchus*”. When erecting the Allodaposuchidae family, Narváez *et al.* (2015) indicated a global similarity of the Fuveau crocodile with *Mu. buffetauti* and included them both in the family, although without introducing them in a phylogenetic analysis: these existing analyses were mainly based on skull characters, almost completely absent in the two latter species. Thus, poorly known, *Ma. affivelensis* and *Mu. buffetauti* have received little phylogenetic attention so far. For Blanco (2021) “The inclusion [of *Musturzabalsuchus* and *Massaliasuchus*] in Allodaposuchidae is still pending further analyses”. In Narváez *et al.*, 2015 (2016, 2019) Allodaposuchidae are a monophyletic lineage, as in Blanco (2021), who considered Allodaposuchidae as a member of Crocodylia within Eusuchia. Rio & Mannion (2021) considered Allodaposuchidae as a clearly differentiated taxon from the *Hylaeochampsia* branch. Several genera and species have been added to the Allodaposuchidae in complement to *Allodaposuchus*, *Musturzabalsuchus* and *Massaliasuchus*, including reattributions of species to new or different genera such as *Arenysuchus* Puértolas *et al.*, 2011, *Lohuecosuchus* Narváez *et al.*, 2015 and *Agaresuchus* Narváez *et al.*, 2016 (Tabl. 1) and integrating *Ischyrochampsia*. Hypotheses of relationships between them and other crocodylians have been postulated. The integration of *Musturzabalsuchus* and *Massaliasuchus* in the family was provisionally accepted (Blanco, 2021; Puértolas-Pascual *et al.*, 2022) with the taxa recorded in Table 1.

The present study aims at detailing the *Ma. affivelensis* characters of the lower jaw and its teeth all along the tooth row of the new specimen, compared with the syntypes drawings of *Ma. affivelensis* (Matheron, 1869a, pl. 1), and the material with teeth which allowed the definition of *Massaliasuchus* in Martin & Buffetaut (2008). Known Allodaposuchid dentition in other species is compared. Allodaposuchidae (Tabl. 1) are attested in the late Cretaceous in Western Europe (France, Spain) and in Central Europe (Romania), spanning the Santonian – Maastrichtian interval, when distinct areas of emerged islands existed as archipelagos, in the northwestern Mediterranean area of the Neotethys (Blanco, 2021; Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015; Dercourt *et al.*, 2000; Martin *et al.*, 2015, fig. 1; Puértolas-Pascual *et al.*, 2016). Authors including Blanco (2021), Csiki-Sava *et al.* (2015), Martin (2010b), Martin *et al.* (2015) and Puértolas-Pascual & Canudo (2015) have shown the presence of a common Cretaceous fauna of crocodiles among reptiles. They discussed the identities, hypothesised the taxon interrelationships between the islands of the two blocks,

and the way they have spread and were distributed along the Cretaceous, and particularly the Allodaposuchidae (Blanco, 2021). Considering the age and the evolutionary state of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*, it is necessary to review the crocodylian distribution in the archipelago, considering new palaeomagnetic dating and discussing possibilities of spreading across sea arms of the different crocodylian taxa. This discussion includes comparisons with coexisting aquatic turtle families, sharing the same dispersal mode, attested in the *Ma. affuvelensis* region. The taxa from the Matheron's sites (1869a, b, 1878) (Arc syncline and surroundings) are examined (Fig. 1), as well as their distribution along the late Cretaceous sites in Europe, trying to specify the times of coexistence of the genera in the Archipelago.

INSTITUTIONAL ABBREVIATIONS

CMGD—ENSMA, Centre des Matériaux de Grande Diffusion, École Nationale Supérieure des Mines d'Alès, IMT – Mines Alès (École Mines-Telcom) (Alès, Gard); GTS, Geological Time Scale; HBCM, Houillères du Bassin du Centre et du Midi (Fuveau-Gardanne) (Bouches-du-Rhône); MHN Genève, Musée d'Histoire Naturelle de Genève. MHNA, Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle d'Aix-en-Provence (Bouches du Rhône); MHNM, Musée d'Histoire Naturelle de Marseille; MEMA, Musée de l'École des Mines d'Alès; MMG, Musée de la Mine de Gréasque (Bouches du Rhône); MNHN. F., Paleontology, and MNHN.RA.AC., Reptiles-Amphibians and Comparative Anatomy, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris; UAM, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid; UL1-ENSL, Université Lyon 1, École Normale Supérieure de Lyon; UP, Université de Poitiers, Paleovprim; USTL, Université des Sciences et Techniques du Languedoc, Montpellier.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. History of the specimen

The new specimen, deposited in the Alès Museum under number MEMA, F 1660, will be transferred to the Aix-en-Provence Museum under number MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1. It was loaned to MNHN by Pr J.-P. Rolley, who was at a time in charge of the Musée of the CMGD – ENSMA, now IMT – Mines Alès (Alès, Gard department, Occitanie region, France). Pr Rolley received the specimen from R. Aubaret's widow. R. Aubaret was involved with the organisation of the pilot mine of the coal basin of Alès, initiated in 1945 and open to the public since 1985. However, R. Aubaret was formerly in position at the HBCM, i.e. the Fuveau-Gardanne lignite basin (Bouches-du-Rhône), as a teacher and head of vocational training for minors. It is believed that he obtained the

fossil in this way and brought it to Alès. A paper label was attached to the specimen with an old-fashioned hand-inked note: "Mâchoire de Crocodile (fragment)", without any identified collection, that seems to have been written at the boundary of the 19th-20th centuries, but it was not identified according to Matheron (1869a, b)'s identification. The coal from the Alès mine, where the owner of the crocodile specimen came to work after the HBCM, being a Carboniferous deposit, and the group of crocodiles, of course, not yet existing in the Palaeozoic, it was important to establish and clarify that it was not a "specimen from the Alès mine" and to specify its origin. The new specimen was embedded in a block of black, hard, and shiny lignite, thus resembling rather "anthracite" coal to the eye (Monteau, 2010), perhaps resembling a fragment of coal from the Alès mines. The black fossil was hardened in the lignite and fractured in places, with the lignite filling the cracks (tooth 4 in particular, fractured horizontally into three parts). Only the left lateral part of the lower jaw was exposed. It was needle-prepared (FLB) then restored, consolidated, and cast (Renaud Vacant, MNHN). Part of the matrix was prepared (Denise Pons) for preliminary palynological research, in order to compare the matrix of the newly described specimen MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 with that of the specimens of the syntype "*Crocodylus*" *affuvelensis*.

The new specimen MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 is compared to the MHNM preserved material (see the material list in the Systematic part) and to the figure of a lost MHNM syntype of "*Crocodylus*" *affuvelensis* Matheron, 1869a, from "La Grande Mène" a similar lower jaw (Matheron, 1869a, pl. 1, fig. 8) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4P). The morphological relationships of *Ma. affuvelensis* material with the allodaposuchids are examined, together by the dentition, and in relation to the stratigraphic situation of the compared localities. The comparison is made with the allodaposuchids sensu Narváez *et al.* (2015) and Blanco (2021), based not only on the published original data but also on some new observations, such as that of the holotype of *Ischyrochampsia* (MNHN. F. Saint-Estève coll.). In Table 1, comparisons are made with species of allodaposuchids in which dentary is preserved with teeth, including *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti*, *Lohuecosuchus megadontos* Narváez *et al.*, 2015, and *Agaresuchus fontisensis* Narváez *et al.*, 2016. It is also compared to *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis*, and to *Allodaposuchus iberoarmoricanus/precedens* (that includes a lower jaw without teeth). *Al. hulki* Blanco *et al.*, 2015 and *Al. palustris* Blanco *et al.*, 2014 have only partial dentary parts and some teeth. The dentition is poorly integrated into the author's descriptions.

Comparisons of the lateral faces of allodaposuchids, depicted in the works, are made with the understanding that, in lateral view, when separated from the other branch, the depicted dental branch is positioned horizontally on the support base, as for the photographs

of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1; but some small different inclinations are possible in the comparative views; so that no precise comparative measurements are possible on the different species of allodaposuchids, although estimates are possible. Corresponding skulls with upper dentition are observed, including that of the type species *Allodaposuchus precedens* Nopcsa, 1928, from the Hațeg Basin, known from a few postero-premaxillary and antero-maxillary teeth (Buscalioni *et al.*, 2001, Delfino *et al.*, 2008a, Martin *et al.*, 2015; Narváez *et al.*, 2019), and by figured isolated teeth from Pui (Hunedoara County, same Hațeg basin) (Solomon & Codrea, 2015). Since the cranial elements of *Lohuecosuchus mechinorum* (Narváez *et al.*, 2015) (Martin, 2010b) are devoid of teeth, a few unpublished isolated teeth of the species are observed, preserved among other parts of the skeleton, including parts of skull tables in the MNHN. F. Fox-Amphoux collection. After its first description (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997, 1999), the lower jaw of *Musturzabalsuchus* (without teeth) was figured again, in colour, in Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015 (fig. 8I). Drawings have been proposed, integrating maxillary teeth from the late Campanian-early Maastrichtian of Armuña (Spain), by Buscalioni *et al.* (1997, 1999, 2001). Teeth of *Lohuecosuchus megadontos*, *Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum* Puértolas *et al.*, 2011 and *Agaresuchus subjuniperus* (Puértolas-Pascual *et al.*, 2014b) (Puértolas-Pascual *et al.*, 2022) are known by specimens bearing teeth, but these are not shown by magnified views.

For the purpose of comparison, but without seeking systematic relationships, the following material was studied, among the brevirostrine non-ziphodont eusuchian forms having a double main cranial festonation; there are: 1) African living Crocodylidae species, *Crocodylus niloticus* Laurenti, 1768 and *Osteolaemus tetraspis* Cope, 1861 (figs in Blainville, 1855, pl. 2; Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002, pl. 1a, b and pl. 2, a, b); 2) some early Cenozoic forms of Western Europe, from countries beforehand occupied by allodaposuchids: the alligatoroid *Diplocynodon* Pomel, 1847 (Ginsburg & Bulot, 1997; Martin, 2010c; Martin & Gross, 2011; Vaillant, 1872); and the crocodylid “*Crocodylus*” [“*Asiatosuchus*”] *depressifrons* Blainville, 1855 group (Delfino & Smith, 2009; Delfino *et al.*, 2017; Godinot *et al.*, 2018; Planté, 1870).

3. GEOLOGICAL SETTING AND PAL-AEONTOLOGICAL CONTEXT. AGE OF *MASSALIASUCHUS AFFUVELENSIS*

3.1. The Provence Arc syncline and the Fuveau Mining Basin (Fig 1.)

Massaliasuchus affuvelensis (Matheron, 1869b) comes from the Fuveau lignite Formation of the Fuveau-

Gardanne Basin (Aix-en-Provence area). The lignite series has been shown to be of early Campanian in age by magnetostratigraphy (see below), which is consistent with the local litho-stratigraphy. The Arc syncline represents a fluvio-lacustrine deposit, which spans a latest Santonian – Oligocene interval (83 Ma to 30 Ma), over about a hundred kilometres from east to west, and about thirty kilometres from south to north (Matheron, 1869a, b; Babinot & Durand, 1980 in Cavelier & Roger, coord. 1980). This continental deposit overlies the Santonian marine deposits in the region, with the late Santonian chalk (“*Hippurites* chalk”), that is visible at Plan d’Aups syncline flanks, east of Marseille and ca. 30 km south-east to Fuveau (Fig. 1). This deposit is correlated more or less with the marine layers of Gosau and other European countries. Matheron characterised these marine layers by the presence of “*Belemnitella mucronata* et *Inoceramus Cripsi*” (the former of both species being accepted as corresponding to the Campanian as a whole: see in particular Remin, 2015, for Poland). Matheron (1869a, b) positioned the Fuveau area studied deposits in the “Cretaceous part of the Great fluvio-lacustrine series of South-East of France, above the marine layers of the Villedieu chalk age”.

Matheron (1862, 1869a, b; 1878, 1880) observed a succession of late Cretaceous continental layers, which he assembled in local stages – Valdonnaian, Fuvelian, Rognacian and Vitrollian – appearing to form aureoles in the Late Cretaceous area of the Arc syncline region (Fig. 1), more to less overlying and locally outcropping. He referred molluscs and reptiles to these successive stages. His data and assessment of the stratotypes of the stages are reported after Babinot & Durand in Cavelier & Roger coord. (1980) – the abundant figures and local sections are referenced herein and briefly commented below.

Based on magnetostratigraphy, Westphal & Durand (1990) positioned the successive Arc syncline layers with reptiles in the Campanian and Maastrichtian. They provided (fig. 1) a magnetostratigraphic synthetic scheme based on the known magnetic position of various locality sites in the Aix-en-Provence Basin: they established a section according to the periods of magnetic data of the samples; this was done in particular by comparison with magnetostratigraphic data from other Upper Cretaceous sections, notably according to the scale defined in the classic Tethyan section of Gubbio (Italy) by Alvarez *et al.* (1977) (Channell & Medizza 1981; Coccioni & Premoli Silva 2015; Gardin *et al.*, 2012). Their sections are broadly integrated into their synthesis of palaeomagnetism by Garcia & Vianey-Liaud (2001, fig. 4), a work initially based on their eggshell scale. From the southern basin of Fuveau to the western Etang de Berre (Fig. 1), the successive aureoles of the stages of Matheron (1869a) are:

3.1.1. Southern and older aureole. Valdonnian Stage of Matheron (1878) (“*étage Valdonnien*”): Group E of Matheron (1862). (Map fig. 1 in “*Valdonnien*” chapter of Babinot & Durand, in Cavalier & Roger coord. 1980), from Valdonne (Fig. 1)

It consists of brackish layers with mollusc shells (listed in Matheron 1862), reptiles (only indeterminable chelonians are cited) (Matheron, 1862, 1869a, b), and plant remains. Probably equivalent to the lower part of the Campanian (“*Campanian*”) for Babinot & Durand (1980), it was transferred to the recent Santonian by Westphal & Durand (1990), because it corresponds to the upper part of the normal period C34n (detailed below): this position is in relative agreement with Plaziat (1981). The Valdonian is added to the Fuvelian in a Valdo-fuvelian by Garcia & Vianey-Liaud (2001), or in a Valdo-Fuvelian, independently of palaeomagnetic data, in some authors (Arlhac & Rouire, 1977; Babinot & Durand, 1980 in Cavalier & Roger, 1980; Broin, 1977; Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997; Garcia *et al.*, 2000; Plaziat, 1981); The Valdo-Fuvelian facies is notably considered as an Upper Santonian-Lower Campanian in Saint-Martin *et al.* (2021).

3.1.2. Next and outcropping northern aureoles, the “*Étages de Fuveau*” of Matheron (1869a), Stages (“*étages*”) F, F', G, H of Matheron, 1862, Fuvelian (“*Fuvélien*” Matheron, 1878)

These aureoles include two parts (Matheron, 1869a) (Maps in Chapters “*Fuvélien*”, fig. 1, and “*Bégudien*”, fig. 1 in Babinot & Durand, 1980).

3.1.2.1. Lower level of Fuveau stages of Matheron (1869). Fuvelian s. s. (for Babinot & Durand 1980, Group F of Matheron 1862). (Map fig. 1 of chapter “*Fuvélien*” of Babinot & Durand 1980)

Extending across part of the width of the Arc Syncline from east to west (Fig. 1), the formation reaches 200 m in height. Matheron (1869a) described a deep basal informal series of marly limestone, marls, compact limestone, and lignites, with molluscs and reptiles. Matheron (1862) listed the molluscs and for the first times mentioned “*Trionyx*” as a reptile (see below Matheron, 1869a). Later, Matheron (1869a) described reptiles, including crocodiles, turtles, and dinosaurs, in two of the successive lignite beds of the thick lignite series. In reality, there are seven main successive layers of lignite, corresponding to “*mènes*” (mines), known to be intercalated in the complete series constituting the Fuveau Lignite Formation. Their depth and regularity are variable in the basin (Babinot & Durand, 1980, section p. 177, fig. 2 of “*Fuvélien*”). In the Fuveau mining basin, just southeast of Aix-en-Provence, several coal extraction

shafts are known at places such as Gardanne, Fuveau, Gréasque, Mimet and Valdonne (Fig. 1). These gave access to the various lignite deposits in the basin (fig. in Babinot & Durand, 1980). The locality of the preserved fossils in the MHNM collection is indicated by the location of the lignite seam entry shaft, or by the location of a coal collection site, and/or by the lignite seam itself, such as “*La Grande Mène*” (i.e. “*mine*”) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008): it does not necessarily indicate the lignite level within the lignite series. Thus, the MHNM specimens are indicated either by a lignite level, such as “*La Grande Mène*,” or by “*Lignites de Fuveau*,” or by “*Fuveau stages*” (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008), or by the shaft location, such as “*Valdonne*” (without indication of a mine level) (Fig. 1).

(a) First basal and deeper lignite bed of the series: “*La Grande Mène*” (Matheron, 1869a) (“*la Grande Mine*” in Babinot & Durand, 1980); this is the stratotypic layer of “*Crocodylus affuvelensis*” Matheron, 1869a (his pl. 1), genus *Massaliasuchus*, to which are attributed the remains found in the Fuveau lignite layer and studied here. In addition to the crocodile, from the “*Grande Mène*”, Matheron (1869a) named a “*paludine*” turtle, “*Pleurosternon? provinciale*” Matheron, 1869a, which became *Polysternon provinciale* (Matheron, 1869a) in Portis, 1882 (see below); This is a foxemydinae bothremydid, previously listed as “*Trionyx*” in Matheron (1862). The association of this turtle species with *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* is worth mentioning. It is stratigraphically decisive for comparing the associations of crocodilian and turtle species in successive sites in Western and Central Europe (palaeogeography part of this work).

(b) The second lignite bed of Matheron is the “*Mène de Quatre pans*”, the fourth lignite layer of the series, located above the “*Grande Mène*” of “*C. affuvelensis*” (section of the Mine lignite series in Babinot & Durand, 1980, fig. 2 of the chapter “*Fuvéliens*”, p. 177). This layer provided the second Fuvelian crocodile: “*Croc. Blavieri. Croc. de Provence, Cuv. Os. Fos. v. 164, t. 6, f. 17. Fossil in the Lignite de Provence*” in Gray (1831) [i.e. the crocodile of Cuvier 1824, 1836: “*Crocodile bones from the lignites of Provence*”]. It is known from a half-femur (see below, crocodile material from Fuveau). Since Cuvier (1824), remains of crocodiles and turtles have been collected, forming part of various collections (MHNM; MHNA; MMG; MNHN; local and amateur associations) at:

- “*Jas de Bassas*” (Fig. 1) (location of Babinot & Durand 1980, fig. 1 of the Fuveau chapters), above the level of “*La Grande Mène*”, where the Bégudian covers the Fuvélien s. s.: the specimen of the genus *Polysternon* Portis, 1882 (pls. 28-29) (Broin 1977) was collected there, coming from a thin marl-limestone matrix interval within the lignite layer.
- “*Valdonne*” (Nopcsa, 1931a, b) (Fig. 1): associated specimens of *P. provinciale* and *Elochelys perfecta*

Nopcsa 1931a were collected in a marly-lignite layer (MHNM Ph. Matheron and Le Comte de Gérin-Ricard collections) (Broin, 1977).

- “Gardanne” (Fig. 1): a possible conical maxillary tooth was collected, attributed to “*Crocodylus affuvelensis* Matheron, 1869 (fig. in Monteau, 2010), with a specimen of *P. provinciale* (MMG; Monteau, 2010, figs 12–13).

The Fuveau lignite Formation, Fuvelian s. s. (lower level of the Fuvelian stage) is defined as early Campanian (period C33r) by magnetostratigraphy (Westphal & Durand, 1990) and by lithology. Previously, the Fuveau lignites were considered to be upper Campanian (Broin, 1977), probably upper part of the Campanian (Babinot & Durand, 1980) notably according to Arlhac & Roure (1977) and Babinot *et al.* (1983), probably early Campanian (Martin & Buffetaut 2008) (see the Campanian stratotype: Neumann & Odin, 2001; Neumann & Platel, 1983; Odin & Lamaurelle, 2001; Platel *et al.*, 1999).

3.1.2.2. Upper level of Fuveau stage of Matheron (1869a, b). “Bégudien” Villot, 1883 (Begudian). (Map fig. 1 in “Bégudien” chapter of Babinot & Durand, 1980): “Fuvelien” Matheron, 1878 (Fuvelian), upper level, upper part. Named from La Bégude (Fig. 1) where the Begudian layers overly the Fuvelian lignites level. F1, G et G’ of Matheron (1862); stage redefinition, local section, and map in Babinot & Durand (1980)

The Bégudian – i.e. the upper part of Matheron’s Fuvelian, above the main sequence with lignite layers – is described by Matheron (1869a, b) as a thick and informal formation with numerous and varied layers with gastropods [“Physes. Anostomes”], molluscs, listed by Matheron (1862). There is no mention of vertebrates. Considered as a local facies of the probable early Maastrichtian (Babinot & Durand, 1980), the stage is reconsidered as late Campanian by magnetostratigraphy (Westphal & Durand, 1990). The Begudian stage has been recognised more recently in other synclinal localities of the Arc syncline which have yielded fragmentary reptiles: at Ventabren (Bouches-du-Rhône) (the hill of the A8 motorway rest area, right side toward Aix-en-Provence coming from Salon-de-Provence) (Fig. 1): by marls with gastropods and bivalve molluscs, indeterminate crocodiles and turtles (*Polysternon cf. provinciale*, *Solemys* sp.), and at Pourcieux with similar and other taxa (Var), near the A8 motorway and the N7 (Fig. 1) (coll. MHNA), and at Trets (Fig. 1), notably with an additional turtle (*Dortoka* sp.) (coll. MNHN. F.), known from the early Campanian locality of Villeveyrac Olivet (Hérault) (see below). Estimation of the Valdonnian – Fuvelian age by palaeomagnetism (Westphal & Durand 1990, fig. 8): Valdonnian samples, exposed in the Fuveau basin, have a normal polarity, and are positioned at the top of the

Long Cretaceous Normal Chron C34n period; thus, the Valdonnian is part of the latest Santonian, the Santonian/Campanian boundary being fixed at the base of the Chron C33r. The Fuvelian begins with the Cr33 period, at the Santonian/Campanian boundary. The boundary corresponds to an age of 83.65 Ma (GTS), giving the older possible age of the Fuvelian Formation in the early Campanian. The new geochronological scale calibration having fixed the superior Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary at 72.17 Ma (Gradstein *et al.*, 1995, 2012, 2020; Ogg, 2020; Ogg & Hinnov, 2012; Scott, 2014), it lengthened the Campanian period. A late Campanian age was given to sites of the lower Rognacian, previously included in the Maastrichtian.

Among their samples Westphal & Durand (1990) collected in the Fuvelian Arc syncline sites, are:

- The Fuvelian s. s. samples: among them the basal one (from site 32) was collected just above the Valdonnian marls, basally in the Lignite series: Westphal & Durand (1990) have positioned the Fuvelian base (Fuvelian s. s.) at the base of the reversal polarity of the C33 period (C33r), just at the limit of the normal C34n period. Another sample, upper in the series of Fuvelian s. s. (from site 4), was taken higher in the great Valdonne quarry (Fig.1), above the “Grande Mine” lignite layer, thus above the *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* type layer; it was correlated to an inferior part of the reverse C33r period. Thus, the lignite Fuvelian s. s. samples span most parts of the Campanian, covering most parts of the reverse period C33r, period which partly follows in the Begudian (Westphal & Durand, 1990, fig. 8), by the upper Fuvelian layers, i.e. Begudian layers. Overlying the Fuvelian lignite beds, various samples of Westphal & Durand (1990) from the Matheron (1869)’s detrital layers, are positioned at the top of the C33r period and in most parts of the C33n period. Notably, the sites at Jas de Bassas and Barque station (Fuveau) (location in Babinot & Durand 1980, Fuvelian chapter, fig.1), at the limit with the underlying Fuveau lignite layers (see Jas de Bassas locality on Fig. 1).

According to all authors since Westphal & Durand (1990), the “Étages de Fuveau” of Matheron (1869a, b), consisted of the Fuvelian s. s. local stage part and of the Begudian local stage part, are both Campanian in age. Above, the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary is positioned in the Chron C32, precisely in the C32n2n, but located a little more (Ogg, 2020) or less basally (Coccioni & Premoli Silva, 2015 at Gubbio, fig. 4).

To summarise: above the Santonian-Campanian boundary (at 83.65/83.6 ± 0.2 Ma), the Fuvelian *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* layers, corresponding to most of the C33r period, are postulated with an early Campanian age, clearly starting earlier than the 33n period of most of the Campanian Begudian, and far from the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary (at 72.1 ± 0.2 Ma) (Gradstein *et al.*, 2020; Ogg, 2020; Ogg & Hinnov, 2012).

3.1.3. Rognacien overlying aureole: the “Étage de Rognac” of Matheron (1869a, b), “Rognacien” Villot, 1883

The Rognacien takes its name from the Rognac railway station (Bouches-du-Rhône) (Fig. 1), west of Aix-en-Provence and north of Marseille, at the northern entrance of the Nerthe railway tunnel, which was excavated through the mountain range between Rognac and Marseille. Matheron (1869a, b) distinguished a lower and an upper part within the stage. Matheron (1869a, b) interpreted the complete Rognac stage as the equivalent of the chalk with *Hemipneustes* of Gensac and Maëstricht (sic), stratigraphically overlying the Fuvelian stages, implicitly assigning it a Maastrichtian age. Matheron described reptiles from both Rognac stages (“Étages de Rognac”) (Map of the Outcrops of the Lower and Upper Rognacien, and Vitrollian: Rognacien chapter, fig. 1, of Babinot & Durand, 1980).

3.1.3.1. Lower level of the Rognac stage

The lower level of the Rognac stage, lower Rognacien (“Rognacien”) Villot, 1883, is composed of detrital [clayey sandstone] layers with reptiles (“Couches détritiques. Reptiles” in Matheron, 1869a, b) (MHNM collection). The reptilian taxa described by Matheron (1869a, b) are:

1. The dinosaurian *Hypselosaurus priscus* Matheron, 1869a (pl. 2, figs 1–5 in Matheron, 1869a) (nomen dubium in Le Loeuff, 1993);
2. The chelonian *Solemys gaudryi* (originally “*Aplolidemys gaudryi*” Matheron, 1869a) [without figures]; given as of “Rognacien, Maastrichtien supérieur” in Broin, 1977: 24, 225; “basal Rognacien, Maastrichtian” in Lapparent de Broin and Murelaga, 1996, 1999 (with the first figures of this Rognac species of Matheron), now considered as late Campanian in age;
3. Large fragmentary eggs, mentioned by Matheron in 1846 and 1869a (Taquet, 2001). Matheron questioned them, attributing them either to a giant bird or to the new reptile “hypselosaure”; they have been attributed to dinosaurs, notably following the studies of Gervais (Taquet, 2001), new discoveries of bones and eggs and their dating, notably in Provençal stratigraphy, from Lapparent (1938, 1943, 1947), in Garcia and Vianey-Liaud, (2001), and other works. No crocodile is mentioned.

The Matheron detrital layers correspond to the “Grès et argiles à reptiles”, i.e. the sandstones and clays with reptiles, in the sense of the southern regions of France. They represent a lithologic unit considered to extend from Bas-Languedoc in Occitania to Provence (France) and as far as Catalonia (Spain), between the Santonian and the Maastrichtian (Matheron, 1878). Babinot and Durand (1980) considered this Formation to be a diachronic

lithologic unit, depending on the localities and regions, with stratigraphic and lithologic equivalences not being clearly established (Buffetaut *et al.*, 2021).

For Babinot and Durand (1980), the Begudien is added only to this part of the Lower Rognacien, forming a “Begudo-Rognacien” of the Late Campanian. Westphal & Durand (1990) correlated their lower Rognacien (“Rognacien inférieur”) samples – those collected in the detrital layers and bearing these lower Rognacien reptiles of Matheron (1869a, b) – , with the upper (but not the latest) part of the C33n anomaly, in the late (but not terminal) Campanian.

3.1.3.2. Upper level of Rognac stage

The upper level of Rognac stage (upper Rognacien). “Calcaires supérieurs. Reptiles. Lychnus” (Upper limestone Reptiles. Lychnus) of Matheron (1869a), consists of limestone, lacustrine sandstone and marly layers with the gastropod *Lychnus* (Matheron, 1869’s section p. 355) (Turin, 2017). It includes two limestone levels: the basal “Calcaire de la gare de Rognac” (Limestone from Rognac Railway station) level and, in the middle, the “Calcaire de la barre de Rognac” (important Rognac bar or Rognac limestone bar), with associated superposed silty marl layers (see figs in Garcia & Vianey-Liaud, 2001).

(a) The inferior part of the upper Rognacien section includes the marls and limestones of the Rognac railway limestone level (Nerthe tunnel, “Gare de Rognac”). Reptiles described by Matheron (1869a, b) are: 1) *Crocodylus vetustus* Matheron, 1869a: without figuration (presumed lost type: a *nomen dubium*); based on Matheron’s description, the teeth are here questioned as possibly corresponding to *Acynodon* Buscalioni, Ortega & Vasse, 1997 (see below); the beds are given as latest Campanian in age (Diez Díaz *et al.*, 2012) and this is the most recent known evidence of a Late Cretaceous crocodile in the Arc Syncline, at the time of Matheron (1869a, b, 1878). 2) The dinosaurian *Rabdodon priscum* Matheron, 1869a (pls. 4, 5). The genus is mentioned in various European Campanian and Maastrichtian (i.e. late Campanian or early Maastrichtian) beds (Broin *et al.*, 1980; Buffetaut *et al.*, 1996, 1999; Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015; and others). 3): Indeterminate chelonians: According to the ornamentation indicated by Matheron (1869a), these chelonians belong to the helochelydrid solemydine *Solemys* sp. and to an indetermined foxemydid bothremydid, both of which were collected later in the region (Broin *et al.*, 1980; Tong *et al.*, 1998) and widely distributed in the Late Campanian in southern France and Spain.

(b) The upper Rognacien part of the Upper limestones (limestone of the Rognac bar and silty marls) did not yield any reptiles to Matheron (1869a). Westphal & Durand (1990) considered the upper Rognacien samples present sections of successive normal and reverse

polarity, corresponding to several Chrons, from C33n top part (above the lower Rognacian part) up to C29r, at K/T boundary.

The Rognac station limestone and the Rognac bar limestone have thus been successively positioned (Westphal & Durand, 1990, fig. 8; Garcia & Vianey-Liaud, 2001, fig. 4) in these short, alternately reversed and normal anomalies of the Late Cretaceous, presumably including the Maastrichtian. At the time of Westphal & Durand (1990) (see above), the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary was fixed at ca. 74 Ma, in the upper part of the C33n period, and since the new calibration of the geochronological scale by Gradstein *et al.* (1995) set the boundary at 71.2 Ma, the Rognac limestone became partly older in the Upper Cretaceous. The new stage boundary was set at the C32n2n period, i.e. high within this anomaly (Coccioni & Premoli-Silva, 2015) or without precision in C32n2n above the C32r1r anomaly (Ogg, 2020). The Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary position in the Arc syncline has been questioned by Garcia & Vianey-Liaud (2001, fig. 4): given as not being clearly positioned, based on egg studies, the authors show that all the Rognac railway station limestone layers could cover the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary. Sites (such as the Nerthe tunnel of *Cr. vetustus* and *Rhadodon priscum*) are late Campanian clearly positioned lithologically below the lower Rognac railway station limestone. Above, the Rognac railway station limestone (with the Rognac bar limestone), with dinosaur eggs but no crocodylian elements mentioned, remain of Maastrichtian age (GTS of Gradstein *et al.*, 2012) (Coccioni & Primoli Silva, 2015; Garcia & Vianey-Liaud, 2001, fig. 4; Scott, 2014; Tabuce *et al.*, 2013).

Finally, the Fuveau lignite Formation (Fuveau s. s.), earlier Campanian, is clearly distinguished from the upper Campanian Begudo-early Rognacian part – composed of detrital clays and sandstone and marl layers with reptiles.

3.1.4. Last upper aureole, “Étage rutilant garumnien” of Matheron (1869a), “Vitrollien” Matheron, 1878. Map of the outcrop of the Vitrollian, in the Rognacian chapter, fig. 1 of Babinot & Durand (1980).

Matheron (1869a) mentioned this layer, which he said did not yield any vertebrate, as belonging to the Upper Garumnian in Provence, in the Cretaceous. This local Garumnian stage, defined by Leymerie (1868) in the Pyrenean region, includes levels from the Maastrichtian to the Palaeocene, according to the southwestern regions (France and Spain: Puértolas-Pascual *et al.*, 2018). In Provence, Westphal & Durand (1990) positioned the Vitrollian in anomalies C29 and C28, corresponding to the Danian, Lower Palaeocene (Cenozoic), in accordance with recent data, the K/T limit being set at approximately 66 Ma.

3.2. The palynological data

The data provided by D. Pons from the *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* matrix clearly support a Campanian age consistent with the previously studied Fuveau palynoflora. Pons considers that the Fuvelian palynoflora shows similarities with floras of the Upper Campanian, i.e. the middle-upper part of the Campanian (Pons, personal communication). It does not express the chronostratigraphic position in the Lower Campanian of the Fuveau Formation of Westphal & Durand (1990) (age elevation of the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary having been integrated). The upper limit of the Campanian – according to the inclusion in the upper Campanian of the Begudian and the base of the Rognacian – is not well redefined in view of the palynological data. The age of the Fuveau lignitic palynoflora is not redefined based on its clearly established chronostratigraphic position relative to other comparable palynofloras, such as those of the Early Campanian of Villeveyrac (previously considered slightly different from that of Fuveau, according to D. Pons), and that (not revised) of the Campanian part of Tercis-les-Bains (Odin & Lamaurelle, 2004). Nevertheless, this preliminary palynological point of view is important to consider, because it is this palynoflora extracted from the matrix of the Alès specimen that confirmed its Upper Cretaceous Campanian age and confirmed it with the Fuveau lignitic Formation, in concordance with the type series of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*.

3.3. Stratigraphic position of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* compared with that of the other Campanian western allodaposuchids (Tabl. 1)

Before studying the morphology of the new Fuveau crocodile specimen, other Campanian crocodylian species need to be stratigraphically resituated, for comparison. The palaeomagnetic position of the Fuveau lignite Formation in the early Campanian comforts a comparison previously done with the Olivet Formation of Villeveyrac (Hérault). The Olivet site is constituted of limestone and grey marls with lignitic intercalation. It was dated as Fuvelian, early Campanian by Buffetaut *et al.* (1996). Palaeomagnetostratigraphic studies of Benammi *et al.* (2006) confirmed this age. They have attributed the site to the chron C33.1r, corresponding to lower and base of the middle Campanian, with an age of 83.5 to 79.5 Ma (Benammi *et al.*, 2006; Garcia *et al.*, 2015). The site has yielded (Buffetaut *et al.*, 1996) a “Trematochampsidae indet.” crocodile [without figuration]: “Trematochampsids are represented by stout blunt teeth with an enamel ornamented with sinuous ridges and granulous carinae. These teeth are similar to those from the Fuvelian of the Fuveau basin, which were

named *Crocodylus affuvelensis* by Matheron (1869)” [pl. 1, figs 6–8]. That description is concordant with that of the posterior teeth of *Ma. affuvelensis* (Fig. 4B). It does not appear as being from *Acynodon*, a genus with another tooth ornamentation (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997, 1999; Blanco *et al.*, 2020; Ösi, 2013), and not yet known as represented in Fuveau lignites. In conformity with allodaposuchids including *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*, the Olivet Formation provided procoelous eusuchian vertebrae: “Eusuchia indet.” agreeing with those of *Massaliasuchus*. The presence of *Ma. affuvelensis* at Villeveyrac is possible, but not yet asserted. In conformity with the Fuveau lignites, this Villeveyrac locality shares the presence of *Polysternon provinciale* (Matheron, 1869a) (figured in Buffetaut *et al.*, 1996). This turtle attribution to the Fuveau species is well asserted. It is comforted by new abundant unpublished turtle material from Villeveyrac (Montpellier: USTL coll., and Costa coll.; Poitiers: UP, Paleovprim coll.). During the late Cretaceous, Fuveau has produced the oldest attested allodaposuchid, although possibly also Villeveyrac. No other potential European allodaposuchid species is as low in the Campanian series.

Three other western European localities with allodaposuchid forms, have also been dated as Campanian, thanks to palaeomagnetism or correlation. They are claimed to be younger than the Fuveau lignite formation and older than the typical *Allodaposuchus precedens* site in Romania, dated to the Maastrichtian. They are clearly posterior to Fuveau lignite and Olivet (Villeveyrac) formations, but also anterior to the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary. Their lithologic position is located above the fuvelian lignite layers. It is demonstrated here that the allodaposuchids they yielded are transitional in time between *Massaliasuchus* and *Allodaposuchus precedens*. 1) The Begudian Velaux-La Bastide Neuve (Bouches-du-Rhône, France) (Fig. 1) (VBN in Martin *et al.*, 2015) (late Campanian, Begudian), is part of the Arc syncline. It has yielded *Allodaposuchus precedens* (Martin *et al.*, 2015), which became *Allodaposuchus iberoarmoricanus* (Blanco, 2021). The site consists in fluviolacustrine sandstone, clays and limestone, stratigraphically positioned 15 m below the historical Lower Rognac Limestone Formation (Rognac railway station). It is positioned (Martin *et al.*, 2015) in the biozone of the Chrons C32n–C32r by the charophytes association; that is correlated by the presence of the dinosaur egg oospecies *Megaloolithus aureliensis*. This oospecies begins in the C32r and continues in the C32n period (according to Garcia & Vianey-Liaud, 2001). This duration spans the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary, as defined by Coccioni & Premoli Silva (2015) and Ogg (2020) at 72.17 Ma. The site of Velaux-La Bastide Neuve being in a lower lithologic position compared to the railway limestone of Rognac, its late Campanian age is confirmed. 2) At Fox-Amphoux

(Var, Provence) (Fig. 1), *Allodaposuchus cf. precedens* recorded by Martin (2010b), became *Lohuecosuchus mechinorum* Narváez *et al.*, 2015. The “Métisson” domain, the original site of the Fox-Amphoux locality (Lapparent, 1938, 1947; Broin *et al.* 1980) is made up of sandstone and clay layers; they are considered to be correlatively located, by lithology, under the level of the Rognac limestone. They are located (by correlation) under the Rognac railway station limestone, lower to the Rognac bar, being late Campanian in age, contrary to an upper-Maastrichtian age previously proposed, notably in Broin *et al.* (1980). This results from the elevation of the Campanian – Maastrichtian boundary at 71.7 Ma instead of 74 M (Gradstein, 2012). Díez Díaz *et al.* (2012) stated: “The composition of the reptile assemblage from Fox-Amphoux-Métisson and the co-occurrence of dinosaur eggs belonging to the Lower Rognacian oospecies *Megaloolithus siruguei* and *Cairanoolithus dughii* indicate that this locality is Late Campanian in age” (see Garcia & Vianey-Liaud, 2001). 3) In Spain, the fluvial vertebrate site Laño 1 (Pereda-Suberbiola *et al.*, 2015; Corral *et al.*, 2021), Sedano Formation, yielded *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997. It is positioned below a marine Maastrichtian level; it has been dated “as the latest Campanian in age as it falls within the C32n (≈72–73.5 Ma)” (Corral *et al.*, 2016). The C32n Chron space is the limit space for the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary. As seen above, Ogg (2020) gives the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary at the base of chron C32n2n, at 72.17 Ma, above the C32r.1r Chron. While Coccioni & Premoli-Silva (2015) positioned this boundary at the end of the C32n.2n, below the C32n.1r Chron. Anyway, the very basal position of the Laño vertebrate site, given in the Sedano Formation (Corral *et al.*, 2016, fig. 3), agrees with a basal position in the Chron C32n.2n, falling in the latest Campanian just below the Campanian-Maastrichtian boundary. Thus, the age Laño is close to that of Velaux-La Bastide Neuve (Begudian), clearly above the Fuveau lignite and the Villeveyrac-Olivet formations, both located in the C33 Chron and correlated with an earlier Campanian. The examined morphology of *Mu. buffetauti*, previously considered as possibly synonym of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*, is considered here to be different from – but closest to – that of *Ma. affuvelensis* among the allodaposuchids (Tabl. 1, list) (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1999, Narváez *et al.*, 2015). This observation is consistent with this proximity in age. Fuveau, Laño and Velaux do not share the same allodaposuchid species (Tabls 1, 3). But, as confirmed by Buscalioni *et al.* (1997, 1999), is it shown below how *Mu. buffetauti* shares some dental characters only with *Ma. affuvelensis*, although *Mu. buffetauti* may also share some more derived characters with the Velaux *Allodaposuchus precedens/iberoarmoricanus* and other Ibero-French Campanian-Maastrichtian forms (Tabl. 1).

4. SYSTEMATIC PALAEOLOGY

Order Crocodylia Gmelin, 1789

Suborder Eusuchia Huxley, 1875

Family Allodaposuchidae Narváez *et al.*, 2015

Genus *Massaliasuchus* Martin & Buffetaut, 2008

Type species: *Crocodylus affuvelensis* Matheron, 1869a: p. 359

Massaliasuchus affuvelensis (Matheron, 1869a)

Figs 2, 3, 4, 5

2008: *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869a): Martin & Buffetaut, 2008: 572

Locality and age. Fuveau-Gardanne Lignite mining Basin, HBCM, Arc syncline, (Bouches-du-Rhône, Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur area, Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region, France) (Fig. 1). Fuveau lignite Formation, lower part of the two "Étages de Fuveau" Matheron 1869a. "Fuvélien" Matheron, 1878 lower part: Fuvelian s. s. Late Cretaceous, early Campanian, inferior Cr33r anomaly.

Fuveau lignite crocodylian material

Syntype and newly referred material:

MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 (provisional Alès number MMEMA, F 1660), left partial lower jaw with teeth (Figs 2–5 A), original and cast in MHNA; casts in MMG, MNHN. F Paris, MHNM, UL1-ENSL. MHNM.6034.11719.5, fragment of the dentary with teeth (Fig. 5B). MHNM.4759, syntype of Matheron (1869a): fragment of the head with remains of two maxillae, lower and upper, each with some posterior teeth in Matheron, 1869a, pl. 1, fig. 7 (original specimen not found, observed here by its figuration). MHNM.6034.11719.5, fragment of the dentary with posterior teeth (Fig. 5B) (Martin's observation and photograph), Series of twelve MHNM teeth (Fig. 3D–O) various anterior and middle teeth (Martin's observation and photograph) including Matheron's figured syntypes (1869a, pl. 1). Matheron's syntypes, 1869a, pl. 1: MHNM.4759.32, fig. 6b (Fig. 3E) (possible maxillary tooth), MHNM.4759.29, fig. 6c, d (Fig. 3H) (caniniform tooth), MHNM.4759.8 (possible Matheron, 1869a's fig. 6a) (Fig. 3J) (not positioned on the skull or lower jaw). And not figured teeth by Matheron (1869): MHNM.4759.28 (Fig. 3D); MHNM.4759.27 (Fig. 3 F); MHNM.4759. 23 (Fig. 3G); MHNM.4759. 12 (Fig. 3I); MHNM.4759.4 (Fig. 3K); MHNM.4759. 3 (Fig. 3L); MHNM.4759.5 (Fig. 3M); MHNM.4759.1 (Fig. 3N); MHNM.4759. 2 (Fig. 3O).

Syntype postcranial material, observation by Martin & Buffetaut (2008): figured specimens by Matheron (1869a), pl. 1: MHNM 6034.11719.4, fragment of femur (fig. 1a–c) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4M–O); MHNM.6034.11719.1, coracoid (fig. 2a–d) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4B–E); MHNM.6034.11719.3, centrum of vertebra (Matheron's "vingt-deuxième

vertèbre",. 3a, b) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4I–J); MHNM.6034.11719.5, centrum of vertebra ("vingt-troisième vertèbre", fig. 4a–b) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4K–L); MHNM.6034.11719.2, a dorsal vertebra ("vingt-troisième vertèbre", fig. 5 a–c) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4F–H).

Material currently not localised: Syntype mandibular ramus of *Crocodylus affuvelensis* Matheron, 1869a (pl. 1, fig. 8); also figured by Répelin (1930), formerly preserved as a plaster cast at MHNM (reproduced pl. 1 in Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4A). According to Matheron (1869a) it was part: "of a new collection due to M. Biver, principal agent of the concessionary company of Gréasque and Fuveau mines" [in French]. – Syntype part of a lower-left "maxilla" (Matheron, 1869a, pl.1, fig. 7).

Material of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869) used for the genus *Massaliasuchus* erection, by Martin & Buffetaut (2008), with authors' figures. MHNM. 15'427.0, suggested neotype, cranium from the posterior end of the naris to the anteriormost corner of the supratemporal fenestrae – Valdonne, Grande Mine, Bouches-du-Rhône (Fig. 2). MHNM. 10'834.0, rostrum and mandible in occlusion – Valdonne, Bouches-du-Rhône (Fig. 3). MHNM. 482.1: regions of the orbits and a portion of the mandible (Fig. 3) and 482.2: a portion of the rostrum – Lignites de Fuveau, Bouches-du-Rhône. MHNM. 10833.1: the anteriormost portion of the rostrum (Fig. 3). Possible other unpublished specimens from the Aix-en-Provence area are preserved in the MHNM, le Comte de Gérin-Ricard coll. included (Ch. Borrelly pers. com.).

Other preserved Fuveau lignite crocodylian material:

Crocodylus blavieri Gray, 1831: "*Croc. Blavieri*. *Croc. de Provence*, Cuv. Os. Foss. v. 164, t. 6, f. 17. Fossil in the Lignite of Provence" in Gray (1831). In Matheron (1869a): from the "Mène de quatre pans" lignite layer at Mimet (Bouches-du-Rhône)" (Fig. 1) ; and according to Cuvier's inscription: "M. Blavier a trouvé dans le milieu d'une couche de charbon de terre, dite des Quatre Pans, à Mimet (Fig. 1) Bouches-du-Rhône...", "Des os de crocodiles des lignites de PROVENCE": Cuvier, (1824, p. 165, pl. 6, fig. 17; 1836 p. 526), Atlas pl. 234, fig. 17. Nomen dubium (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008), the holotype specimen is the proximal part of a femur, MNHN. F. AC-1861.8704. gift of M. Blavier. Chief Ingenior, he was the first operator (1821) of the bauxite aluminium stone from Baux de Provence region. *Crocodylus blavieri* might be or not a senior synonym of *Crocodylus affuvelensis* Matheron (1869a). Matheron compared the two femurs: holotype of *C. blavieri* help to Cuvier's figure, and his syntype femur part of *C. affuvelensis*, MHNM 6034.11719.4. He morphologically distinguished them, a statement which cannot be discussed in the view of the description and poor figuration, and even if femurs of *Cr. blavieri* and *Cr. affuvelensis* are both in hands: the *Cr. blavieri* holotype is preserved by the proximal

Fig. 2. *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869), Gardanne-Fuveau-Valdonne mining basin (HBCM), Fuveau lignite Formation, early Campanian. Part of lower jaw, MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1. A, B, C, D, left lateral (labial), medial (lingual), ventral and dorsal views. Abbreviations: 1 to 16, teeth; dent, dentary; r, 16th tooth root; sp, splenial; sp ex, splenial anterior extremity; sp sut, dentary suture mark of inferior splenial part. Scale bar, 30 mm.

midpart of the femur, while the “Cr.” *affivelensis* femur is preserved by a medial proximo-diaphyse part, without the proximal head. Both specimens have in common the size and global appearance and the fourth trochanter area (its presence and size). They will be later compared, testing if several crocodile species can surely be differentiated on such femur parts, and notably within allodaposuchids.

4.1. Description of the new specimens of *Massaliasuchus affivelensis* from Fuveau

New dentary MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, fragment MHN.M.6034.11719.5 and series of twelve MHN teeth, including some syntypes teeth of *Massaliasuchus affivelensis* (Matheron, 1869a) (pl. 1, figs 6–8).

4.1.1. Morphology of the lower jaw MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 (Figs 2–5)

Preservation: it consists of a left dentary, posteriorly broken after the 16th tooth, ventrally toward the anterior point of the angular, indicating that an external mandibular fossa was possibly absent. The splenial is mostly preserved, medially against the dentary, and missing the posterior part, and the ventral part below the Meckel canal where the print of its surface is preserved. The teeth 4, 8, 11 to 15 are complete, the teeth 2, 9, 10 and 16 are cut more or less close to the base, and the teeth 1, 3, 5, 6 and 7 are fully missing, their alveolus being filled by lignite. An oblique very slight mesio-distal torsion (external to internal) affects the posterior 11th to 14th teeth position in the alveoli, and the splenial is completely applied over some medio-posterior tooth roots.

Dentary bone ornamentation: The preserved lateroexternal (labial) surface of the dentary is ornamented by elongated vermiculations, separated by sinuous sulci which anastomose by place, isolating variably short to long pits, and, along with the corresponding symphysis part, some isolated nutritive punctiform ones (Fig. 2A). In a short upper part of the labial face, approximately from the diastema between teeth 7#8 up to the posterior extremity, the surface is devoid of vermiculations. It forms a smooth facet on a height of 0.5 to 0.9 cm, indicating the pattern of labial (external) maxillary over lingual (inner) dentary occlusion. The facet overhangs the decorated surface; its inferior border, at the dorsal limit of the vermiculated surface, is undulated and punctuated by vascular foramina. Posteroinferiorly, the vermiculations become longer and wider rounded crests, toward the anterior angular extremity position, forming like three nested rounded arrowheads, probably being part of the external surface of the angular anterior extremity ornamentation.

General morphology of the dentition state (Figs 2–5) (Tabl. 2): Conforming to the syntype figures of dentary and isolated teeth (Matheron’s 1869a, pl. 1, fig. 8), the specimen MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 possesses a heterodont dentition of brevirostrine form.

Teeth are bicarinated, not denticulated, contrary to other European brevirostrine forms such as Eusuchian Pristichampsinae, and such as Mesoeucrocodylian forms, Gondwanian in origin, among which the Austrian *Doratodon* (Buffetaut, 1979; Csiki-Sava, 2015) and the Ibero-French *Iberosuchus* (see Godinot *et al.*, 2018). The carinae form a thin acute tooth border, not being protruded above the root and crown base. The preserved sixteen teeth of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, irregularly spaced, house in oval alveoli for an oval tooth section. Eleven of the alveoli contain more to less preserved teeth (Figs 2–5): seven teeth are complete (teeth 4, 8, 11 to 15), one misses the apex (the 10th) and the crown apex of 2^d, 9th and 16th is obliquely more broken.

Massaliasuchus affivelensis MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 lower jaw size: Among compared crocodiles, it is slender (not deep compared to its length) (Tabl. 2). Compared to juvenile and adult dentary specimens of *Diplocynodon* and *Crocodylus niloticus*, the specimen appears as a grown adult specimen by the density of the bone, the depth of the preserved teeth, fully filling the alveoli, the fully developed specimen in height with clear established heterodonty along the dentary (identified by the relative size and shape of the teeth), and the fully sutured splenial to the dentary. It was not the larger available *Ma. affivelensis* specimen, according to the size of Matheron’s and Martin & Buffetaut’s specimens. By its measures (Tabl. 2) and by comparison, the full dentary series of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 was a little shorter than that of *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* from Laño (ca 124 mm, with a complete lower jaw of ca. 242 mm, for a skull

Tabl. 2. Measurements of the specimen MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 (in mm). Abbreviations: dw1, dorsal width at tooth 4; dw2, dorsal width at tooth 11; h1, height at tooth 4 (at mid-alveolus length); h2, minimal dentary height, between teeth 7 and 8; h3, height at tooth 11 (at mid-alveolus length); h4, height at tooth 16 (at mid-alveolus length); h5, symphysis, medial maximal height; L1, full preserved length; L2, length between teeth 4 and 11; L3, length between teeth 4 and 16; L4, symphysis length; Sp h, full splenial height; Sp dh, dorsal preserved part of splenial height; Sym h x L, symphysis height at tooth 4 and length.

h1	h2	h3	h4	h5
25.5	17.5	24	29	13.5
L1	L2	L3		L4
111	78	42		34
dw1	dw2	Sp h	Sp dh	Sym h x L
18	11	20	16	14 x 33

Fig. 3. *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869), Gardanne-Fuveau-Valdonne mining basin (HBCM), Fuveau lignite Formation, early Campanian. Lower jaw part MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1. A-C, occlusal views; A, photograph with superposed drawing layer, B, photograph, C, drawing, dorsal occlusal views. Abbreviations: 1 to 16, teeth; bul, bulges around teeth 5–6 and 7; c, 16th tooth crown; f, displaced dentary fragment hiding 3^d tooth; r, 16th tooth root. dd, dentary dorsal face; dsp, splenial extremity at dorsal border; medd+sp, medial dentary face covered by splenial; spex, anterior splenial extremity at the symphysis posterior end; pale grey, preserved crown surface; dark grey, cut crown and root surface; black, coal filling the alveolus. A-C, scale bar, 20 mm. D to O, twelve isolated teeth, MHNM: D 4759.28, E 4759.32 (Matheron's syntype pl. 1, 6a, b), F 4759.27, G 4759.23, H 4759.29 (Matheron's syntype pl. 1, 6c d), I 4759.12, J 4759.8, K 4759.4, L 4759.3, M 4759.5, N 4759.1, O 4759.2, scale bar, 10 mm. P, MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, lateral dentary view showing the measurements location on the external labial view: Abbreviations: h1, h2, h3, h4, height of the dentary at tooth 4, between teeth 7 and 8, and at teeth 11 and 16; h5, maximal height of the symphysis, posteriorly; L1, full preserved dentary length; L2, length between teeth 4–11 and 4–16, at middle alveolus length, Q, MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, anterior dentary showing the maximal symphysis height h5; white bars; measures in Table 2.

which might have reached 228–230 mm), by comparison with the skull and lower jaw of *Agaresuchus fontisensis*, for example (Tabl. 1). If put at the same lower jaw height, MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 might have belonged to a skull of ca 200 mm long at least (220 mm?) up to the quadrate condyle. By comparison, the neotype skull MHNM 15427.0. of *Ma. affivelensis* Martin & Buffetaut, 2008 might have reached ca. 250 mm: other named allodaposuchids (Tabl. 1) have adult skulls ranging from 385 to 430 mm (up to the quadrate condyle extremities or up to the supraoccipital rim, according to authors' data). In *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis* (missing a complete skull, only a premaxilla being preserved beside the lower jaw), the nearly complete and deformed lower jaw branch is preserved on 580–610 mm, for a great skull of more than 450 mm; *Lohuecosuchus megadontos* has a lower jaw of 470 mm for a skull length of 385 mm (from the snout tip to the posterior margin of the quadrate condyle) (Narváez *et al.*, 2015). Thus, *Ma. affivelensis* is known by relatively small specimens. *Mu. buffetauti* lower jaw excepted (the tooth series of which being close in length to that of *Ma. affivelensis*), the species is relatively small by comparison with all the other known allodaposuchid species listed in Table 1.

Dentary waves (festoons): As seen in lateral view (Figs 2A, 3P), the dorsal border of the tooth row shows three waves or festoons (an anterior and a double posterior festonation), as in the syntype of Matheron (1869, pl. 1 fig. 8) and the specimen MHNM. 10'834.0 of Martin & Buffetaut (2008, fig. 3 C). The first anterior festoon bears alveoli 1 to 7; its maximal height (Fig. 3P, h1) corresponds to alveolus #4, and its dorsal border lowers at the level of alveoli #5 to 7, in a relatively abrupt slope (ca 40°). The obtuse angle of the slopes between the first two festoons is of ca. 130° and the angle (at h2) is barely rounded. The surface of the tooth 1 alveolus is barely visible as a thin compressed black line of coal. The tooth 2, also compressed, is reduced to a short oval crown part, and the smaller tooth 3 alveolus is nearly completely hidden by the small fragment of broken and displaced dorsal symphysis bone. The medial wall of the tooth 4 alveolus is slightly elevated against the tooth crown, in a weak medial bulge. The tooth 4 crown is the longest preserved one of the series; its alveolus is barely longer than those of the posterior teeth 10 and 11, the 11th crown being barely less mesiodistally long than – or as long as the 10th, that is slightly crushed). At the base of the alveoli 5, 6 and 7, on the descending slope of the first festoon, the dentary surface is elevated in two small bulges, letting see only thin black areas of coal, filling each tooth alveolus hole, without crown elements (Figs 3 A-C).

The second marked festoon rises with an abrupt slope, at the level of alveolus #8, reaches a peak height at the level of alveoli #10–11 (Fig. 3P, h3) and the border

follows with a low inflection at the level of alveolus #13 corresponding to the weak angle between a 2d festoon and a 3d weak festoon (weak undulation in the second festoon border of Eusuchian heterodont forms). The later forms an angle of ca. 150°, being wider than the one between 1st and 2d festoons, and it draws a much obtuse curve. Here, forming the slight upward slope of the 3rd festoon, the dentary border rises slightly, with teeth 14 to 16; it is cut there at the last tooth, as in the figured syntype of Matheron, normally anterior to an elevation towards the posterior end, as exists in this syntype (1869a, pl. 1, fig. 8). The posterior part of the dentary bears the teeth 8–16. On the second festoon top, the tooth 10 (obliquely broken at its apex, and its crown, being slightly basally crushed), was the longer and higher posterior tooth. The minimal dentary height (h2) is positioned at the level of the diastema between alveoli #7–8 (Tabl. 2, Figs. 2 A-B, 3P). Complete preserved posterior crowns include the tooth 11, also on the 2nd festoon top (ca. 7.8 mm on 8 mm of crown height); then, on the weak descending slope, the tooth 12 (obliquely artificially inclined mesiodistally in its alveolus); and positioned in the bottom of the slight inflection between festoons 2 and 3, is the tooth 13; it is slightly medially inclined (being pushed postmortem into its root alveolus part). Posteriorly, on the slight elevating part of the festoon 3, are the teeth 14 and 15, slightly inclined externally; their root appears medially, being broken in their inferior part; posteriorly, the 16th tooth crown is obliquely broken nearly completely: its full root appears posteriorly, from base to top, doing the posterior extremity of the specimen.

Anterior dentary part: symphysis (Figs 2A, B; 3P) (principal measures in Tabl. 2): The symphysis border (Figs 2B, C, D, 3P) is partly antero-externally slightly compressed in dorsal view, doing a postmortem slight incurvation at the lateral border (Fig. 2D): it is a particular artefact at tooth 2 border, instead of a straight (or rounded) external anterior border from teeth 1 to 4, as in other compared crocodiles. A fragment of symphysis bone is pushed over the 3rd tooth and at 4th proximal basis (Fig. 3A, B). Posteriorly, the dorsal symphysis surface area is medially slightly obliquely downward incurved, up to the extremity at the upper rise of the splenial dorsal border, at its more dorsal alveolar level at tooth 11.

The lower jaw has a relatively short symphysis for crocodiles, not exceeding in length the level of the tooth 6 (Fig. 2D). It is relatively short for its height, when comparing it to *Crocodylus niloticus*, giving them both the same relative height at tooth 4. In lateral view (Fig. 2A, B), the symphysis angle (positioning the vertex at the ventral surface, one angle side at the vertical of the mid alveolus surface length of the tooth 4, and the other angle side directed to the surface of the tooth 1 at its mid-length), is of ca. 42° in MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1. In *Cr. niloticus*, the symphysis being relatively longer

Fig. 4. *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* (Matheron, 1869), Gardanne-Fuveau-Valdonne mining basin (HBCM), Fuveau lignite Formation, early Campanian. Lower jaw part MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1. Teeth enlargement: A1, A2, left tooth 4 in medial (lingual) and lateral (labial) views; B1, B2, teeth 12 and 11 in lingual views; C, tooth 11 in occlusal view (anterior at the right side). Scale bars, 5 mm.

for the height, this angle is ca. 53° (Blainville, 1855, *Cr. "vulgaris"*, pl. 2), to 60° (young MNHN. F.REP 100, Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002, pl. IIb), not far from the angle of 55° in *Osteolaemus tetraspis*. Both extant species, *Cr. niloticus* and *Os. tetraspis* (fig. in Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002), have the teeth further apart on a longer occlusal dentary border relative to dentary height, including this difference in symphysis in relative length and angle. In *Massaliasuchus affivelensis*, in occlusal view, the distance between teeth 1 and 4 (Fig. 2D) is short, their implantation being in a relative straight line. The symphysis extends from the anterior tip of the dentary to the level of the middle to the extremity of the 6th tooth, where it contacts the anterosuperior splenial process (Fig. 2B). The symphysis medial suture, clearly longer than high, is not deformed (Figs 2B, 3P; Tabl. 2). Posteriorly to the symphysis, the dentary follows medially with the slightly medially flattened splenial at tooth roots contact. At contact with the symphysis, the splenial anterodorsally begins by an upper-bulging part, the anterosuperior process, and ventrally by the print of the anteroinferior process, both processes delimiting between them the sulcus of the Meckel canal. Being part of the symphysis posterior border only, the splenial does not anteriorly participate to the symphysis length. Above the Meckel canal, the full superior splenial part misses its posterior end, from the tooth root 14 and on, to the posterior extremity. Below the canal, its missing lower part presence is indicated by a striated marked dentary surface, which tapers posteriorly with the enlargement of the Meckel canal (Fig. 2B sp, C, sp ex; Fig. 3C, spex). Thus viewed, the splenial covered most of the lingual postsymphysis surface of the dentary section. Its dorsal border elevates from its anteromedial symphysis contact, being anteriorly slightly inferior to the upper dorsomedially incurved surface of the symphysis; it reaches the more dorsal dentary surface at the mid-length of the tooth 11 level (Fig. 2D, sp). At this level toward posteriorly, the splenial becomes compressed against the teeth roots, up to the tooth 13 included, its convex external face fitting the teeth roots cylindrical contours. The splenial maximal preserved superior part is 16 mm high (at tooth 11), on 20 mm full jaw height, its print surface of the missing inferior part being included (Fig. 2B, Tabl. 2).

Dentary teeth proportion in length on the sequence: Alveolus 3, and alveoli 5 to 7 were less long than the 4th, 2^d and 1st ones and the 4th tooth base occupy the third of the symphysis length. The occlusal length of the seven anterior alveoli of the first festoon and of their interspaces they occupied on the dentary is shorter than the dentary length that is occupied by the posterior teeth and interspaces (from the 8th to 16th): it is of 4.2 cm long against 6.3 cm. The posterior teeth are all mesiodistally longer than the anterior ones, the dentary longest 4th excepted (Figs 2D, 3 A-C). The distribution of teeth in two main waves (festoons), the

second one being divided in two sub-festoons, conforms to that of extant brevirostrine forms. Such as *Crocodylus niloticus* and *Osteolaemus tetraspis* (Blainville, 1855, pl. 2; Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002, pl. 1, 2); and as well as in alligatoroids forms, among other brevirostrine Eusuchian forms (Blainville, 1855, pl. 2; Martin *et al.*, 2014; Vaillant, 1872).

Direction, contours and relative size of the dentary teeth by category: Pointed teeth, anterior and median teeth 1 to 10. The size of the anterior missing teeth is estimated by their alveolus length and then their possible height. The first tooth is anterodorsally directed, from its root direction in the symphysis (as seen laterally, Fig. 2A), compressed with the anterior symphysis part; although reduced to a thin black matrix line, it was mesiodistally longer than the second tooth, considering the occlusal volume and the estimated volume of its root in the anterior symphysis part; the 2nd crown length cut few above its base (also artificially compressed linguo-labially) was less long; both 1st and 2nd crowns seem to have been longer than the 3rd. This third (also occlusal reduced to a remnant of a black alveolus, hidden by the tiny displaced bone fragment), is joined against the 4th alveolus, and it was at least smaller than the 2nd. The 4th high caniniform crown, corresponding to the skull space between the premaxilla and the maxilla, is slightly elevated regarding the three anterior ones. Much pointed and slightly curved, it is the highest preserved crown in the series and the mesiodistally longest one: 13 mm in height, 8.5 mm in mesiodistal length on 6 mm linguolabially; it fully fills the alveolus. The 5th, 6th, and 7th teeth (on the descending slope of the first festoon) were smaller than the 4th according to their mark on the bulges (their alveolus being reduced to a thin black lignite mark on a slight elevation), the 7th being slightly greater, on its taller elevation. At the beginning of the ascending slope of the 2nd festoon, the pointed 8th (the first medioposterior tooth of the dentary series) is less high than the 4th, and less long: 3 mm mesiodistally long, 2 mm linguolabially wide and 4 mm high, and straight: it is the shortest in height and length among the well-preserved teeth and alveoli, posterior to the 4th. Following on the ascending slope of the second festoon, the teeth 9 (cut at the crown base) and 10 (ca. 8 mm, the longer and higher posterior tooth, cut at tip), grew in height and basal length after the 8th (according together to their ascending alveolus border in mesiodistal length and to their crown base length). They were probably pointed as the 8th, based on the syntype of Matheron (1869a, pl. 1, fig. 8), where pointed teeth 8–10 ascend and grow in height. However, they were either posteriorly inclined at the top, according to the syntype of Matheron (1869a, fig. 8), or not inclined as the 8th, according to a possible intraspecific variability known in *Lohuecosuchus megadontos* Narvéz *et al.*, 2015. 2).

"Blunt" teeth posterior set shape and relative proportions: "Blunt" means here all teeth 11–15 (16)

Fig. 5. *Massaliasuchus affivelensis* (Matheron, 1869), Gardanne-Fuveau-Valdonne mining basin (HBCM), Fuveau lignite Formation, early Campanian. A, Lower jaw part MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1. Enlarged teeth series 7 to 14, A1, A2, labial and lingual views. B, Fragment of the dentary with posterior teeth, MHN.M.6034.11719.5. B1, print of a crown and 3 teeth in external view; B2, left tooth of Fig. 4B1, probable tooth 13, with well visible root, compressed shape, and ornamentation, in oblique view. Scale bars, 10 mm.

are neither pointed nor conical; they are not “bulbous”, i.e. not fully blunt and bulbous, because they are clearly longer mesiodistally than linguolabially, oval in section and not thick inflated in volume (Figs 2D, 4C). On the second festoon, the 11th tooth is a little less long than the 10th, and barely less long than the 4th. The following ones, 12th up to 16th, are barely a little less mesiodistally long. The subset of teeth 11–12, of the rounding of the second festoon: both are relatively higher for their length than the following ones. They have a curved-rounded carina outline (in lateral view), going to a mesiodistally longer and rounder apex than the previous preserved pointed teeth, but the 11th has a minute point at its rounded top. The subsets 13–15 teeth (16th crown lacking) of the third festoon have a mesiodistally longer carina curve of the apex than all the other teeth, 11th and 12th included. The carina apex of the 15th tooth is nearly mesiodistally horizontal (Figs 2A, B; 5A). Thus, the posterior 13 to 15 lower crowns (16th crown being cut), lower and more rounded in lateral profile for an approximately similar length, appear as “blunter” teeth than the 11th and 12th.

Summary of relative teeth size: In decreasing height and mesiodistal length order (crown and/or the alveolus), greater dentary teeth are the 4th and the 10th (less high, mesiodistally as long as the 4th tooth). Teeth 5 to 7 were evidently smaller than the 4th, from the place and mark they occupy in length on the dentary; First tooth, oblique was taller than the 2nd and overall than the 3rd this (vertical) inserted against the high 4th, by the anterior inclination and height of the symphysis containing the roots; longer posterior teeth are also less high and long than 4th and 10th teeth.

Teeth relative distance, diastema (Tabls 1, 3): Length of the alveoli/teeth and distance between the alveoli must be distinguished. On the anterior part and 1st festoon, the teeth 1 and 2 are shortly distanced; the 2^d is clearly distanced from the 3^d, this being closer to the 4th alveolus border (Fig. 3C); by their approximation on this first festoon, the teeth 3 to 7 do a group of teeth in the dentary. The 4th is equally close to the 5th, itself nearly equally close to the 6th, and this only nearly as close to the 7th, marking a short interalveolar diastema 6th/7th. They are closer between them, slight diastema # 6/7 included, than to the 8th, on the second festoon ascending slope, with a clearly more important diastema between the 7th and 8th teeth (#7/8). This one is estimated as corresponding to the largest upper maxillary tooth. The teeth of the posterior dentary tooth group are relatively more distanced than those of the first festoon. The 8th is a little separated from the following 9th, by a short 8/9 diastema, shorter than between 7th and 8th teeth; the following 9th to 11th teeth are close (as the 3^d to 6th between them), doing a subgroup in tooth proximity (Fig. 5A2); their interalveolar spaces are shorter than those between the 12th to 16th teeth, which

are approximately as equally separated, and a little more distanced between them and from the tooth 11 (Fig. 5A2). To resume, marking diastema posterior to 4th teeth have a short interalveolar 6/7 space (# 6/7), dominant longer diastema between teeth 7 and 8 (# 7//8), and short 8/9 space (# 8/9). This distancing of MHN.AIX.PV.2023.15.1 teeth corresponds to the syntype of Matheron (1869a) (p. 11, fig. 7): groups of teeth 8–11 (including the short space between teeth 8/9), and the remaining group of the more distanced posterior teeth 12–15 (the 15th being the last figured tooth in the syntype).

Tooth detailed morphology: contours, sections, crown and root relation at collars: The crowns are more or less (according to their position) linguolabially compressed but do not have a circular section s. s. (Figs 2D, 3 A-C). This is valid as well for the thinned alveoli of the teeth 4–7, those implanted on the artefact domes (bulges), as for the other preserved teeth (Fig. 2D, 3 A-C, 4C). The preserved teeth have a more important labial face, and the lingual face is a little less wide and convex. The 4th tooth root is hidden, and its rounded protruding root volume is visible in the external face (Fig. 2A “4”) but its lateral border is dorsally straight (Fig. 3A-B in medioposterior teeth 12 and 13, Fig. 5A1, and Fig 5B1), the crown base appears as very slightly widened, just above the collar, in relation to the mesiodistal root length. The carina is barely protruding above the crown base at the root limit, its contour being just softly convex to straight toward the apex; and that does not produce a deep collar, a marked incurved sulcus between the carina and the root, and a thin protruding carina border. Some of the roots of the medioposterior teeth are covered by the crushed splenial in the lingual face, but their volume is visible as preserved below the splenial face (Figs 2B, 4B, 5A2). The posterior roots which are visible inferiorly to the carinae at their uncovered parts are those of the teeth 13–15. Those of teeth 14 and 15 are cylindrical (having parallel borders) just below the collar. The anterior ones, if not cylindrical (and if not by crushing), were possibly cylindrical or sub-cylindrical inferiorly in the alveolus; but they are evidently not much inflated below the collar, contrarily probably to the 4th. The roots are slightly flattened linguolabially according to the oval alveolus shape (Figs 2B, 4B, 5A2) and to the crown shape. The root lengths are thus slightly less long (mesiodistally) than the crown lengths (Figs 2B, 4B, 5A2): that is similar in the lost “*Crocodylus*” *affiuvensis* syntype of Matheron (1869a, pl. 1 fig. 7) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4P) and in MHN.M.6034.11719.5 (Fig. 5B). From the anterior symphysis lateral face part and its height, the teeth 1 to 3 had to have a cylindrical root, as in one syntype full tooth of Matheron (1869a, g fig. 1c-d) (Fig. 3H) (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4P), being inclined within the symphysis and not having a marked collar.

Crown surface (fluted, smooth surface, ridges):

1) Fluted caniniform tooth 4 (Figs 2, 3, 4A): curved anteroposteriorly and lingually, more convex labially with a wider surface than lingually, like the other teeth, but it is just more curved at the apex. To the naked eye, both surfaces have fine longitudinal cracks due to preservation, but the enamel surface appears smooth. On photographic enlargement, the labial surface is slightly fluted by some low and rounded ridges, at difference from other teeth. The surface being slightly eroded, only two anterior ridges are well visible in the inferior tooth height and three in the intermediary height (Fig. 4A2), doing, in total, eight labial ridges between the anterior and posterior carinae, only in the labial face. That is unlike various crocodiles, constituting a diagnostic character: *Crocodylus niloticus*, for example, often presents all the teeth with ridges, on both sides, and which are relatively narrower and more distanced between them. The *Massaliasuchus affivelensis* 4th tooth root not being visible, it is not seen if there were diverging root borders, inflated root, and, further, a crown partly wider or not than the crown base. But as seen above, according to its volume in the symphysis, the 4th root was slightly inflated, with divergent borders from the alveolus surface toward the base. This tooth is the one possible to compare to the figured isolated teeth of *Allodaposuchus precedens* in Martin *et al.* (2015).

2) Smooth teeth: preserved tooth 8 (Figs 2, 3, 5A1) and teeth 9–10. On the ascending slope of the 2nd festoon, tooth 8 is the smallest and shortest preserved tooth; linguolabially narrow and ovoid in section at the alveolus, as the 4th, but vertically pointed, not incurved mesiodistally or linguolabially. In lateral view, it has a slightly rounded upper part mesiodistally, thus beginning a feature of the posterior teeth by a minute perceptible horizontal carina apex. Its surface is smooth, not fluted; the enamel surface is just striated by cracks due to preservation. It seems to represent the smooth surface condition of the teeth 9 and 10, slightly linguolabially flattened, probably as that of the missing anterior teeth 1–3, 5–7. The crown of the tooth 9, higher than the 8th, is cut at the apex as the 10th: the ornamentation is not preserved, but if pointed as in the Matheron's syntype, the surface was smooth.

3) Medioposterior “ornamented” teeth 11–15 (16) (Figs 2, 3, 4 B-C, 5A). As seen above, teeth 11–15 are not bulbous in circumference and preserved ones (11 to 15) are not “worn” at tip, do not have a flat horizontal upper surface in “boot button tooth” as in some early Palaeogene French (Marne) *Allognathosuchus*-like forms (mentioned in Russell *et al.*, 1982) and *Allognathosuchus* from Germany (Ösi, 2013). According to their position, the mesiodistally rounded carina is more to less horizontal at the top: less in the set of higher teeth 11–12, more in the set of lower posterior 3–15 teeth (as seen above). From the 11th, these teeth have the very finely wrinkled-striated enamel, visible in macroscopic vision (Figs 4 and 5). It is done of very much fine sinuous ridges, arranged in a

network of anastomosed ridges in the inferomedian crown mid-part, these extremely fine ridges are not directed transversally at the carina border in this inferior part (Fig. 4B); basally remaining vertically parallel and just ending obliquely diverging at the lateral carina border, the ridges converge mediosuperiorly, irregularly and roundly, at the apex (Figs 4B1, B2, C). So that the carina border is not externally protruding and transversally minutely “festooned” (on the mid-upper part), by the angulous external extremity of each crown minute ridge, as seen in some other crocodiles such as “*Asiatosuchus*” group/*Isselosaurus doduni* (Gray, 1831) (Godinot *et al.*, 2018, fig. 8, N, O). Nor they have the smooth tooth surface of the ziphodont forms, with carina denticulations (festoons).

4.1.2. Comparison of the new fragment of lower jaw MHN.6034.11719.5 (Fig. 5B) with the new MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1 and the syntypes of Matheron

The new specimen MHN.6034.11719.5 is particularly similar, in terms of teeth, to the syntype specimen MHN.6034.11719.5 of Matheron (1869a pl. 1, fig. 7), as well as to the same part of the lost dentary figured syntype (pl. 1, fig. 8). It conforms to the new specimen MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1. In the syntype specimen of Matheron (1869a, fig. 8), behind the teeth 4, 8, 9, 10 slightly inclined backwards and pointed (the highest of the series after the 4th), the posterior teeth 12 to 15 constitute the same set as in the new specimen MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1. They are longer mesiodistally at alveolus than the preceding ones, appearing more rounded in sections. They have this kind of rounded carina contour toward the apex seen in the new specimen. Also in two subsets, the teeth 11 and 12 are a few higher (although relatively, the tooth 11 is few higher and the tooth 12 a few shorter), and both teeth 13 to 15 are a few shorter. On this figure, the collar is not clear but does not seem to be marked, as in MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1. The surface texture is not figured.

New MHN.6034.11719.5. It consists of the posterior part of a dentary, second-third festoons posterior to the 9–10th teeth in Fig. 5A1. It presents the print of a tooth and three teeth in lingual view. They correspond to teeth between the 11th and 15th of MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1. There is probably the print of the 11th tooth on the left side, and the teeth 12, 13 and 14 on the right (Fig. 5B1), by their lower size for the same width in relation to the anterior pointed teeth. They are low, not pointed, slightly linguolabially compressed. They have the same kind of rounded carina contour toward the apex, seen in the new specimen MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1 (Figs 2, 5A) and in the figured syntypes (pl. 1, figs 7, 8): being longer (mesiodistally at the base) than high and with a rounded-horizontal carina contour toward the apex, they are more to less mesiodistally “blunt” at the apex, not being fully bulbous in volume (Fig. 5B2). I. e. their section is not

fully circular, and the crown is not inflated all around the collar at the base. The one preserved on the left is higher (nearly as long as the high crown), with a more rounded-pointed tip than the anterior teeth, as the 12th of the syntype MHN.4759 of the fig. 8 of Matheron. The teeth are narrowly carinated without border denticulation on their thin carina. In magnified view, they have a finely striated enamel, in a network at the inferior part, similarly to that of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, done by roundly/parallel fine ridges converging toward the apex. They have a similar cylindrical root, below the unmarked collar in a groove, the root being mesiodistally only slightly shorter than the crown. These teeth, with their “compressed-rounded” crown with a “curved-horizontal” apex, their ornamented enamel and their cylindrical roots, conform to the posteriormost teeth of the specimens of Matheron (1869a, pl. 1, figs 7–8); as well as of the MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1, sharing the ornamentation visible in magnified view.

The MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 dentition is thus that of the Matheron’s syntype (1869a, pl. 1, fig. 8): a first sequence of variably high and long anterior and medioposterior pointed teeth, followed by posterior teeth in two sets after the 10th: one set of a higher anterior teeth with a narrower tip, and one set of lower posterior ones, this with teeth having a more rounded to horizontal in profile apex contour. The dentary festoonation corresponds to the maxillary one of the neotype of *Allodaposuchus precedens* in Narváez *et al.*, 2019 (fig. 3C).

4.1.3. Comparison with the series of twelve isolated teeth from the Fuveau lignite layers (Fig. 3 D-O)

This preserved MHN.4759 series of twelve teeth (photographed by Jérémy Martin, 2007–2008) is being compared in a preliminary manner with the figured and new material, pending future enlarged photographs. It includes:

- The slender caniniform anterior syntype tooth MHN.4759.29 with a long root, of Matheron (1869a, pl. I, fig. 6c-d) (Fig. 3H).
- A tooth MHN.4759.8 rather identical to that of Matheron 1869a, pl. 1, fig. 6a (Fig. 3J), also similar to the tooth MHN.4759.12 (Fig. 3I).
- The syntype tooth MHN.4759.32 of Matheron 1869a, pl. 1, fig. 6b (Fig. 3E), a probable maxillary tooth (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 4P).
- And eight other unpublished teeth MHN.4759- 8 (Fig. 3D), - 27 (Fig. 3F), - 23 (Fig. 3G), - 4 (Fig. 3K), - 2 (Fig. 3L), - 5 (Fig. 3M), -1 (Fig. 3N) and - 2 (Fig. 3O). The caniniform syntype tooth MHN.4759.29 of the Fig. 3H preserves most of its long root. The tooth is slightly curved, labially more convex, rather rounded in external contours but slightly oval in sections and narrow; on each anterior and posterior side, its carina is not salient above

the collar; this is not at all marked by a sulcus; the root is subcylindrical, rather rounded in external contours, and it is barely less wide than the crown. The surface is smooth i.e. without any ridge visible to the naked eye and without fine enamel network. The curve and proportions might indicate an anterior tooth of the upper jaw, partly similarly to the other curved tooth of Fig. 3G, which is slightly larger (being longer in diameter).

Most of these teeth might have been premaxillary or maxillary teeth. They do not fit with the medioposterior dentary teeth of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, MHN.6034.11719.5 and MHN.4759 of Matheron (1869a pl. 1, figs 7–8) by their smooth surface, MHN.4759.3 (Fig. 3L) excepted. The tooth in Fig. 3G might be an anterior tooth, similarly to the 1st dentary tooth of *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* and *Agaresuchus fontisensis* Narváez *et al.*, 2016 (Tabl. 1) or a possible premaxillo-maxillary tooth. The other teeth of the series are falling adult teeth, cut at the collar also possibly of the upper jaw. Some have preserved a short root part just below the collar. Fig. 3K-O teeth, have a short beginning of cylindrical root. The tooth Fig. 3K is similar to the dentary tooth 7 of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, by its relative short height, short mesiodistal length and by its similar rather pointed shape without rounded borders. The maxillary teeth of Fig. 3D-F are relatively large (around 13–14 mm long mesiodistally), for a larger specimen than that of the dentary specimen MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1. Some of these teeth, mostly not positioned on the jaws, are more pointed and variably narrow (i.e. mesiodistally short), others are more rounded at carina borders and apex. The Fig. 3L-O teeth are short for their mesiodistal length, less pointed than the other teeth, and slightly rounded in external volume, although slightly linguolabially flattened. The Fig. 3L-O teeth with worn root, are mesiodistally slightly shorter for their height and more pointed than the medioposterior dentary teeth of specimens MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 (Fig. 5A1, A2), MHN.4759 (Matheron pl. 1, fig. 7) and MHN.6034.11719.5 (Fig. 5B1, B2). At a limited magnified view, the finest enamel structure of these teeth is not visible, except for the posterior tooth of the Fig. 3L, possibly having a wrinkled enamel: this, short and rounder for its length, has the rounded-horizontal carina apex of the dentary tooth 11 of MHN. AIX. PV.2023.15.1. It is similar to the posterior dentary teeth of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, MHN.6034.11719.5 and MHN.4759, by a narrowing at the collar above the diverging upper root wore short wall (without marked sulcus), but the crown is relatively higher for its length; it has a short grown worn root with imperceptible diverging preserved borders, contrary to the medioposterior figured dentary teeth of the preserved MHN specimens, which have cylindrical, long, not worn roots: it corresponds to a maxillary posterior tooth. The surface of the others appears as “smooth”, only “finely striated” (because of the preservation state) as in MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 tooth 4);

anyway, at that enlargement a fine enamel ridges network is not visible, contrary to enlarged posterior teeth of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1. The first tooth, Fig. 3D (MHN.M.4579.28), but perhaps also that of MHN.M.4579.32, syntype (Fig. 3E), is fluted on the apparent face, as on the labial face of the caniniform tooth 4 of MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1; its presented convex face is widest, with a larger number of ridges, perhaps ca. 12, and it ought to be a maxillary tooth as in *Allodaposucus precedens* figured teeth.

4.1.4. Size of all the specimens of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*

Matheron (1869a, b) attributed all the Fuveau crocodylian specimens of the lignitic inferior level to his “*Crocodylus affuvelensis*”. The size of the postcranial elements of La Grande Mène figured by Matheron (1869a), agrees with head parts of animals reaching between two and three metres. For Matheron (1869a b), as for Martin & Buffetaut (2008), the elements belong to a Eusuchian form, as shown in Matheron’s syntype material by procoelous vertebrae (Matheron, 1869a, pl. 1, figs 3–5); being of a brevirostrine form with two dentary waves (for two premaxillary-maxillary festoons) the second being slightly subdivided in two; with a similar generalised heterodonty (anteromedian pointed one, and more rounded posterior one in two lots). Matheron (1869a) pointed out the brevirostry: “The crocodile from the coal layers of la Grande Mène had not the nearly equal teeth of gavials.... [is] of a brevirostrine form” [in French]. Matheron estimated the total length of the animal from the dental specimen (Matheron, 1869a, pl. 1, fig. 7) to be about two metres. And he estimated that some “La Grande Mène” specimens (femur, coracoid, and head fragment: Matheron, 1869a, pl. figs 1, 2, and 7) possibly belong to specimens of three metres. This size is consistent with the size of the skull neotype MHN.M.15427.0., which could reach 250 mm (up to the occipital condyle), for an animal of 1.50 to 1.73 m, considering 6 to 7 times the skull length in the full-body length for a brevirostrine form. This is a ratio varying according to the “brevirostrine” pattern within a family (variable brevirostry), here comparable to that of *Crocodylus niloticus*. It agrees with the size of the dentary specimen MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 which could belong to a skull of 200 mm long a least and a full body of about 1.32 m to 1.64 m.

4.1.5. Summary of shared dentary characters of observed specimens of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*

They all share (according to their preserved part):

- A relatively short and high dentary, with the same two high festoons, the last being subdivided in two and

forming a weak third posterior festoon, well marked here.

- Same characteristic slope angle of ca. 130° between the first two festoons and a weak curve between the 2^d and 3^d festoons.
- Same position of the preserved teeth on the slopes.
- Similar relative proportions in height and length of the different dentary parts (Fig. 3P).
- Same global tooth shape and proportions of comparable preserved teeth, in two sets (pointed teeth 1–10 and “blunt” 11/12 up to posterior one tooth 16, in two subsets).
- Same external tooth morphology by category (contours, proportions, preserved surface, enamel, crown and root details).
- Diastemae 6#7 (short 6/7) and 7#8 (the longest 7//8), visible on MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1, are not visible on the lateral view of the syntype of Matheron (1869a, pl. 1, fig. 8). But both specimens show the same short diastema 8/9 (8#9) and they share the same teeth 10–12 grouping.
- The highest same tooth 10 after the canine 4th, with the same relative height.

5. COMPARISONS

5.1. *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*, *allodaposuchids* and *external forms*

Ma. affuvelensis has been recognised as an allodaposuchid by Narváez *et al.* (2015, 2016). The lower jaw characters presented here have already been partially described. They supported the similarity, observed by Buscalioni *et al.* (1997, 1999), between *Ma. affuvelensis* and *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997. However, when erecting *Massaliasuchus*, based on the skull, Martin and Buffetaut (2008) pointed out differences between *Ma. affuvelensis*, *Mu. buffetauti* and the original Romanian material and the new material of *Allodaposuchus precedens*, as described by Buscalioni *et al.* (2001), Delfino *et al.* (2008a) and confirmed by Narváez *et al.* (2017, 2019). Specific differences between *Ma. affuvelensis* and other allodaposuchids are confirmed here, as far as the dentary morphology is concerned. However, it must be considered that the dentary of *Al. precedens* is absent and that its dentition is known only from a few isolated maxillary teeth. Therefore, *Ma. affuvelensis* is comparable to *Allodapadosuchus precedens* only by a part of the skull, that described at the time of the erection of the genus *Massaliasuchus*, and not by the dentary and its dentition. However, *Ma. affuvelensis* is mainly integrated into the family by other crocodylian elements than the type species *Allodaposuchus*: those already integrated into the family (Tabl. 1), as well as by the combination of characters of the skull, the dentary

and the teeth. Nevertheless, the tooth shape variability in allodaposuchids is poorly known, and tooth figures are rarely available at sufficiently high resolution. When isolate teeth are figured, they are rarely positioned on the jaws (upper or lower jaw, tooth number in the dental series) and the teeth shown are sometimes not even definitively attributed to *Allodaposuchus* (Blanco *et al.*, 2014; Blanco *et al.*, 2018, 2020; Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997, 1999; Martin *et al.*, 2015; Narváez *et al.*, 2019). The preserved dentition of *Allodaposuchus* is mainly represented in situ in the complete jaws, shown in lateral views, with the teeth implanted in the alveoli, and without magnification. With some exceptions (Blanco *et al.* 2020; Narváez *et al.*, 2015; Puértolas-Pascual *et al.*, 2011), the description of the teeth lacks the detailed characters considered here for each category of tooth. In the latest phylogenetic analyses of *Allodaposuchus* (Narváez *et al.*, 2015 then Blanco, 2021), few of the dental characters they listed are applicable to *Ma. affuvelensis*. Of the 189 characters listed for the complete skeleton, in a matrix of 109 crocodylian taxa (*Massaliasuchus*, *Ischyrochampsia* and *Mustuzabalsuchus* not included), characters 47 to 54, 79, 91 and 92 are possible to retain: but among them, the definition of five characters does not allow its application to *Massaliasuchus* and others are too generalised. The application of some of them to several allodaposuchid species must be reexamined.

Therefore, the comparisons given here with *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* are insufficient. But they are given here to open a new investigation. In the compared forms of allodaposuchids, the characters associated with the organisation of the implantation of the teeth on the jaws are sought, being the distances/diastema, relative sizes, crown and root variable shape elements, in their difference or similarity according to each genus or group of species, in comparison with the forms external to the allodaposuchids (figs in Blainville, 1855), pl. 2; Delfino & Smith, 2009; Delfino *et al.*, 2017; Ginsburg & Bulot, 1997; Murelaga *et al.*, 2002; Martin, 2010b, Martin *et al.*, 2015; Planté, 1870; Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002; Vaillant, 1872) (MNHN. F, MNHN.RA coll). Differences in size of the teeth are related to the rostral border morphology in brevirostrine forms, eusuchian pristichampsine *Pristichampsus*/*Boverisuchus*” (Brochu, 2013; Godinot *et al.*, 2018) as well as included mesosuchian forms (Buffetaut, 1979; Company *et al.*, 2005; Godinot *et al.*, 2018; Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002). The lower jaw of *Ma. affuvelensis* is consistent with that of these outgroups, with a skull corresponding to a rostrum exhibiting three waves (festoons): the premaxillary festoon followed by two maxillary festoons, with a notch or an indentation for the dentary canine, between the premaxilla and the maxilla. The brevirostrine forms compared here (restricted to not ziphodont forms) share these general characters. In particular, their lower jaw most often shares with that of *Ma. affuvelensis* the

same longer dominant diastema between teeth seven and eight (#7//8).

5.1.1. General dentary teeth characters in allodaposuchids compared to *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*

As is the case in allodaposuchids (Tabls 1 and 2) and in most eusuchian crocodylians, unlike *Diplocynodon* and *Borealosuchus*, alveoli 3 and 4 are not confluent and the teeth are bicarinate without denticles, unlike ziphodont forms; the 1st tooth projects variably anterodorsally but not horizontally. Without a preserved dentary, no precise comparison is possible with *Al. precedens*, *A. subjuniperus* and *Al. gascabadiolorum*. However, the corresponding cranial festoons could help to complete Tables 1 and 3. As in *Ma. affuvelensis*, in *Mustuzabalsuchus buffetauti*, *Al. iberoarmoricus* / *precedens* probably, *Ag. fontisensis*, *Al. palustris* and *Lohuecosuchus megadontos* probably, the highest and longest tooth after the 4th is the 10th. As in *Ma. affuvelensis*, in *Mu. buffetauti* and *Al. iberoarmoricus/precedens* there are 16 dentary teeth, unlike in *Lo. megadontos* (14) and *Agaresuchus fontisensis* (17) and the dentary teeth are mesiodistally longer than linguolabially, being linguolabially compressed; but the teeth are less compressed in *Lo. megadontos* and even less, being rounder, in *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis*. In *Ma. affuvelensis*, probably as in *Mu. buffetauti* and *Al. iberoarmoricus/precedens* and others, the teeth are more convex labially than lingually: it is not clear for some forms when the figures are deficient. Some differences require revision, such as the heterodonty in *Al. fontisensis* with posterior teeth more pointed at the tip.

5.1.2. Symphysis and splenial relationships

In allodaposuchids (Tabl. 1), the symphysis is short, not extending beyond the level of teeth 4 to 5, with the exception of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* where it reaches tooth 6. Depending on the allodaposuchid forms compared, as indicated in the authors' work, the upper extremity of the splenial processes is shorter or longer than – or equal to – the extremity of the lower process. When described and figured, the splenial is excluded from the symphysis contact but variably close to it (the furthest is that of *Agaresuchus fontisensis*). *Ma. affuvelensis* is an exception with a clear contact between the posterior border of the symphysis and the two anterior processes of the splenial (the dorsal process having a contact bulge), at the level of the 6th tooth (Figs 2B, 2 A-C). At the same time, the symphysis is longer compared to other forms of allodaposuchids. Depending on the perspective, the end of the symphysis relative to a given tooth may appear slightly different, viewed medially or dorsally:

an apparent difference may be noted, for example, the posterior end of the symphysis appears at the beginning of the 5th tooth, or at mid-length. In allodaposuchids other than *Ma. affuvelensis*: – the symphysis is relatively shorter for its height than in *Ma. affuvelensis*; – and its posterior end does not reach the two splenial processes in direct contact. Based on figures only and, subject to confirmation, dentaries in hands, in medial view: – The symphysis approximately reaches the mid-tooth 4 and both splenial processes seem to reach the tooth 5 in *Mu. buffetauti* (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997, fig. 2).

The splenial process reaches:

- approximately the level of the middle tooth 4 and, of the two splenial processes, the lower process is slightly longer in *Ag. fontisensis*;
- the mid-tooth 5 level (superior process) and nearly the symphysis end (inferior process), without contact in *Al. palustris* (Blanco *et al.*, 2014, fig. 4C);
- apparently, the level of the 5th tooth in *Al. iberoarmoricanus/precedens*, from Velaux (the condition of the specimen view does not give the precise splenial-symphysis relationship);
- the level of the interval tooth 4/tooth 5 (superior process) and the tooth 6 (inferior process) in *Is. meridionalis*;
- the level of the tooth 5 (superior process), and toward the end of the tooth 4 (inferior process) or both processes at tooth 5 in *Lo. megadontos*.

In the external brevirostrine (non-ziphodont) fossil European forms compared, the symphysis is of variable length. The splenial-symphysis relationship and the distance of each splenial process from the symphysis vary. In the compared forms, the symphysis is short in *Diplocynodon*. The splenial only clearly participates primitively in the symphysis in the Palaeocene Thanetian *Diplocynodon remensis* Martin *et al.*, 2014 (fig. 5E, F), the long symphysis including teeth 5–6. It is shorter, at teeth 4 to 3, and its distance from the splenial is specifically variable in stratigraphically younger species, such as *Diplocynodon* sp. from the Oligocene locality of La Millloque (Nouvelle-Aquitaine, France) (MNHN.F.Filhol 1903-1 coll.) and from the Lower Miocene of Las Bardenas Reales de Navarra (Murelaga *et al.*, 2002), the type species *D. ratelii* Pomel, 1847 (in Vaillant, 1872), from the Aquitaine of St-Gérand-le-Puy (MNHN.F.SG coll.) and *D. styriacus* (Hofmann, 1885) from the Miocene of France and Austria (Ginsburg & Bulot, 1997; Martin & Gross, 2011). Similar variability in symphysis-splenial distance exists according to stratigraphy and/or species in the group “*Asiatosuchus*” *depressifrons*. The symphysis reaches the teeth 6 extremity area but the splenial never participates to the long symphysis, as in Allodaposuchids. It does not come into contact with the border of the symphysis, unlike *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*. However, the splenial is more or less close to the posterior edge of the symphysis depending on the dorsal or inferior process, and depending

on the species, as shown by the forms of this group:

- From the Thanetian at Mont-de-Berru, basal “conglomérat de Cernay” (Lemoine quarry) (MNHN.F.CRL coll.) or overlying Mourras quarry (MNHN.F.Be coll.) (Delfino *et al.*, 2017).
- From the early Ypresian of Muirancourt (France), the holotype of “*Crocodylus*” *depressifrons* Blainville, 1955 (MNHN.F. coll.) and specimens of “Les Brillants quarry” at Issy-les-Moulineaux (Planté, 1870) (specimens MNHN.F, Planté, 1870-444 coll.), and “*Cr.*” *depressifrons* form of Orp-le-Grand (Belgium), IRSNB R253 (Delfino & Smith, 2009).

In the extant comparative forms, the length of the symphysis also varies specifically in similar proportions, and it is not in contact with the splenial. The location of each splenial process relative to the symphysis also varies very specifically according to the elongation of the lower jaw (MNHN.RA.AC.coll.). However, the two elements are further apart than in the compared fossil forms, allodaposuchids included, the lower jaw being lower for the length of its dentary tooth series, with festoons less developed in height, variably; and it is notably lower than in *Massaliasuchus* and *Musturzabalsuchus* in all allodaposuchids, with festonation angles more obtuse. In extant forms, the anterior dentary part is lower than in the lower jaws of allodaposuchids, with the 1st tooth pointed dorso-anteriorly but distinctly less so dorsally. The alveoli are of variable distance (with some larger diastema as seen above) (figs in Blainville, 1855, Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002) and further apart than in allodaposuchids: the symphysis of *Osteolaemus tetraspis* MNHN.RA.AC 1931-45, reaches the end of the interval of teeth 5–6, and the splenial the end of tooth 6; the symphysis is longer than that of *Crocodylus niloticus* MNHN. F.REP 100; where it reaches the interalveolar 4–5, and the splenial reaches only the beginning of tooth 7 (upper process) and the interalveolar 6–7 (lower process). Thus, the positions of the symphysis and splenial vary in all species, reinforcing the differences observed between *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* and all other named allodaposuchids (at least as seen by those whose dentary is sufficiently figured).

In view of all these cases, the situation in *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*, with the splenial clearly contacting the superior and slightly longer symphysis by both processes, appears to be representative of the least derived condition in its group, as in *Diplocynodon remensis* within the Diplocynodontidae, and both being less derived than in the comparative extant crocodylian forms.

5.1.3. Allodaposuchid festooning and diastema characters

The cranial and/or mandibular festoons described in Allodaposuchidae are broadly consistent with those of the *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* specimen MHN.AIX.

Tabl. 3. Diastemae formula of some allodaposuchid taxa of Table 1, known by this character.

group morphotype 1a	<i>Massaliasuchus affuvelensis</i>	1//2//3-4-5- <u>6//7//8/9</u>	6/7 short space is added to main 7//8. space 8/9 is specific according to the present knowledge
group morphotype 1b	<i>Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti</i> , <i>Velaux Allodaposuchus iberoarmoricanus</i> / <i>precedens</i> , <i>Lohuecosuchus megadontos</i> ,	1//2//3-4-5- <u>6//7//8-9</u>	short 6/7 space added to main 7//8, no space 8/9
group morphotype 1c	<i>Agaresuchus fontisensis</i> <i>Ischyrochampsia meridionalis</i>	1//2//3-4-5-6- <u>7//8-9</u>	No added space 6/7 to 7//8, no space 8/9. Heterogenous. Thin 4-5-6-7 are separated in <i>Agaresuchus</i> ; and rounded close in <i>Ischyrochampsia</i>
group morphotype 2	<i>Al. palustris</i>	1//2//3/ <u>4</u> //5-6// <u>7//8</u> (...)	3/4 shorter and 4//5 and 6//7 are longer specific spaces, present and dominant, longer than in other groups

PV.2023.15.1 and with the figured material of the syntype of Matheron (1869a). The three festoons of the lower jaw correspond to similar cranial festoons (one premaxillary and two maxillaries), as partly shown in the skull specimen MHN. 10'834.0 (Martin & Buffetaut, 2008, fig. 3C-D). However, the maximum height of the dentary festoons (# h1, # h3 in Fig. 2P) relative to the height of the lower jaw between them (# h2) is highly variable in the compared allodaposuchids as in the comparative external forms. *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* is the only species to share the tallest festoons for their length with *Ma. affuvelensis*. The festooning of the lower jaw in all allodaposuchids compared is associated with the same successive categories of tooth tips:

1. pointed teeth 1–10; the teeth of the anterior symphyseal part of the 1st festoon are or not incurved, and the 1st tooth is more or less strongly pointed dorsally depending on the possible lowering of the symphysis;
2. “blunt” lower posterior teeth 13–16: with a more to less horizontally long semi-“blunt” apex (on the ascending 3d festoon slope) (13th is the last preserved tooth for 14 alveoli in *Lohuecosuchus magadontos*).

Diastema, similarities and differences (Tabl. 3). The tooth organisation of the diastema of allodaposuchids is globally identical to that of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*. Allodaposuchids present in the first festoon the small group of alveoli # 5–7 closely framing the stronger alveolus # 4 (larger tooth 4); the 3rd and 5th teeth are particularly close to the 4th, with the exception of *Agaresuchus fontisensis* with thinner and more widely spaced teeth; the short space between teeth 6 and 7 (space 6/7) is known in five species (Tabl. 3); in all species, as frequently in brevirostrine forms, there is a notable diastema 7//8; the length between the posterior teeth of the second to third festoons is variable, notably depending on the relative size of the teeth. So far, the short 8/9 gap is only visible in *Ma. affuvelensis* in tooth

groups 8–12. In all species, the upper dentary point (# h3) is located at the level of dominant teeth 10 or possibly at the level of subequal teeth 10–11, the intervals between the posterior teeth are larger, and the size and shape of the tips of the last teeth differ between individuals and species.

5.1.3.1 Discriminant, taxonomic differences in lower jaw proportions

Ma. affuvelensis MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 and *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* share (as observed laterally in a straight line), a relatively shorter dentary tooth series on the jaw (Fig. 2P) compared to other allodaposuchids, where the most widely spaced teeth are distributed on the lower festoons of relatively longer jaws for their height. Whereas in the first two species, the festoons are relatively tall and tightly packed, with a taller symphysis: *Mu. buffetauti* shares the relatively tall height of festoons 1 and 2 with *Ma. affuvelensis*. The angle between the slopes of the first two festoons is identical to that of *Ma. affuvelensis*, i.e. approximately 130°. In both species, teeth 4–10 are distributed on steeper descending and ascending slopes of festoons 1 and 2 (respectively), so that (the teeth being relatively similarly spaced) the complete set of teeth 1–16 results in a shorter length from anterior tip to tip than in other lower-festooned allodaposuchid dentaries: such as *Agaresuchus fontisensis* (a finer-toothed species). Thus, there is a greater elevation of the festoon (#h1, #h3) relative to the height between festoons (#h2) in *Ma. affuvelensis* and *Mu. buffetauti*, while there are inferior festoons on a relatively longer and shallower anterior dentary in the other species, with a varying degree of jaw lowering, depending on each. *Velaux – La Bastide Neuve Allodaposuchus iberoarmoricanus/precedens, lower jaw*: Although most of the anterior part of the diaphysis is missing, from teeth 1 to 3, the specimen shows a much wider and gentler angle between the two slopes of the festoon, compared

to *Mu. buffetauti* and *Ma. affuvelensis*. The angle is approximately 155°, and the teeth are further apart, with the dental series appearing longer, from teeth 4 to 16.

Agaresuchus fontisensis lower jaw is similar to that of Velaux by a weaker second festoon slope, with apparent similar obtuse angle of ca. 155° between the festoons, and with a slightly less incurved angle between festoons 2 and 3. It does not show the short diastema # 6/7. It has the relatively longer interalveolar distances, posteriorly to tooth 4, of the species from Velaux.

Lohuecosuchus megadontos dentaries, HUE-04498 holotype and HUE-05161 paratype (Narváez et al., 2015, figs 4, 6): Its specific name refers to the enlarged and thicker teeth. Their alveolar section is less compressed linguo-labially than in *Ma. affuvelensis* and other species, except for those visible occlusal, except *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis*. The festoons are lower; the dentaries have a wider obtuse angle of 160° between the festoons, with a weak upward slope throughout the tooth series after the minimum height (# h2), which is only slightly lower than the maximum anterior height (# h1); specimen HUE-04378 is more festooned (perhaps by sexual difference, compared with *Diplocynodon* in Vaillant (1872)), the angle between the two festoons being 145°: in this species, the angles are always more obtuse than in *Ma. affuvelensi* and *Mu. buffetauti* and closer to the angle in the Velaux *Al. iberoccitanus/precedens*. The large posterior teeth of *Lo. megadontos* are close together, unlike *Ma. affuvelensis*, *Mu. buffetauti*, *Ag. fontisensis* and *Al. iberarmoricanus/precedens*, but as in *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis*.

Ischyrochampsia meridionalis: It is distinguished by its broad, low, and massive jaw and its thick, rounded teeth. In lateral view (Martin et al., 2015, Vasse, 1995) and based on the new observation of the holotype (Martin et al., 2015, fig. 14), tooth 7 is seen close to the 6th and separated from the 8th as in other allodaposuchids; teeth 1 to 7 are close together. The jaw, slightly festooned, is high at tooth 4, dropping very slightly at teeth 5 to 7. There is an angle of 145° between the slopes of festoons 1 and 2, similar to that of the holotype of *Lo. megadontos*; but after the slight upward slope and the weak festoon, at tooth 12, the dentary is as low as at teeth 4 to 7 and the third festoon is barely defined. The rounded alveoli of the rounded teeth are close together, not distant in groups, except by the narrow diastema 7//8; teeth 8–11 are close (the posterior part of the tooth series is damaged).

5.1.4. Dentary branch contour: external (labial) and inner (lingual) dentary borders, external compared forms included

5.1.4.1. External (labial) border

In dorsal view, at the level of the symphysis, from tooth 1 to tooth 4, the border is transversely straight in *Agaresuchus*

fontisensis and *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis*. That of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* is slightly artificially inflected outwards, postmortem, by compression at the level of teeth 1 and 2: in any case, the dentary was neither transversely external, more protruding at the level of tooth 4, nor very convex anteriorly; it was rather straight oblique as in the Thanetian and early Ypresian forms of the “*Asiatosuchus*” *depressifrons* group. *Is. meridionalis* also has a straight, rather transverse anterior edge between teeth 1 to 4, but it is very prominent (almost entirely transversely) at the level of large tooth 4, compared to the direction of the dental edge posteriorly, with a broad dorsal symphysis dental surface and without a protrusion in height of the first festoon: thus, its next dentary border appears dorsally as particularly narrow posterior to its 4th tooth symphysis part. *Lohuecosuchus magadontos* also has a wide symphysis, without a high 4th tooth festoon, the festoon being much lower in the holotype and only slightly higher in two paratypes. But its lateral symphysis border does not appear dorsally as horizontally prominent as in *Is. meridionalis*. This is because *Lo. megadontos* has a rounded external anterior border and does not have such a marked edge inward curve, behind tooth 4.

5.1.4.2. Posterior incurvation of the external border up to tooth 9

In all forms compared (fossil and extant included), posterior to the largest tooth 4, there is this incurvation of the external border up to tooth 9. It is barely marked in *Ma. affuvelensis* and in the Velaux *Allodaposuchus iberarmoricanus/precedens*, and, in both, the dentary is narrow and not widened at the symphysis (no occlusal view is known in *Mu. buffetauti*). In general, this incurvation is followed by a slight protrusion of the border of tooth 9 towards the posterior end of the series, corresponding to the posterior maxillary festoon, except in *Ma. affuvelensis*. However, the dentary of Velaux *Al. iberarmoricanus/precedens* is preserved anteriorly only from tooth 4 (at the posterior width of the symphysis): it does not indicate a strong external protrusion at tooth 4 and a marked incurvation behind tooth 9.

Most of the above-mentioned differences occur independently of size because *Ag. fontisensis*, *Lo. megadontos* and *Is. meridionalis* are known from large specimens, at least twice as long as *Ma. affuvelensis*. The preserved part of the lower jaw of Velaux *Al. iberarmoricanus/precedens* is about twice as long as the latter. Specific individual differences in a strong protrusion at tooth 4 of *Is. meridionalis* (external) or possibly in height (part of the *Lo. megadontos* specimens) may be due to sexual dimorphism in these forms as in *Diplocynodon ratelii* Pomel, 1847 (MNHN, F.SG 542, estimated male) compared to “*D. gracile* Vaillant, 1872” (estimated female) figured by Vaillant (1872), and as in extant *Crocodylus*. However, the parameter “rounded” or “straight” of the contour of the external anterior

border, with a more or less oblique direction, appears to belong to a specific rank (or group of species), and is not included in this potentially sexual difference of the protrusion of the 4th tooth. By this strongly protruding anterior contour at the level of the 4th tooth, the large specimen of *Is. meridionalis* and a part of the specimens of *Lo. megadontos* differ fundamentally from the slender and small (although well-developed) *Ma. affivelensis* and *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti*, as well as from the large but slender *Ag. fontisensis*.

The rounded outer border of the symphysis of the lower jaw of *Al. palustris* corresponds to that of *Lo. megadontos*, the curve following without interruption the edge posterior to tooth 4. But the particularly regular width of the symphysis (in dorsal view) does not give *Al. palustris* as wide a symphysis as in *Lo. megadontos*. The proportion of its symphysis, the implantation of its teeth and its diastema differ from all other allodaposuchids (Tabl. 3), being very different from those of *Ma. affivelensis*.

Inner lingual/medial border contour. In dorsal view, in most allodaposuchids, the medial (lingual) outline of the lower jaw has a regular curve, forming a pronounced obtuse angle, from the tip of the symphysis posteriorly. In *Ag. fontisensis*, the internal angle is closer to a right angle at the symphysis, which, in dorsal view, suggests a wider symphysis posteriorly.

5.1.5. Tooth morphology

In brevirostrine eusuchian crocodiles, heterodonty partly reproduces the mammalian distinction between canines and molars. Thus, the general shape of the anterior tooth MHN.4759.29 of Matheron (1869a, pl. 1, fig. 6c, d; Fig. 3H) of *Massaliasuchus affivelensis*, curved, pointed, and with a long cylindrical root, as wide as the crown, is considered “caniniform,” and the depressed and elongated posterior teeth (pl. 1, fig. 7) are considered, “molariform.” This category of *Massaliasuchus* teeth is comparable to that of extant crocodiles such as *Osteolaemus tetraspis* (figs in Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002), but the “molarity” (tooth height, carinae, and tip contours) is highly variable.

5.1.5.1. Tooth size, difference by taxon and by position the jaw

In allodaposuchids (Tabl. 1), the mid-posterior teeth of the lower jaw are more pointed in *Lohuecosuchus megadontos* than in *Massaliasuchus affivelensis*; as also the teeth 11–12 and 15–16 of *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1999, fig. 5; Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015, fig. 8). In *Agaresuchus fontisensis*, the lower jaw posterior teeth are higher, compared to their length, and more pointed at the apex than in *Ma. affivelensis*. The anterior teeth 1 to 3 are larger in *Ischyrochampsia* compared to teeth 5 to 7, and relatively to other species.

In *Al. palustris*, the relative size of teeth 1 to 7 is unclear in the original photograph compared to the drawing. It appears to represent a particular condition in allodaposuchids, a variability that is presented in Blanco *et al.* (2020).

5.1.5.2. Crown, collar and root characters, crown fluted surface and ornamentation

In allodaposuchids, with rare exceptions, authors speak of “smooth teeth” (Narváez *et al.*, 2015) or “completely smooth teeth” (Blanco *et al.*, 2015; Narváez *et al.*, 2019; Puértolas *et al.*, 2014a): this means that the teeth are devoid of crests or ornamentation. It is not known precisely which: dorsal or ventral teeth, only the 4th and posterior teeth being included. However, ornamented teeth are mentioned in some species (Tabl. 1) (see below), like in *Massaliasuchus affivelensis*. Indeed, depending on the species and the position of the tooth on the jaws, the conjunction of characters is different. In other words, the teeth have cylindrical, diverging, or inflated roots beneath a protruding, or not, crown, depending on the tooth number in the series.

Tooth root: The roots of the teeth of the upper and/or lower jaws are often barely visible or not visible, including the root of caniniform tooth 4 in specimens of *Ma. affivelensis* MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15 (Figs. 2, 4) and the teeth of the lost syntype of Matheron, 1869a (pl. 11, fig. 8). The teeth may be partially raised postmortem from the alveoli sockets, revealing the upper part of the root externally, as in *Lohuecosuchus megadontos*.

Possible cylindrical roots, no wider than the crown, without a marked collar at the limit with the crown, are present in various cranial or mandibular teeth, as in the posterior dentary teeth of *Ma. affivelensis*: MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15. (Figs 2B, 4B), MHN.6034.11719.5 (Fig. 5A2, B), and figured Matheron’s, 1869a syntypes: lost syntype (MHN.4759.29, pl. 1, fig. 6) and MHN.4759 (pl.1, fig 7). Cylindrical roots are seen in the two figured “dentary teeth” of *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997 (1999) which are close in shape to the medioposterior dentary teeth of *Ma. affivelensis*. Premaxillary-maxillary magnified teeth of *Al. precedens* (Martin *et al.*, 2015, fig. D; Narváez *et al.*, 2019) also have cylindrical roots, and the carina crown border is roundly protruding above the collar. Another *Al. precedens* tooth (Martin *et al.*, 2015, fig. 11 E-F) has also a slightly protruding carina and a not marked collar, but only a sub-cylindrical root. Two teeth of *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis* have:

- one; diverging root borders directly in prolongation of the crown, without a marked collar (making the root slightly mesiodistally longer than the crown) (Martin *et al.*, 2015, fig. 11G),
- the other one; a nearly cylindrical root, barely at mid-length inflated, below a protruding crown carina (Martin *et al.*, 2015, fig. 11H).

Flutation: Contrary to the posterior teeth of *Ma. affuvelensis*, the crown surface of some allodaposuchid teeth (the root of which is observed above) may be fluted by ridges visible to naked eye on the lingual face, and the crown is smooth between the ridges. Such are the dentary MHN.AIX. PV.2023.15.1 tooth 4 of *Ma. affuvelensis* (Fig. 4A2) with 8 ridges on the presented lingual face, and the possible maxillary tooth MHNM.4759.32 (Matheron, 1869a, pl.1, fig. 6b) (Fig. 3D). More than 8 ridges are possibly present in figured allodaposuchid teeth, on the lingual face. However, in *Is. meridionalis* the two figured teeth by Martin *et al.* (2015, Fig. G) are also fluted on the labial face: clearly on the 1st tooth with diverging root borders, and barely visible on the preserved labial crown surface of the 2nd tooth (Martin *et al.* 2015, Fig. 11H-I), by fluted signs toward the top (Fig. 11I), beside the fluted lingual face; that tooth has a long, nearly cylindrical, at mid-lengthy inflated root. Another unpublished rounded tooth (at least) of the *Is. meridionalis* MNHN. F. St-Estève Janson collection is also fluted on both faces. This fluting of *Is. meridionalis* on both faces is an exception among observed allodaposuchids. A 9th pointed tooth is attributed to cf. *Allodaposuchus palustris* by Blanco *et al.*, 2018: it is clearly fluted by 8 to 10 ridges on the lingual face, and very weakly striated on the labial face: this tooth, narrow all along its height in relation to other known fluted allodaposuchid teeth, has also a protruding carina above the collar. In cf. *Allodaposuchus palustris* sp. 2, in Blanco *et al.*, 2020, pointed anteromedian teeth are clearly fluted on the lingual face; narrow all along the height in relation to other known fluted allodaposuchid teeth, they also have a protruding carina above the collar. In Blanco *et al.* (2020) study, there are several morphotypes of smooth teeth, i.e. without a wrinkled enamel, including comparable smooth teeth to those known in *Al. precedens* (particularly cf. *Allodaposuchus palustris* morphotype IX). In the holotype lower jaw of *Agaresuchus fontisensis*, some teeth are slightly postmortem elevated above the alveolus: there is no marked collar, medioposterior teeth seem to be cylindrical; while the tooth 4 had a root with diverging borders in the alveolus, becoming wider than the crown. Teeth with root wider than the crown by diverging borders, and without marked collar, seem also visible in maxillary teeth of *Ag. subjuniperus*: magnified views are needed for both species.

Situation in Cenozoic-extant external groups: In *Osteolaemus tetraspis*, the exposed roots are cylindrical (the medioposterior teeth root 11–12 at least) in the specimen figured by Prasad Guntupalli & Lapparent de Broin (2002, pl. 1b), as in Allodaposuchids. *Osteolaemus*, *Crocodylus niloticus* and the “*Asiatosuchus*” group have, beside the anterodorsal pointed 1st tooth, other pointed teeth 2 to 10, much variable in height (the higher anterior teeth being the 1st and the 4th as in allodaposuchids). The posteriormost “molariform”

teeth are less pointed and falsely blunt (i.e. narrow and not bulbous, as in *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*) in the *Osteolaemus* specimen of Prasad Guntupalli & Lapparent de Broin (2002, pl. 1b). In the external taxa compared, the molariform posterior teeth vary by a rounded to nearly horizontal tip, depending on the taxa. In the latter, the teeth are divided into two height groups, like the most posterior ones of the allodaposuchids: from which they differ by their own characters of relative width, length, height and surface elements, beside other similarities of implantation on the dentary.

Ornamented wrinkled tooth enamel: A network of much finer anastomosing ridges (“minimal ridges”) is visible in enlarged views of *Ma. affuvelensis* teeth (Figs 2, 4, 5). In *Allodaposuchus palustris* Blanco *et al.*, 2014, wrinkled enamel is depicted on the upper part of a tooth; the surface is regularly longitudinally finely ridged, with fewer anastomoses than in *Ma. affuvelensis* (Fig. 4B); the lower medial part (which has more anastomoses in *Ma. affuvelensis*) is not enlarged: in any case, no preserved mid-posterior or posterior tooth of *Ma. affuvelensis* (dentary, or isolated tooth in Fig. 3D-O) has the narrow mesiodistal length for height, an inflection at the collar and an inflated root of this figured tooth of *Al. palustris* (possibly maxillary).

Compared external forms: crown surface characters, root, flutation: Elements are partly shared with Allodaposuchids, each taxon having its own characterisation. Crown: In *Diplocynodon*, the thin, pointed anteromedial teeth have a diagnostic extruded carina, constituting a thin, flat border on the tooth, on each side above the marked collar, giving them a characteristic shape (Martin *et al.* 2014, fig. 9). The shorter, rounded crowns of the posterior teeth (shorter than the pointed medial teeth) have a less horizontal contour at the tip than in *Crocodylus* and overall than in *Osteolaemus* (Prasad Guntupalli & Lapparent de Broin 2002, pls. 1, 2). In these compared taxa (*Diplocynodon* and extant), the molariform teeth are also slightly shorter mesiodistally than in *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*. Linguo-labially, all these molar teeth of these taxa, as also of the “*Asiatosuchus*” group, are either wider or narrower than in *Massaliasuchus* depending on the taxon.

Root morphology: It also varies. The teeth of *Crocodylus niloticus* and *Diplocynodon*, with the exception of the canines, do not have entirely cylindrical roots. Below a marked collar, very characteristic in *Diplocynodon* (Martin *et al.* 2015), either the posterior dental root is inflated over a middle or medioinferior part of its length below the marked neck (Fig. 9 D-F), or the medioinferior root borders clearly diverge downwards from the alveolus, without a marked collar (Fig. A-C).

Flutation in external compared forms: It is found in isolated teeth of the “*As.*” *depressifrons* group from the early Ypresian, of the pointed or short category, as in *Diplocynodon*. The latter has pointed, fluted teeth

with crests on the lingual side or on both sides, but this dentition is a minority next to the smooth teeth; Some teeth show a kind of enamel striation, visible to the naked eye, different from the fine wrinkles of the enlarged posterior teeth of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*. In extant crocodilian species, fluted teeth are frequently present on both sides, with more or less ridges depending on the face and position of the tooth on the jaw. In various specimens of *Crocodylus niloticus* observed (col. MNHN.RA.), all anteromedial teeth are fluted on each side; the posterior teeth have few ridges on the inner surface (skull and lower jaw) and the anteromedial pointed teeth are more finely narrow, with a lower number of ridges (about 6) than in allodaposuchids. In *Osteolaemus*, at least some ridges are present on the 4th pointed tooth of one specimen (Prasad Guntupalli & Lapparent de Broin, 2002, figs). In the external taxa compared, wrinkled tooth enamel is sometimes visible (see above) in early French Cenozoic specimens of the “*As. depressifrons*” group (specimens from Mont de Berru (Thanetian) and Rians (Ypresian) (Tabuce *et al.*, in prep.), *Asiatosuchus*-like specimens from Rouzilhac (Late Ypresian), *Isselosaurus doduni* (Gray, 1831) in (Godinot *et al.*, 2018, fig. 80), and Eocene *Allognathosuchus*-like forms (Ösi, 2013). In these forms, the fine ridges of the wrinkled blunt teeth are roughly parallel, not being anastomosed in the network at the base, and not converging at tip as they do in *Massaliasuchus*. The carinae are transversally finely ridged by the external angulation of the crown ridges (false denticulations in relation to ziphodont forms), as observed in some extant forms (Prasad & Lapparent de Broin 2002, pl. 15). A detailed study of the enamel of all the non-pointed allodaposuchid lower jaw teeth in magnified views is expected for comparison with *Ma. affuvelensis* and external forms.

5.1.5.3. Larger longer-higher dentary teeth, tooth distribution on the dentary, diastema

To differentiate Allodaposuchids from other families, it is important to define the largest posterior tooth, in terms of length at the alveolus border, and of crown height. In Allodaposuchids, this is the 10th, or (rarely) the 10th and 11th (both identical) (Narváez *et al.*, 2015).

In the external forms compared, the largest posterior tooth, located at the top of the second festoon, varies between individuals and species. In *Diplocynodon*, this is the 11th and 12th, or the 12th and 13th, depending on the species. The 12th and 13th are of equal height and length; or only of equal length, the 12th being higher: *D. remensis*, *D. styriacus* (Hofmann, 1885) from the Middle Miocene of Bézien and Artenay (France) (Ginsburg & Bulot, 1997); the higher tooth is the 11th, or they are the 11th and 12th in *D. ratelii*. In the group “*Crocodylus*”/“*Asiatosuchus*” *depressifrons*, according to specimens from the Thanetian and the Lower Ypresian of France and Belgium: the higher posterior tooth is the 11th or the 12th, even in

the same individual, as in the left branch and in the Blainville’s figured holotype. The situation of the 10th posterior tooth as the highest in *Massaliasuchus*, as in the compared allodaposuchids (added or not to the 11th), therefore constitutes an important diagnostic character.

As brevirostrine forms, the compared forms share the same tooth arrangement on the dentary, and most often they show the same process of angle opening variability between the lower jaw festoons. In compared forms, the festoon angles vary from few to more obtuse (as within the Allodaposuchidae), in forms other than both *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis* and *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti*. This angle opening is linked both to the lowering festoon height and to the elongation of the festoon slopes, i.e. of the dentary sequence. In extant compared forms, the dentary elongation is linked to a longer distancing of the teeth between them, along the tooth series (with specific variability), as it varies in Allodaposuchids. As in Allodaposuchidae, some Cenozoic and extant genera may have, in one family, a lower and less festooned dentary, and more distanced teeth, than others: such as *Crocodylus niloticus* in relation to *Osteolaemus tetraspis* (Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002) in Crocodylidae.

As far as the largest dentary tooth is concerned, most brevirostrine compared Eusuchia share with allodaposuchids the 4th largest tooth. But they present a variability of situations and length of the diastema, and a variability of the higher tooth of the second festoon, which characterises each taxon. In Cenozoic forms, the longest lower jaw diastema 7//8 is or not present in adults and, often, it is not the longer diastema. In the “*Asiatosuchus*” *depressifrons* group, the diastema specifically differ. In Mont de Berru “*As.*” *depressifrons* group form (Thanetian), the longest diastema is between the teeth 8//9, after a shorter 7//8. In the Ypresian “*As.*” *depressifrons* holotype, there is an isolation of the couple teeth 8–9 doing a diastema 7//8 and another 9//10, with irregular left-right sides, and other differences exist in other species. In all species, the anterior mid-part teeth rather conform to *Ma. affuvelensis* but the first festooning group differs by the inclusion of the 8th tooth, instead of finishing at the 7th included: in all the *depressifrons* group the posterior mid-part group differs from *Allodaposuchus* by its 9th to 16th teeth grouping with the much larger tooth 11 (or 11/12), with clearly smaller other teeth (Delfino & Smith, 2009; Delfino *et al.*, 2017). In *Diplocynodon*, with the derived confluent alveoli 3–4 teeth duo, where the larger tooth is the 4th (or both 3rd/4th), all the teeth are relatively close together on the dentary and less clearly differentiated in alveolar size and interalveolar distance. In one specimen of *D. remensis* Martin *et al.*, 2014 (Thanetian, Mont de Berru), the diastema between teeth 7 and 8 is not present in a juvenile; and it is also absent in one adult of *D. ratelii* Pomel, 1847 of Aquitanian of Saint-Gérard-le-Puy

(France) (Vaillant, 1872). In specimens of *D. remensis*, teeth 8 and 9 are or not separated (either juvenile or adults) (Martin *et al.*, 2014). All that reflects the large plasticity in *Diplocynodon*. This comparison shows the need to base the observation on several specimens per species in this taxon, which is not the case in allodaposuchids. However, all characters being considered simultaneously, there is an allodaposuchid specific homogeneity in the teeth grouping and spaces, *Al. palustris* excepted. This observation is made when possible, i.e. when the teeth are known, because named allodaposuchids lacking occlusal views and lacking completely preserved sets of teeth are common. In summary for extant comparative crocodiles (Blainville, 1855; Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002) (MNHN. F. *et al.* AC): compared to allodaposuchids and compared fossils, the teeth are more widely spaced on the longest dental series than in allodaposuchids, with longer interalveolar spaces between the thinner teeth, the maxillary and dentary festoons are both slightly accentuated on a relatively less high dentary, particularly in front, and the splenial is distant from the symphysis. *Crocodylus niloticus* has lower festoons, thinner teeth more widely spaced than *Osteolaemus tetraspis* which therefore has a slightly higher dentary with slightly higher festoons; the latter has a shorter anterior part, and a flatter tooth tip of the most posterior teeth. Both share the same 7/8 space and the same large 8/9 space (Prasad & Lapparent de Broin (2002) (as in allodapsuchids), but they share the same 11th upper posterior tooth (or rarely the 12th in *Cr. niloticus*) (instead of the 10th in allodaposuchids). A parallel of the depressed posterior tooth tips of *Os. tetraspis* with “*As.*” *depressifrons* is notable.

5.2. Summary of the dentary and dentition of allodaposuchids, based on comparisons between *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*, Allodaposuchidae and external forms

The dentition of allodaposuchids exhibits heterodonty with many generalised characters of brevirostrine eusuchians. The three waves (festoons) with the larger teeth diastema 7//8, tooth 1 dorsoanterior (more or less dorsal, but not strictly anterior), pointed anterior teeth (including the caniniform tooth 4) and “blunt” posterior teeth. All the teeth are mesiodistally longer than linguolabially, more convex labially than lingually, carinated but without denticles (not ziphodont); the dentary caniniform tooth 4 is the highest tooth (on the first festoon) and the longest at its alveolus border. The occlusion is lingual, with the premaxilla-maxilla externally overlapping the dentary.

Allodaposuchidae are characterised by the larger 10th tooth in the medioposterior tooth part (second festoon). The splenial does not participate in the symphysis:

but either it is in contact with the posterior border (*Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*) or it is close, with a short distance; and the symphysis is relatively short, at teeth 3–4–5, maximum not exceeding the level of the tooth 6 in *Ma. affuvelensis* (needing a confirmation in some species). In brevirostrine forms, teeth are grouped in sets, but with particularities. In 16 teeth (exceptions: 14 in *Lohuecosuchus megadontos* and 17 in *Agaresuchus fontisensis*), the teeth are less large (wide) labiolingually than mesiodistally (long). Set 1 (festoon 1) has anterior teeth 1–7 (with close teeth 3–7), a diastema 7//8, and an eventual supplementary short diastema 6//7; except: in *Agaresuchus fontisensis* (with short diastema 5//6 instead of 6//7 and with distanced thinner appearing teeth); and in *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis* (with rounded larger teeth, from the preserved root section in alveoli). The enamel is smooth in pointed teeth: in set 1 (festoon 1), teeth 1–3, larger tooth 4 (smooth-fluted), teeth 5–7; in teeth 8–10 of set 2 (festoons 2); the enamel is ornamented wrinkled in “blunt” (not being globulous) teeth of two subsets: teeth 11–12 and 13–16 (festoons 2–3); these latter shorter teeth have a more rounded carina contour, without a horizontal flat surface at the apex; but with a carina either shortly horizontal at the apex or very briefly pointed, depending on the species. Ornamented wrinkled enamel is known on all the *Ma. affuvelensis* posterior teeth (11–15), in a few isolated teeth of some species, and it is suspected on all posterior teeth of the allodaposuchid species (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997; Blanco 2014). Wrinkled enamel is visible in magnified views. The distribution of numerous fine ridges is in a particular network (from base to tip) on the crown surface, unlike other taxa with a different wrinkled enamel morphotype (Ösi, 2013; Prasad & Lapparent de Broin, 2002, figs)

After the Lower Campanian *Ma. affuvelensis*, the variability of allodapsuchids from the Campanian to the Maastrichtian concerns the proportions of the festoons of the lower jaw, in parallel to other eusuchians particularities: lowering of the tooth height with softening of the festoons, widening of the angle of the slopes of the festoons (from 130° in *Ma. affuvelensis* and *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* to 145° – to 160° in *Ischyrochampsia*), lowering and shortening of the symphyseal part, from the level of tooth 6 to tooth 4, lengthening of the dental part with teeth, and either lengthening of the distances between the teeth (species with relatively fine teeth) or narrowing of the interalveolar spaces by widening of the teeth (large teeth of *Lo. Megadontos*, *Ischyrochampsia*).

A detailed redescription of the teeth according to all the characters (contours, proportions, surface elements given above) is necessary for each allodaposuchid species, which could highlight the taxonomic variability. It is necessary to review the different maxillary and dentary morphotypes of the teeth (crown, root and root-crown boundary), according to each skull and each dentary

position. Thus, in summary, the crown can be protruding above the root, have a diameter at the level of the carinae larger than the root; and consequently, the root can have a diameter shorter than that of the crown, it can be cylindrical or subcylindrical, or with obliquely diverging edges, or slightly, partially swollen towards mid-length. In allodaposuchids, it is acquired that there is never a strongly marked groove at the crown-crown limit. Lingual flutation on one face affects some lower or upper pointed teeth; ridges on both surfaces seem to be known only in *Ischyrochampsia*. The maxillary teeth appear taller for their length than the posterior dentaries, i.e. they appear relatively shorter mesiodistally than the dentaries.

An additional dentary character should be associated: the external dentary fenestra. Known to be very reduced, or even absent, in Allodaposuchids, it is unknown in *Allodaposuchus precedens*, and its absence is suspected in *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*.

6. RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN CROCODILES OF THE ISLANDS OF THE WESTERN AND CENTRAL EUROPEAN ARCHIPELAGO AT THE END OF THE CRETACEOUS. PALAEOGEOGRAPHY

6.1. Overview of European brevirostrine crocodiles of the Upper Cretaceous other than the taxa of Matheron (1869)

Massaliasuchus affuvelensis appears to be the earliest differentiated Allodaposuchidae species, morphologically less derived by a narrower splenial-symphysis contact, with a relatively longer and taller symphyseal portion, taller festoons, and a relatively shorter dentary series. This is consistent with its relatively basal stratigraphic position in the Early Campanian. A re-evaluation of the possible migration routes of reptilian species, including Allodaposuchidae, in the Cretaceous, and of the interrelations between taxa could therefore be considered. A Hungarian “*Allodaposuchus*-like” form (Csiki-Sava *et al.* 2015) (Tabl. 1) has been identified from the Hungarian Santonian Basin, in the Bakony Mountains at Iharkút (Csehbánya Formation) (Ösi *et al.*, 2007). It was previously presented as “*Hylaeochampsidae* gen. et sp. indet.” in Rabi & Delfino (2012) and as “*Alligatoroidea* indet.” in Rabi (2005). Its possible relationships with allodaposuchids, especially by comparison with *Allodaposuchus precedens*, *Massaliasuchus* and *Musturzabalsuchus*, were preliminarily examined by Rabi & Delfino (2012). In addition to the cranial and mandibular features not preserved in *Massaliasuchus*, the authors mentioned mandibular features that they consider similar to those of *Massaliasuchus* and *Musturzabalsuchus* (*Al. precedens*, the absence of a mandible being excluded):

- The dentary portion anterior to the 4th alveolus is short, but this is the case in other forms, such as *Diplocynodon*, “*Asiatosuchus*” *depressifrons*, Gosau *Doratodon* and Gonwanian forms.
- The 4th dentary alveolus is the largest and there is a diastema after the seventh tooth, a feature shared by allodaposuchids, but also by many brevirostrine forms, as seen above.
- The splenial does not reach the symphysis, a feature shared by allodaposuchids and by various other brevirostrine forms, *Massaliasuchus* excepted, which was unknown at the authors’ time.
- The splenial anterior tip passes ventral to the Meckelian canal: this is not valid at a familial level. In allodaposuchids, the superior tip is anterior to the inferior tip or both are at the same distance, and both are more to less close to the symphysis, or at its contact in *Massaliasuchus* (previous character).
- The 12th tooth has the largest alveolus, caudal to the 4th: the largest posterior tooth is a crocodylian discriminant character, but the 12th largest is not shared by any allodaposuchid (*Massaliasuchus* included): in all allodaposuchid species, the largest posterior tooth is the 10th. As noted by Delfino (Rabi & Delfino, 2012; Delfino pers. com.) a 12th largest tooth (caudal to the 4th) does not attest to the belonging of this Hungarian form to Allodaposuchidae.

Despite this assertion, this Hungarian form was considered as “*Allodaposuchus* like” and “*Allodaposuchus*” by Csiki-Sava *et al.* (2015: p. 33, table 1). The latter authors mentioned the existence of some isolated crocodyliform teeth, similar to those of this *Allodaposuchus*-like form from Iharkút, in the Ajka Coal Formation (same Santonian Hungary Basin), without figures and description.

Acynodon: The genus is often sympatric with Allodaposuchids in Occitanie-Provence and Iberian Campano-Maastrichtian basins, notably in the late Campanian of Fox-Amphoux (Fig. 1) and perhaps in the lower Rognacian (Matheron, 1869b) (Tabl. 1) (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997, 1999; Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015; Martin, 2010a; Martin *et al.*, 2015). The particularly short skull of *Acynodon*, extremely brevirostrine, with a markedly broad and rounded shape, has a peculiar dentition. It comprises rounded, bulbous, and spatulate posterior teeth, grooved by a few ridges joining the horizontal ridge at the apex, and some of them (at least) have very divergent root edges. These teeth therefore have coarsely wrinkled enamel, as a whole like many crocodiles of various taxa, including *Ma. affuvelensis*. However, the teeth are globose, and the parallel longitudinal ridges of this enamel are larger than in allodaposuchids, and not distributed over the tooth in the partial network of *Ma. affuvelensis* (Blanco *et al.* 2020; Buscalioni *et al.*, 1999, fig. 9; Martin, 2010b; Martin & Buffetaut, 2005; Ösi, 2013); the ridges are neither spread out as in “*Asiatosuchus*” *depressifrons* (in his own way: see above); and the shape of the teeth is clearly different.

These different dentary characters underline the different peculiarity of the teeth of allodaposuchids. Along the study of the Arc Syncline Basin, Matheron (1869a, b) named and described three crocodiles: “*Crocodylus affuvelensis*”, “*Crocodylus blavieri*” Gray, 1831 and “*Crocodylus vetustus*” (unpreserved type material, *nomen dubium*). The latter comes from the basal Upper Rognacian, the Nerthe tunnel, the limestone of the Rognac station, which also yielded *Rhabdodon priscum* (sic) Matheron, 1869a) (see above). Matheron (1869a) provided a brief description of the teeth, showing them to be different from the teeth of “*Crocodylus*” (i.e., *Ma. affuvelensis*), indicating that they might belong to *Acynodon*: “Les dents [maxillaires] postérieures ont une couronne obtuse qui est séparée de la racine par un étranglement et sur le sommet de laquelle on observe de légères rugosités rayonnantes” (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997, 1999; Blanco *et al.*, 2020; Ösi, 2013). The Arc Syncline “*Cr.*” *vetustus* level is correlated with that of Fox-Amphoux locality (Fig. 1), which yielded *Acynodon* teeth (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1997; Martin, 2010b), and *Allodaposuchus* cf. *precedens* in Martin (2010b), that species which became *Lohuecosuchus mechinorum* Narváez *et al.*, 2015 (additional material observed of MNHN. F.Fox coll. from Métisson; Broin *et al.*, 1980). Coexistence of *Acynodon* with *Ma. affuvelensis* is unknown but *Acynodon* surely coexisted with Campanian s. l. allodaposuchids. It was mentioned as present in the Santonian-Campanian of Italy (Delfino *et al.*, 2008b) but not precisely stratigraphically. In Central Europe, the question is whether *Acynodon* s. s. is sympatric with *Al. precedens* in the Hațeg Basin (Martin *et al.*, 2006), as in other Central European areas (Ösi, 2013), at a time close to the approximate time it is present in Western Europe; or if it was only represented by the *Acynodon* clade. A set of teeth of the Hațeg Basin is attributed to cf. *Acynodon* sp. or to a “*Acynodon* like” species by variation in the tooth dentition. Clearly, by their globular shape and ornamentation, at least two of these teeth are possibly attributable to this genus *Acynodon* (Martin, 2010a, fig. 7; Martin & Buffetaut, 2005; Martin *et al.*, 2006, pl. 1 figs 5–7). Even with variability at the generic level, the clade at least is therefore probably present in the Hațeg Basin (Central Europe) (Ösi 2013; Ösi *et al.*, 2012).

Iharkutosuchus makadii Ösi *et al.*, 2007: Originating from the Santonian of Hungary, this species is a mesorostrine form which presents multicuspid teeth. It is unknown in the southwestern European area, late Santonian Valdonnian of the Arc syncline included. Its coexistence with Allodaposuchidae in the Hungary Basin is not attested (Ösi, 2008; Ösi *et al.*, 2007, 2012; Rabi & Delfino, 2012). *Doratodon carcharidens* (Bunzel, 1871): This form from the lower Campanian of Muthmannsdorf (Austria) (Buffetaut, 1979; Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015): bears denticulated teeth of a particular ziphodont morphotype and it is considered as having a Gondwanian origin. The genus is considered as represented in Spain by *Doratodon*

ibericus Company *et al.*, 2005 (late Campanian of Spain). This should therefore indicate a relationship between the western and central European regions in the Campanian period. But this relationship seems, at best, to be at a generic level only. Given that the duration of the actual geographical relationships between the two island basins is not specified, the belonging of *Do. ibericus* to the genus *Doratodon* itself or only to its clade could be considered (as suggested by Godinot *et al.*, 2018). The precise relationship of this Spanish form to western ziphodont sebecosuchians, such as *Iberosuchus* Antunes, 1975 (a Gondwanan form from the western Eocene), as well as to the Austrian *Doratodon* type material, also deserves to be examined.

6.2. Relationships between islands in the Western and Central European archipelago at the end of the Cretaceous: Comparisons help to understand the shared presence of crocodiles and turtles

Allodaposuchidae have been suggested as related to Hylaeochampsidae, based on the (poorly known) skull of *Hylaeochampsia vectiana* Owen, 1874, Barremian of the Isle of Wight (Martin *et al.*, 2015). Being a form without known dentary and teeth, relationships between *Allodaposuchus* and Hylaeochampsidae were estimated based on skull bones. At least, Allodaposuchidae differ from *H. vectiana* by the brevirostral morphotype. At the erection of the family Allodaposuchidae, Narváez *et al.*, 2015 proposed Allodaposuchidae and Hylaeochampsidae as sister clades. While Blanco (2021), notably considering the importance of the postcranial in the taxa definitions, separates Hylaeochampsidae from Allodaposuchidae, situating the last in the “Crocodylia”. Rio & Mannion (2021) consider various possibilities for these familial relationships. The early Campanian (Cr33r) *Ma. affuvelensis* is here considered as the oldest preserved species of the allodaposuchid lineage, up to now. In the absence of any known dentary, the strongly festooned skull (Delfino *et al.*, 2008a) of *Allodaposuchus precedens* (type species) from Central-Europe, agrees with the dentary strong festooning of *Massaliasuchus affuvelensis*. *Massaliasuchus* is here shown as being a taxon well distinct from other allodaposuchid genera by its dentary. *Ma. affuvelensis* and *Al. precedens* differ in age and were not sympatric (Tabl. 1). It is stated that during the late Cretaceous Allodaposuchidae existed in both western and central-eastern European islands of the European Archipelago domain, in Mesogea (Buscalioni *et al.*, 1999, 2003; Buscalioni & Vullo, 2008; Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015; Martin & Delfino, 2010; Martin *et al.*, 2015). But the questions that remain are:

- When and in what way the Hațeg/Sebes Basin could have been connected to localities in Western Europe so that migration was possible.

- The orientation of the dispersal.
- The relative importance of geographical inter-relationships between the two blocks.

This has already been suggested by several hypotheses, i.e. (Blanco, 2021) and others cited above. Stratigraphic comparisons, level by level, during the Santonian-Maastrichtian time interval is difficult because stratigraphic equivalences between the localities are not always stated. However, thanks to paleomagnetostratigraphy, before the presumed early-middle Maastrichtian time of the type species *Al. precedens*, no doubt several different allodaposuchid species (Tabl. 1) clearly existed in the western block, as soon as at early Campanian with *Massaliasuchus affivelensis* first, and just after, with the late Campanian *Musturzabalsuchus buffetauti* and the late Campanian Begudo-Rognacian species (Tabl. 1). The allodaposuchid species diversity assumed by Narváez *et al.* (2015) and Blanco (2021) (Tabl. 1) indicates a relatively long separation in time/ or important barriers, allowing such a taxonomic diversification.

Available paleogeographical maps figuring the European Cretaceous Archipelago, are synthetic. The position of the emerged lands is established for transgressive levels. The positions of shorelines are based on fossil marine animals such as ammonites, foraminifers, nannofossils, rudists, corals from carbonate platforms and other possible markers. At the time of a map, chosen for the presence of a studied allodaposuchid species, continental deposits (which eventually had contained allodaposuchid deposits) may be eroded, notably by the transgressive sea waters. In palaeogeographic atlas, regressive periods are not figured (examples in Barrier *et al.* 2018), or rarely for one period (Ziegler, 1988). Thus, it is unknown at which time might have occurred the terrestrial relationships, and particularly if at regressive periods (Odin & Lamaurelle, 2004). One may wonder at what successive periods continental amphibious vertebrates, including crocodiles and turtles, were able to benefit from the best conditions to spread between western and eastern Europe. The continental reptiles concerned here are accustomed to living in freshwater streams and lakes, with a terrestrial margin, at least for burrowing, nesting and sunbathing (with a dependence on water salinity varying according to the species). Their terrestrial dispersal requires a well-established network of freshwater streams. Thus, the contours and geographical proportions of the islands of the archipelago, represented on the proposed maps, may or may not indicate the correct geographical distance that allowed the passage of allodaposuchids between the islands considered (Barrier *et al.*, 2018; Blanco, 2021; Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015; Dercourt *et al.*, 2000; Martin *et al.*, 2015; Puértolas *et al.*, 2016, 2018; Rabi *et al.*, 2013; between others).

During regressive periods, the islands may have been less separated, enough to allow for reptilian migration. Transgressive periods, on the other hand, may have allowed for greater taxonomic diversification. It is well known that crocodiles, like some turtles, could cross temporary brackish waterways without hindrance and could have followed the coasts or crossed short inlets, aided by favorable currents. This assertion is based on the known dispersal abilities of the amphibian-reptilian fauna associated with allodaposuchids, including other crocodiles, which have indicated documented relationships. Notably, some continental families of crocodiles and ziphodont turtles from Gondwana are sympatric with allodaposuchids in the western and central blocks of the archipelago during the Cretaceous. Gondwanan forms may have invaded Europe as early as the Cenomanian transgressions, at least. However, it is evident that the exchange of crocodiles and turtles between the two blocks of the archipelago, at the end of the Cretaceous, was more limited than suggested by syntheses from some palaeogeographic studies (Csiki-Sava *et al.*, 2015). This is confirmed by the low number of taxa shared by the two blocks of the archipelago, which requires a more precise vision of the possible shared presence of crocodiles.

During the Santonian, the Central European Iherkút region of Hungary yielded the hylaeochampsid *Iherkutosuchus makadii* Ösi, 2008 and the indetermined new “allodaposuchid like” form (seen above), both forms being unknown in western islands. Santonian deposits are rarely continental in the western Europe areas, the short terminal regressive Valdonnian of the Arc syncline excepted (Fig. 1).

During the early Campanian, the Central region yielded *Doratodon carcharidens* (Bunzel, 1871), from Muthmannsdorf (Gosau, Austria) (Buffetaut, 1979; Rabi & Sebok, 2015), which is unknown in Western Europe at the early time of *Massaliasuchus*, in the Fuveau lignite Formation. During the middle to late Campanian, the presence of *Doratodon* is postulated in the Western European Archipelago by *D. ibericus* Company *et al.*, 2005, from Chera (Valencia, Spain). This is said sympatric with *Acynodon* and *Musturzabalsuchus* (which is not figured and described). As mentioned above, this attribution to the genus *Doratodon* itself and its precise age – in correlation with the *Do. carcharidens* locality at the early Campanian of Gosau – needs a revision (Godinot *et al.*, 2018; Rabi & Sebok, 2015). Thus, the shared Campanian *Doratodon* presence in Spain and Austria, is given based on specimens which are not asserted as exactly present at the same time. The two species might belong or not to the same genus. Even the Austrian and Spanish species might be just parts of a particular Gondwanian clade, for example a “*Doratodon-Iberosuchus*” group.

The Romanian species *Allodaposuchus precedens* was recognised in the western block in the late Campanian (Begdian) of Velaux-La Bastide Neuve locality by Martin *et al.* (2015). Previously, the presence of *Al. precedens* had been hypothesised in the slightly younger late Campanian (Lower Rognacian) of Fox-Amphoux with *Al. cf. precedens* by Martin, 2010a. Both Campanian species are older in age than the Maastrichtian *Al. precedens*. The first species, *Al. precedens* from Velaux, the older in age, was reevaluated as *Al. iberoarmoricanus* Blanco, 2021. The second species from Fox-Amphoux, younger and closer in age to *Al. precedens* from Romania, was reconsidered as distinct at the genus level, by its attribution to *Lohuecosuchus mechinorum* Narváez *et al.*, 2015. Thus, these taxonomic reevaluations have distanced the interfamily relationships of the two forms from the Romanian type species of the Hațeg/Sebes Basin. Meanwhile, the Maastrichtian of Spain provided allodaposuchid species that were mostly assigned to new genera (Tabl. 1). However, two species of the Tremp Basin, from two early Maastrichtian distinct levels, remain attributed to the genus *Allodaposuchus*: *Al. hulki* Blanco *et al.*, 2015 and *Al. palustris* Blanco *et al.*, 2014 (Tabl. 1). However, the last species possibly needs a generic reattribution, when considering its dentary characters (Tables 1, 3). Whatever the geographical distances according to the stratigraphic times, the simultaneous genus *Allodaposuchus* presence during the early-middle Maastrichtian in both Archipelago regions (Tremp and Hațeg) postulates a previous differentiation (Tabl. 1). Supporting Blanco (2021), a west-eastern direction of migration is preferred for the family, because the allodaposuchids are firstly identified in Western Europe and widely distributed there, as soon as early Campanian times (Tabl. 1). The presence of an *Acynodon*-like form, sympatric with *Al. precedens* in the Hațeg basin of Romania, at early middle Maastrichtian, is postulated. The answer to this possibility might help, when evaluating the stratigraphic time of possible geographical relationships between the Archipelago blocks. *Doratodon* shared presence in the two blocks also supports the possibility of migrations between Western and Central Europe during the Campanian. As for *Acynodon*, the material needs a taxonomic revision (Martin *et al.* 2006).

Among the continental freshwater reptile fauna associated with allodaposuchids, perhaps sharing identical dispersal patterns, several turtles provide information on the limited interconnections between blocks in the archipelago. Continental terrestrial forms such as tortoises, squamates, and dinosaurian forms have their own dispersal patterns. The study shows that turtle records shared between blocks were limited to aquatic forms (freshwater to littoral). There is a particular endemism of tortoise taxa in the Late Cretaceous of the Central European zone of Hungary (Santonian), Austria (Gosau, Lower Campanian)

and Romania (Hațeg Basin, early Middle Maastrichtian, according to Panaiotu & Panaiotu, 2010) (Codrea *et al.* 2002; Lapparent de Broin & Murelaga, 1999; Nopcsa, 1923; Rabi *et al.*, 2013).

The sympatric occurrence of terrestrial turtles with *Al. precedens* in the Hațeg Basin is limited to the endemic *Kallokibotion bajazidi* Nopcsa, 1923. Unlike this terrestrial form, at this time, allodaposuchids from western Europe are sympatric with *Solemys*, type species *Solemys gaudryi* (Matheron, 1869a) (see Geological Context). This is part of a family widespread in North America and Europe from the Late Jurassic-Early Cretaceous boundary. *Solemys* is widely distributed in the Ibero-French Campano-Maastrichtian zone, but is not recognised in the Central European part (Lapparent de Broin & Murelaga, 1999). In contrast, two families of littoral or freshwater turtles are present in western and central European sites from the Late Cretaceous, from the Santonian to the Maastrichtian-Palaeocene boundary: the Gondwanan Bothremydidae and the Pangeo-Laurasiatic Dortokidae. But no genera or species of these two families are shared in both the western and central blocks. A bothremydid turtle from the Santonian of Iharút (Hungary) (seen above this site) has been assigned to the western European genus *Foxemys*: *F. trabanti* Rabi *et al.*, 2011 (Rabi & Botfalvai, 2006). In Europe, *Foxemys* occurs at Fox-Amphoux, its type locality, in sympatry with *Lohuecosuchus* (formerly "*Allodaposuchus*") *mechinorum*. But by reconsidering the morphology of its skull (columella area), its lower jaw and its shell characters, the Santonian *F. trabanti* does not belong to the genus *Foxemys*. It is neither a member of *Polysternon*, nor any other genus of Iberian-French bothremydids from Western Europe (from the Fuveau Matheron Arc syncline and its surroundings up to Portugal) (Antunes & Broin 1988; Broin, 1977, Pérez-García *et al.*, 2012). Nevertheless, the Hungarian species clearly appears as a member of the family Bothremydidae, as previously indicated (Rabi & Botfalvai, 2006; Rabi & Tong, 2007; Rabi *et al.*, 2011). For this, it seems necessary to erect a new genus.

Of continental Afro-South American Gondwanan origin, during the late Jurassic to early Cretaceous, the family Bothremydidae spread widely, from Africa and its tributaries, at least since the early Cenomanian, around the Mesogean and Atlantic margins (Palestine, Iberia and France) during the Cretaceous (Antunes & Broin, 1988; Haas, 1978a, b; Lapparent de Broin, 2000; Lapparent de Broin & Murelaga, 1999; Marmi *et al.*, 2012; Pérez-García *et al.*, 2017): i.e., for Cretaceous times, the Hungarian presence of "*Foxemys*" *trabanti* only indicates the presence of a particular Bothremydidae in the central block during the Santonian, related or not to those of the western zone, and, so far, not associated with allodaposuchids. After the Hungarian Santonian site, the family is (so far) not recognised in Central

Europe. Whereas this family Bothremydidae is known in the Western Archipelago block with other genera only from the Lower Campanian to the Upper Maastrichtian (after the Upper Santonian marine regression), and in synchrony with allodaposuchids. The other turtle family shared by Western and Central Europe during the Cretaceous is the pleurodiran Dortokidae. Known from the Early Cretaceous in Western Europe (Jacobs *et al.*, 2023; Lapparent de Broin & Murelaga, 1997, 1999; Murelaga-Bereikua, 1998), it is found in association with allodaposuchids from western Campanian and Maastrichtian sites. In the Hungarian (Santonian) and Austrian (Early Campanian) areas, with other turtles endemic to Gosau (Lapparent de Broin & Murelaga, 1999), partial specimens of dortokids are present. But they are not confirmed as belonging to the Ibero-French *Dortoka* lineage from the western Campano-Maastrichtian. Thus, at Iharkút (Hungary), the figured dortokid ilium (Rabi *et al.*, 2013, Fig. 19.2h) conforms to that of the Romanian Palaeocene *Ronella* Lapparent de Broin, 1999 (in Gheerbrant *et al.*, 2000) and not to that of the Campanian-Maastrichtian Franco-Iberian *Dortoka* (s. s.) lineage (Lapparent de Broin *et al.*, 2004, pl. 2, figs 7-8). In the present paper, the Hungarian Santonian dortokids are considered to be related to the local form “*Dortoka*” *vremeri* Augustin *et al.*, 2021 (see Vremir 2010) from the Maastrichtian Romanian Hațeg Basin. This dortokid form sympatric with *Al. precedens* in the Hațeg Basin is not closely related to the Western Cretaceous *Dortoka* branch. Its morphology indicates a direct relationship with the Palaeocene Romanian *Ronella* (carapace elements, postcranial bones) rather than with the European *Dortoka*. It is here considered that the European and Romanian forms have been wrongly synonymized as “*Dortoka*” by Augustin *et al.* (2021). The genus *Muehlbachia* of “*Muehlbachia nopcsai* Vremir & Codrea, 2009” (*nomen nudum*) could be validated, rightly according to the ICZN. For both dortokidae and bothremydidae, there are no proven contacts between the two blocks of the archipelago at the times of coexistence of Allodaposuchidae, i.e. during the Lower-Middle Maastrichtian.

Finally, in Western Europe, from the end of the Campanian, before the appearance of *Allodaposuchus precedens* in Romania at the beginning of the Middle Maastrichtian, a greater taxonomic diversity of allodaposuchids was highlighted during the Late Cretaceous (Blanco & Brochu, 2017; Blanco 2021) (Tabl. 1). In the Late Cretaceous, Allodaposuchidae are attested in several western localities with European turtles (local bothremydids with foxemydids, *Solemys*, *Dortoka*). These western turtle taxa are different from those of the central zone (local bothremydid, eastern dortokid, *Kallokibotion*), notably in association with *Allodaposuchus precedens*. The question of the degree of similarity of crocodylian associations in the two blocks

of the archipelago, whether at the generic or specific level, is valid for *Allodaposuchus* as for the *Doratodon* and *Acynodon* material. As outlined here for the turtles Bothremydidae and Dortokidae, new research on the definitions of crocodylian taxa, and, first of all, on the Allodaposuchidae, could update the question. The dentary and its dentition constitute useful elements for redefining taxonomic determinations. Already, it is assumed that the two blocks of the archipelago each present their particularities in terms of taxonomic associations, similarities and differences. At least the existence of a lineage consisting of Allodaposuchids is recognised in the western and central European archipelago of the Upper Cretaceous, the oldest element of which is here considered to be the western *Massaliasuchus affivelensis*, from the Lower Campanian of Fuveau.

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REFERENCES

- Alvarez W., Arthur M. A., Fischer A. G., Lowrie W., Napoleone G., Premoli Silva I. & Roggenbathen W. M. 1977. Upper

- Cretaceous -Palaeocene magnetic stratigraphy at Gubbio, Italy: V. Type section for the Late Cretaceous - Palaeocene geomagnetic reversal time scale. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, 88:383–389.
- Andrews C. W. 1913. On the skull and part of the skeleton of a crocodile from the Middle Purbeck of Swanage, with the description of a new species (*Pholidosaurus laevis*) and a note on the skull of *Hylaeochampsia*. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History, London* 11:485–494.
- Antunes M.T., 1975. *Iberosuchus*, un crocodile sébécosuchien nouveau, l'Éocène ibérique au Nord de la Chaîne Centrale et l'origine du canyon de Nazaré. *Comunicações dos Serviços Geológicos do Portugal*, 49:285–330.
- Antunes M. T. & Broin F. de 1988. Le Crétacé terminal de Beira Litoral, Portugal : Antunes M.T., remarques stratigraphiques et écologiques; Broin F. de, étude complémentaire de *Rosasia soutoi* (Chelonii, Bothremyidae). *Ciências da Terra (UNL)* 9: 153-200.
- Arlhac P. & Rouire J. & Contributeurs 1977. *Carte géologique de la France, Martigues -Marseille à 1/50000*, 1020-1043, XXXI-44-45, 2^e édition. Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières (Orléans).
- Augustin F. J., Csiki-Sava Z., Matzke A.T., Botfalvai G. & Rabi M. 2021. A new latest Cretaceous pleurodiran turtle (Testudinata: *Dortokidae*) from the Hațeg Basin (Romania) documents end-Cretaceous faunal provinciality and selective survival during the K-Pg extinction. *Journal of Systematic Palaeontology*, 19:15:1059–1081, Doi: 10.1080/14772019.2021.2009583—ch.
- Babinot J. F. & Durand J.-P. 1980. Le Valdonnien - Le Fuvélien - Le Bégudien - Le Rognacien - Le Vitrollien. In: Cavelier & Roger (coord.) : Les étages français et leurs stratotypes. *Mémoires du Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières* (B.R.G.M.) 109 : 171-192.
- Babinot J. F. & Freydet P. (coord.), Amiot M., Bilotte M., Broin F. de, Colombo F., Durand J.-P., Feist M., Floquet M., Gayet M., Lange-Badré B., Masriera A., Massieux M., Medus J., Tambareau Y., Ullastre J. & Villatte J. 1983. Le Sénonien supérieur continental de la France méridionale en France et Espagne septentrionale : état des connaissances biostratigraphiques. *Géologie méditerranéenne*, 10 (3-4) : 245-268.
- Barrier E., Vrielynck B. & Brunet M.-F. 2018. *Paleotectonic Reconstruction of the Central Tethyan Realm. Tectono-Sedimentary-Palinspastic maps from Late Permian to Pliocene*. Atlas Darius 20 maps. CCGM/CGMW, Paris Publisher, <http://www.ccgmg.org>
- Benammi M., Urrutia-Fucugauchi J. & Vianey-Liaud M. 2006. Preliminary magnetostratigraphic study of the Late Cretaceous dinosaur site from Villeveyrac-Mèze Basin, southern France. *International Geological Review*, 48:89–96. Doi : <https://doi.org/10.2747/0020-6814.48.1.89>
- Blainville H. M. Ducrotay de 1855. *Ostéographie ou Description iconographique comparée du squelette et du système dentaire des mammifères récents et fossiles pour servir de base à la zoologie et à la géologie. Quaternatès — Maldentés*, 1839-1864. Atlas 4, 93 Planches, J. B. Baillière et fils, Paris.
- Blanco A. 2021. Importance of the postcranial skeleton in eusuchian phylogeny: Reassessing the systematics of allodaposuchid crocodylians. *PLoS ONE*, 16 (6): e0251900. Doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0251900.
- Blanco A. & Brochu C. A. 2017. Intra- and interspecific variability in allodaposuchid crocodylomorphs and the status of western European taxa. *Historical Biology*, 29 (4): 495–508. Doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2016.1201081
- Blanco A., Puértolas-Pascual E., Marmi J., Vila, B. & Sellés A. G. 2014. *Allodaposuchus palustris* sp. nov. from the Upper Cretaceous of Fumanya (South-Eastern Pyrenees, Iberian Peninsula): systematics, palaeoecology and palaeobiogeography of the enigmatic allodaposuchian crocodylians. *PLoS ONE*, 9: e115837: 34 p. Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0115837
- Blanco A., Fortuny J., Vicente A., Luján A. H., García-Marça J. A. & Sellés A. 2015. A new species of *Allodaposuchus* (Eusuchia, Crocodylia) from the Maastrichtian (Late Cretaceous) of Spain: phylogenetic and paleobiological implications. *PeerJ.*, 3, e1171, 35p. Doi. 10.7717/peerj.1171.
- Blanco A, Puértolas-Pascual E. & Marmi J. 2018. *Assessing the crocodylomorph diversity in the Maastrichtian (Late Cretaceous) of Ibero-Armorica, based on tooth qualitative traits*. In: 1st European Symposium on the Evolution of Crocodylomorpha. XVI Annual Meeting of the European Association of Vertebrate Palaeontologists, Nova University of Lisbon (UNL) in Caparica, Portugal, EAVP 2018, Abstract book. <https://docentes.fct.unl.pt/sites/default/files/omateus/files/eavp>.
- Blanco A., Puértolas-Pascual E., Marmi J., Moncunill-Solé B., Llácer S. & Rössner G. E. 2020. Late Cretaceous (Maastrichtian) crocodyliiforms from north-eastern Iberia: a first attempt to explain the crocodyliiform diversity based on tooth qualitative traits. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 189:584–617. Doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlzl106.
- Brochu, A. 2013. Phylogenetic relationships of Palaeogene ziphodont eusuchians and the status of *Pristichampsus* Gervais, 1853. *Earth and Environmental Science Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh*. 103 (3–4): 521–550 Doi: 10.1017/S1200
- Broin F. de 1977. Contribution à l'étude des Chéloniens. Chéloniens continentaux du Crétacé et du Tertiaire de France. *Mémoires du Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris C*, 38 : I-IX, 1-366.
- Broin F. de, Buffetaut E., Cappetta H., Kérourio P., Koeniguer J.-C., Russell D., Secrétan S., Sigogneau-Russell D., Taquet Ph. & Wenz S. 1980. Nouvelles découvertes de Vertébrés maestrichtiens dans le gisement de Fox-Amphoux (Var). 8e R.A.S.T., Marseille 1980, *Société Géologique de France* (Ed.) : 68.
- Buffetaut E. 1979. Revision der Crocodylia (Reptilia) aus der Gosau-Schichten (Ober-Kreide) von Österreich. *Beiträge zur Paläontologie von Österreich*, 6: 89–105.
- Buffetaut E., Angst D., Claude J., Tong H., Amoros A., Boschetto D., Chenet J.-P., Clavel D., Maggia B. & Roques T. 2021. Les niveaux à vertébrés fossiles du Crétacé supérieur de Castigno et Combeville (Villespassans, Hérault) : historique et nouvelles découvertes. *Carnets Natures*, 8: 41-55. hal-03762287
- Buffetaut E., Costa G., Le Loeuff J., Martin M., Rage J.-Cl., Valentin X. & Tong H. 1996. An Early Campanian Vertebrate Fauna from the Villeveyrac Basin (Hérault, Southern France). *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie Monatshefte*, 1: 1-16.
- Buffetaut E., Le Loeuff J., Tong H., Duffaud S., Cavin L., Garcia G., Ward D. & l'Association culturelle, archéologique et paléontologique de Cruzy 1999. Un nouveau gisement de

- vertébrés du Crétacé supérieur à Cruzy (Hérault, Sud de la France). *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences*, Paris, II A, Sciences de la terre et des planètes/Earth and Planetary Sciences, 328: 203–208.
- Bunzel E. 1871. Die Reptilfauna der Gosau-Formation in der Neuen Welt bei Wiener Neustadt. *Abhandlungen Geologische Reichsanstalt*, 5: 1–18.
- Buscalioni A., Ortega F. & Vasse D. 1997. New crocodiles (Eusuchia: Alligatoidea) from the Upper Cretaceous of southern Europe. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences*, Paris, II A, Sciences de la terre et des planètes/Earth and Planetary Sciences, 325 (7): 525–530.
- Buscalioni A. D., Ortega F. & Vasse D. 1999. The Upper Cretaceous crocodylian assemblage from Laño (Northcentral Spain): implications in the knowledge of the finicretaceous European faunas. *Estudios del Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Alava*, 14 (1): 213–233.
- Buscalioni A., Ortega F., Weishampel D. & Jianu C. 2001. A revision of the crocodyliform *Allodaposuchus precedens* from the Upper Cretaceous of the Hateg Basin, Romania. Its relevance in the phylogeny of Eusuchia. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 21 (1): 74–86. Doi.org/10.1671/0272-4634(2001)021[0074:AROTCA] 2.0.CO;2
- Buscalioni A. D., Perez-Moreno B. P. & Sanz J. L. 2003. Patrones de reemplazamiento biotico en cocodrilos modernos durante el Cretacico Superior. *Coloquios de Paleontología*: 2003: 77–93. Doi:10.5209/REV_COPA.2003.30319.
- Buscalioni A. D. & Vullo R. 2008. Three steps in the Cretaceous evolution of Crocodylomorpha: example from Barremian to Maastrichtian diversity in the Iberian Peninsula, and what about mid-Cretaceous gap. Mid-Mesozoic Life and Environments. *Documents des Laboratoires de Géologie de Lyon*, 164 : 29–32.
- Cavelier Cl. & Roger J. (coords) 1980. Les étages français et leurs stratotypes français. *Mémoires du Bulletin de Recherches Géologiques et Minières (B.R.G.M.)*, 109 : 295 p.
- Channell J. E. T. & Medizza F. F.† 1981. Upper Cretaceous and Palaeogene magnetic stratigraphy and biostratigraphy from the Venetian (Southern) Alps. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 55 (3): 419–432.
- Coccioni R. & Premoli Silva I. 2015. Revised Upper Albian - Maastrichtian planktonic foraminiferal biostratigraphy and magneto- stratigraphy of the classical Tethyan Gubbio section (Italy). *New Letters on Stratigraphy*, 48 (1): 47–90. Doi.org/10.1127/nos/2015/0055
- Codrea V., Smith Th., Dica P., Folie A., Garcia G., Godefroit P. & Van Itterbeecke J. 2002. Dinosaur egg nests, mammals and other vertebrates from a new Maastrichtian site of the Hateg Basin (Romania). *Comptes Rendus Palevol*, 1 : 173–180. Doi.org/10.1016/S1631-0683%2802%2900021-0
- Company J., Suberbiola X. P., Ruiz-Omeñaca J. I. & Buscalioni A. D. 2005. A new species of *Doratodon* (Crocodyliformes: Ziphosuchia) from the Late Cretaceous of Spain. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 25 (2): 343–353. Doi.org/10.1671/0272-4634 (2005) 025 [0343:ANSODC] 2.0.CO;2
- Cope E. D. 1861. Recent species of Emydosaurian reptiles represented in the Museum of the Academy. *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia*, 1860:549–551.
- Corral J.-C., Berreteaga A., Poyato-Ariza F. J., Bardet N., Cappetta H., Floquet M., Astibia H., Badiola A. & Pereda-Suberbiola X. 2021. Stratigraphy, age, and vertebrate palaeontology of the latest Cretaceous Quintanilla la Ojada locality (Basque-Cantabrian Region, northern Spain): a synthesis. In: A. Folie, E. Buffetaut E., N. Bardet, A. Houssaye, E. Gheerbrant & M. Laurin (Eds), Palaeobiology and palaeobiogeography of amphibians and reptiles: An homage to Jean-Claude Rage. *Comptes Rendus Palevol*, 20 (7) : 91–117. Doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2021v20a7
- Corral J.-C., Pueyo E. L., Berreteaga A., Rodríguez-Pintó A., Elisa Sánchez S., & Pereda-Suberbiola X. 2016. Magnetostratigraphy and lithostratigraphy of the Laño vertebrate-site: Implications in the uppermost Cretaceous chronostratigraphy of the Basque-Cantabrian Region. *Cretaceous Research*, 57:473–489. Doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2015.07.0150195-6671
- Csiki-Sava Z., Buffetaut E., Ősi A., Pereda-Suberbiola X. & Brusatte S. L. 2015. Island life in the Cretaceous—faunal composition, biogeography, evolution, and extinction of land-living vertebrates on the Late Cretaceous European archipelago. *ZooKeys*, 4 69:1–161. Doi : 10.3897/zookeys.469.8439
- Cuvier G. 1824. *Recherches sur les Ossemens fossiles, où l'on rétablit les caractères de plusieurs animaux dont les révolutions du globe ont détruit les espèces*. Sur les ossemens de crocodiles. 2^e éd. 5 (2) 4 : *Des os de crocodiles des lignites de Provence* : 164–165, Atlas : pl. 6, fig. 17. Paris, Dufour et D'Ocagne.
- Cuvier G. 1836. *Recherches sur les Ossemens fossiles, où l'on rétablit les caractères de plusieurs animaux dont les révolutions du globe ont détruit les espèces*. 4^e éd. 9 (3) 4 : 526–527. Atlas (2) : pl. 234, fig. 17. Paris, Dufour et D'Ocagne.
- Delfino M. & Smith T. 2009. A reassessment of the morphology and taxonomic status of “*Crocodylus*” *depressifrons* Blainville, 1855 (Crocodylia, Crocodyloidea) based on the Early Eocene remains from Belgium. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 156:140–167.
- Delfino M., Codrea V., Folie A., Dica P., Godefroit P. & Smith T. 2008a. A complete skull of *Allodaposuchus precedens* Nopcsa, 1928 (Eusuchia) and a reassessment of the morphology of the taxon based on the Romanian remains. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 28:111–122. Doi.org/10.1671/0272-4634 (2008) 28 [111:ACSOAP] 2.0.CO;2
- Delfino M, Martin J.E. & Buffetaut E. 2008b. A new species of *Acynodon* (Crocodylia) from the Upper Cretaceous (Santonian—Campanian) of Villaggio del Pescatore, Italy. *Palaeontology*, 51:1091–1106. Doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4983.2008.00800.x
- Delfino M., Martin J. E., Lapparent de Broin F. de & Smith T. 2017. Evidence for a pre-PETM dispersal of the earliest European crocodyloids. *Historical Biology*: 20 p. doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2017.1396323.
- Dercourt J., Gaetani M., Vrielynck B., Barrier E., Biju-Duval B., Brunet M.-F., Cadet J.— P., Crasquin S. & Sandulescu M. (Eds) 2000. *Atlas Peri-Tethys. Palaeogeographical maps*. Commission de la Carte Géologique du Monde/ Commission for the Geological Map of the World, Paris, 24 maps: 269 p.
- Díez Díaz, V., Garcia, G., Knoll, F., Suberbiola, X. P., & Valentin, X. 2012. New cranial remains of titanosaurian

- sauropod dinosaurs from the Late Cretaceous of Fox-Amphoux-Métisson (Var, SE France). *Proceedings of the Geologists' Association*, 123: 626-637.
- García G., Bardet, N. Houssaye, A., Pereda-Suberbiola X. & Valentin X. 2015. Mosasauroid (Squamata) discovery in the Late Cretaceous (Early Campanian) continental deposits of Villeveyrac—L'Olivet, southern France. *Comptes Rendus Palevol*, 14 : 495–505. Doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2015.05.002
- García G., Duffaud S., Feist M., Marandat B., Tambareau Y., Villatte J. & Sigé B. 2000. La Neuve, gisement à plantes, invertébrés et vertébrés du Bégudien (Sénonien supérieur continental) du bassin d'Aix-en-Provence. *Geodiversitas*, 22 : 325–348.
- García G. & Vianey-Liaud M. 2001. Dinosaur eggshells as biochronological markers in Upper Cretaceous continental deposits. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 169:153–164. Doi.org/10.1016/S0031-0182(01)00215-2
- Gardin S., Galbrun B., Thibault N., Coccioni R. & Premoli Silva I. 2012. Bio-magnetostratigraphy for the upper Campanian—Maastrichtian from the Gubbio area, Italy: new results from the Contessa Highway and Bottaccione sections. *Newsletter on Stratigraphy*, 45:75–103. Doi.org/10.1127/0078-0421/2012/0014
- Gheerbrant E., Codrea V., Hosu A., Sen S., Guernet C., Lapparent de Broin F. de & Riveline J. 2000 Découverte de vertébrés dans les Calcaires de Rona (Thanétien ou Sparnacien), Transylvanie, Roumanie : les plus anciens mammifères cénozoïques d'Europe orientale. *Eclogae geologicae Helvetiae* (1999), 92 (3): 517-535.
- Ginsburg L. & Bulot C. 1997. Les *Diplocynodon* (Reptilia, Crocodylia) de l'Orléanien (Miocène inférieur à moyen) de France. *Geodiversitas*, 19 (1): 107-128.
- Gmelin, J. F. 1789. Caroli a Linné, Systema Naturae pp. 1033–1516 in G. E. Beer (ed.), Tom. I. Pars III. Leipzig, Germany.
- Godinot M., Labarrère H.-P., Erfurt J., Franzen J. L., Lange-Badré B., Lapparent de Broin F. de & Vidalenc D. 2018. Un nouveau gisement à vertébrés éocènes, Rouzilhac (MP 10-11), dans la série molassique d'Issel (Aude, France). *Revue de Paléobiologie*, 37 (1) : 143-335. Doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1315461
- Gradstein F. M., Agterberg F. P., Ogg J. G., Hardenbol J., Van Veen P., Thierry J. & Huang Z. 1995. *A Triassic, Jurassic and Cretaceous time scale*. In: Geochronology Time Scales and global Stratigraphic Correlation. Berggren W. A. Kent D. V., Aubry M.-P. & Hardenbol J. (Eds), SEPM, Tulsa, Oklahoma: 95-126.
- Gradstein F. M., Ogg J. G., Schmitz M. D. & Ogg G. M. 2020. *International Chronostratigraphic Chart*. Geologic Time Scale. 1st Edition. Elsevier, Amsterdam.
- Gradstein F. M., Ogg J. G. Schmitz M. & Ogg G. (Eds). 2012. *The Geologic Time Scale*, 2 Volumes. Elsevier, Oxford (UK), Amsterdam, Waltham (USA).
- Gray J. E. 1831. *Synopsis Reptilium; or short descriptions of the species of Reptiles*. Part I. Cataphracta. Treuttel, Wurtz & Co (Eds.) Londres : I-VIII, 1–85.
- Haas G. 1978a. A Cretaceous Pleurodire Turtle from the Surroundings of Jerusalem. *Israel Journal of Zoology*, 27:20–33.
- Haas G. 1978b. A new turtle of the genus *Podocnemis* from the lower Cenomanian of 'Ein Yabrud. *Israel Journal of Zoology*, 27:169–175.
- Hofmann, A. 1885. Crocodiliden aus dem Miocæn der Steiermark. *Beiträge zur Paläontologie von Österreich-Ungarns und des Orients*, 5: 26-35.
- Huxley Th. 1875. On *Stagonolepis robertsoni*, and on the evolution of the Crocodylia. *Quarterly Journal of the Geological Society* 31:423–438.
- Jacobs M. L., Pérez-García A., Martín Jiménez M., Mottram C., Martill D., Gale A., Mattsson O. S. & Wood C. 2023. A well preserved pan-pleurodiran (Dortokidae) turtle from the English Lower Cretaceous and the first radiometric date for the Wessex Formation (Hauterivian—Barremian) of the Isle of Wight, United Kingdom. *Cretaceous Research*, 150:15 p. 105590. Doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2023.105590
- Lapparent A. F. de 1938. Études de paléontologie stratigraphique sur les faunes continentales de Provence. *Mémoire de la Société géologique de France*, 15 (4) 35 : 34 p.
- Lapparent A. F. de 1943. Les dinosaures de France. *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France*, 47 : 5–20
- Lapparent A. F. de 1947. Les dinosaures du crétacé supérieur du Midi de la France. *Mémoires de la Société Géologique de France*, 26 (4) 56 : 1-54.
- Lapparent de Broin F. de. 2000. African chelonians from the Jurassic to the Present. A preliminary catalog of the African fossil chelonians. *Palaeontologia Africana*, 36: 43-82.
- Lapparent de Broin F. de & Murelaga X. 1996. Une nouvelle faune de Chéloniens dans le Crétacé supérieur européen. *Comptes rendus de l'Académie des Sciences Paris*, IIA, 323 : 729-735.
- Lapparent de Broin F. de & Murelaga X. 1999. Turtles from the Upper Cretaceous of Laño (Iberian Peninsula). In: Geology and palaeontology of the Upper Cretaceous vertebrate-bearing beds of the Laño Quarry (Basque-Cantabrian Region, Iberian Peninsula), H. Astibia *et al.* (coords.) *Estudios del Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Alava*, 14 (Num. Esp. 1): 135–211.
- Lapparent de Broin F. de, Murelaga Bereikua X. & Codrea V. 2004. Presence of Dortokidae (Chelonii, Pleurodira) in the earliest Tertiary of the Jibou Formation, Romania: Palaeobiogeographical implications. *Acta Palaeontologica Romaniaiae*, 4: 203-215.
- Laurenti J. N. 1768. *Specimen medicum, exhibens synopsis reptilium emendatam cum experimentis circa venena et antidota reptilium austriacorum*. Vienna: Joan. Thom. Nob. de Trattner: 53–55.
- Le Loeuff J. 1993. European Titanosaurids. *Revue de Paléobiologie*, special volume 7: 105–117.
- Leymerie A. 1876. Garumnien. *Journal officiel*, 21 avril 1876, p. 2836, 1re col.
- Marmi J., Luján A. H., Riera V., Gaete R., Oms O. & Galobart A. 2012. The youngest species of *Polysternon*: A new bothremydid turtle from the uppermost Maastrichtian of the southern Pyrenees. *Cretaceous Research*, 35:133–142.
- Martin J.E. 2010a. New material of the Late Cretaceous globidontan *Acynodon iberoccitanus* (Crocodylia) from southern France. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 27 (2): 362–372. doi.org/10.1671/0272-4634 (2007) 27 [362:NMOTLC] 2.0.CO;2
- Martin J.E. 2010b. *Allodaposuchus Nopsca*, 1928 (Crocodylia, Eusuchia), from the Late Cretaceous of southern France and its relationships to Alligatoroidea. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology*, 30 (3): 756–767. Doi.org/10.1080/02724631003758318
- Martin J.E. 2010c. A new species of *Diplocynodon* (Crocodylia

- (Crocodylia, Alligatoroidea) from the Late Eocene of the Massif Central, France, and the evolution of the genus in the climatic context of the Late Palaeogene. *Geological Magazine*, 147:596–610.
Doi.org/10.1017/S0016756809990161
- Martin J. E. & Buffetaut E. 2005. An overview of the Late Cretaceous crocodylian assemblage from Cruzy, southern France. *Kaupia*, 14:33–40.
- Martin J. E. & Buffetaut E. 2008. *Crocodylus affivelensis* Matheron, 1869 from the Late Cretaceous of southern France: a reassessment. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 152 (3): 567–580.
Doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-3642.2007.00358.x
- Martin J. E., Csiki Z., Grigorescu D. & Buffetaut E. 2006. Late Cretaceous crocodylian diversity in Hațeg Basin, Romania. 4th annual meeting of the European Association of Vertebrate Palaeontologists. *Hantkeniana*, 5: 31–37.
- Martin J. & Delfino M. 2010. Recent advances in the comprehension of the biogeography of Cretaceous European eusuchians. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 293 (3): 406–418.
Doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2009.10.021
- Martin J. E., Delfino M., Garcia G., Godefroit P., Berton S. & Valentin X. 2015. New specimens of *Allodaposuchus precedens* from France: intraspecific variability and the diversity of European Late Cretaceous eusuchians. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*: 25 p.
Doi. 10.1111/zoj.12331.
- Martin J. & Gross M. 2011. Taxonomic clarification of *Diplocynodon* Pomel, 1847 (Crocodylia) from the Miocene of Styria, Austria. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie Abhandlungen*, 261: 177–193.
Doi.org/10.1127/0077-7749/2011/0159
- Martin J. E., Smith T., Lapparent de Broin F. de, Escuillié F. & Delfino M. 2014. Late Palaeocene eusuchian remains from Mont de Berru, France and the origin of the alligatoroid *Diplocynodon*. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 17: 867–891—Supporting information.
Doi.org/10.1111/zoj.12195.
- Matheron Ph. 1832. Observations sur les terrains des Bouches-du-Rhône suivies de la description d'espèces nouvelles. *Annales des Sciences et Industrie du Midi de la France*, 3.
- Matheron P. 1862. Recherches comparatives sur les dépôts fluvio-lacustres tertiaires des environs de Montpellier, de l'Aude et de la Provence. *Mémoires de la Société d'Emulation de Provence*, 1 (1861-1862).
- Matheron P. 1869a. Note sur les reptiles fossiles des dépôts fluvio-lacustres crétacés du bassin à lignite de Fuveau. *Mémoires de l'Académie Impériale des Sciences. Belles-Lettres et Arts de Marseille* : 1–39.
- Matheron P. 1869b. Note sur les reptiles fossiles des dépôts fluvio-lacustres crétacés du bassin à lignite de Fuveau. *Bulletin de la Société géologique de France*, 2, 26 : 781–795.
- Matheron P. 1878 (1880). *Recherches paléontologiques dans le midi de la France*. 15^e partie, Terrain tertiaire ou Étude sur les animaux fossiles découverts dans cette région. Marseille, chez l'auteur.
- Monteau R. 2010. *Le lignite du bassin de l'Arc (Bouches du Rhône)*. Conférence A.P.B.G (Association des Professeurs de Biologie et de Paléontologie) 2-06-2010. Centre de Formation à l'Enseignement de la Géologie, Académie Aix-Marseille. Online power point.
- Murelaga-Bereikua X. 1998. Primeros restos de tortugas del Cretácico inferior (Barremiense superior) de Vallipón (Castellote Teruel). *Mas de las Matas*, 17 : 189–200.
- Murelaga X., Pereda Suberbiola X., de Lapparent de Broin F., Rage J.-Cl., Duffaud S., Astibia H. & Badiola A. 2002. Amphibians and reptiles from the Lower Miocene of the Bardenas Reales of Navarra (Ebro Basin, Iberian Peninsula). *Geobios*, 35: 347–365.
Doi.org/10.1016/S0016-6995(02)00031-1
- Narváez I., Brochu C. A., de Celis A., Delfino M., Escaso F., Pérez-García A., Rabi M. & Ortega F. 2017. *Allodaposuchus precedens* Nopcsa, 1928 (Crocodyliformes : Eusuchia: Allodaposuchidae): proposed designation of a neotype. *Bulletin of Zoological Nomenclature*, 74: 95–101.
Doi.org/10.21805/bzn.v74.a024
- Narváez I., Brochu C. A., Escaso F., Pérez-García A. & Ortega F. 2015. New crocodyliforms from southwestern Europe and definition of a diverse clade of European uppermost Cretaceous basal eusuchians. *PLoS ONE*, 10:e0140679: 34 p.
Doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0140679
- Narváez I., Brochu C. A., Escaso F., Pérez-García A. & Ortega F. 2016. New Spanish Late Cretaceous eusuchian reveals the synchronic and sympatric presence of two allodaposuchids. *Cretaceous Research*, 65: 112–125.
Doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2016.04.018
- Narváez I., Brochu C. A., Celis A. de, Codrea V., Escaso F., Pérez-García A. & Ortega F. 2019. New diagnosis for *Allodaposuchus precedens*, the type species of the European Upper Cretaceous clade Allodaposuchidae. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 20: 1–17.
- Neumann M. & Odin G. S. 2001. *Le stratotype historique du Campanien, définition, éléments de corrélation*. In: G. S. Odin (Ed.), The Campanian—Maastrichtian stage boundary: characterisation at Tercis les Bains (France): correlation with Europe and other continents. IUGS Special Publication (monograph) Series, 36, Developments in Palaeontology and Stratigraphy Series, 19, Elsevier Sciences Publ. Amsterdam: 677–706.
- Neumann M. & Platel J.-P. (coord.) : Neumann M., Bellier J.-P., Damotte R., Masure E., Monciardini Ch., Platel J.-P. & Andreieff P. 1983. Le Campanien stratotypique : étude lithologique et micropaléontologique. *Géologie Méditerranéenne*, 10 (3-4): 41–57.
- Nopcsa F. B. 1915–1916. Die Dinosaurier der siebenbürgischen Landesteile Ungarns. Mitteilungen aus dem Jahrbuche der KGL. *Ungarischen Geologischen Reichsanstalt*, 23: 1–24.
- Nopcsa F. 1923. *Kallokibotium* A Primitive Amphichelydian Tortoise from the Uppermost Cretaceous of Hungary. *Palaeontographica Hungarica*, 1: 1–34.
- Nopcsa F. B. 1928. Palaeontological notes on Reptilia. 7. Classification of the Crocodylia. *Geologica Hungarica*, Series Palaeontologica, 1: 75–84.
- Nopcsa F. 1931a. Note préliminaire sur quelques tortues du Danien du Midi de la France. *Annales du Musée d'Histoire Naturelle de Marseille*, 22(6) : 4 pp.
- Nopcsa F. 1931b. Sur des nouveaux restes de Tortues du Danien du Midi de la France. *Bulletin de la Société géologique de France*, 5e sér., 3-4 : 223–235.
- Norell M. A., Clark J.M. & Hutchison J. H. 1994. The Late Cretaceous alligatoroid *Brachychampsia montana* (Crocodylia): new material and putative relationships. *American Museum Novitates*, 3116: 11–26.

- Odin G. S. & Lamaurelle M. A. 2001. *The global Campanian-Maastrichtian stage boundary*. In: Odin G. S. (Ed). 2001. *The Campanian-Maastrichtian Stage Boundary. Characterisation and Correlation from Tercis-les-Bains (Landes, SW France) to Europe and Other Continents 19*, 1st Edition: 229–238.
- Ogg J. G. 2020. *Geologic Time Scale*. Ch. 5:159–191. Doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-824360-2.00005-X © 2020 Elsevier B.V.
- Ogg J. G. & Hinnov L. 2012. Cretaceous. In: Gradstein F. M., Ogg J. G., Schmitz M. D., Ogg G. M. (Eds.), *The Geologic Time Scale 2012*. Elsevier, p. 793–853 1st Edition—July 31, 2012. Paperback ISBN: 9780444594259 eBook ISBN: 9780444594488.
- Ösi A. 2008. Cranial osteology of *Iharkutosuchus makadii*, a Late Cretaceous basal eusuchian crocodyliform from Hungary. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 248 (3): 279–299. Doi.org/10.1127/0077-7749/2008/0248-0279
- Ösi A. 2013. The evolution of jaw mechanism and dental function in heterodont crocodyliforms. *Historical Biology*: 136 p. Doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2013.777533
- Ösi A., Clark J. M. & Weishampel D. B. 2007. First report on a new basal eusuchian crocodyliform with multicusped teeth from the Upper Cretaceous (Santonian) of Hungary. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 243 (2): 169–177. Doi.org/10.1127/0077-7749/2007/0243-0169.
- Ösi A., Makádi L., Rabi M., Szentesi Z., Botfalvai G. & Gulyás P. 2012. *The Late Cretaceous continental vertebrate fauna from Iharkút, western Hungary: a review*. In: Godefroit P, editor. *Bernissart dinosaurs and Early Cretaceous ecosystems*. Indiana University Press: 533–570.
- Owen R. 1874. Monograph on the fossil Reptilia of the Wealden and Purbeck formations. Supplement no. V. Dinosauria (*Iguanodon*). [Wealden and Purbeck.]. *The Palaeontographical Society, London* 1873: 1–18.
- Panaïotu C. G. & Panaïotu C. E. 2010. Palaeomagnetism of the Upper Cretaceous Sânpetru Formation (Hațeg Basin, South Carpathians). *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 293: 343–352. Doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2009.11.017
- Pereda-Suberbiola X., Corral J., Astibia H., Badiola A., Bardet N. & Berreteaga A. 2015. Late Cretaceous continental and marine vertebrate assemblages of the Laño Quarry (Basque-Cantabrian Region, Iberian Peninsula): an update. *Journal of Iberian Geology*, 41(1): 101–124. Doi.org/10.5209/rev_JIGE.2015.v41.n1.48658
- Pérez-García A., Antunes M. T., Barroso-Barcenilla F., Callapez P. M., Segura M., Soares A. F. & Torices A. 2017. A bothremydid from the middle Cenomanian of Portugal identified as one of the oldest pleurodiran turtles in Laurasia. *Cretaceous Research*, 78: 61–70. Doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2017.05.031
- Pérez-García A., Ortega F. & Murelaga X. 2012. A new genus of Bothremydidae (Chelonii, Pleurodira) in the Cretaceous of Southwestern Europe. *Geobios*, 45: 219–229. Doi.org/10.1016/j.geobios.2011.03.001
- Planté G. 1870. Sur les lignites inférieurs de l'argile plastique du Bassin parisien. *Bulletin de la Société géologique de France*, 2e sér. 1869-1870, 27 : 204-216.
- Platel J.-P. (coord.), Célerier G., Duchateau-Kervazo C., Chevillot C. & Charnet F. 1999. *Notice explicative de la feuille Ribérac à 1/50 000*. Éditions du Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières, Orléans.
- Plaziat J.-C. 1981. Late Cretaceous to Late Eocene palaeogeographic evolution of Southwest Europe. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 36: 263–320.
- Pomel A. 1847. Note sur les animaux fossiles découverts dans le département de l'Allier. *Bulletin de la Société géologique de France*, 2e sér. 4 : 378-385.
- Portis A. 1882. Les chéloniens de la molasse vaudoise conservés dans le Musée géologique de Lausanne. *Mémoires de la Société paléontologique de Suisse*, 9 : 1-78.
- Prasad V. R. & Lapparent de Broin F. de 2002. Cretaceous crocodile remains from Naskal (India): comparisons and biogeographic affinities. *Annales de Paléontologie*, 88 (1) : 19-71.
- Puértolas E., Canudo J. I. & Cruzado-Caballero P. 2011. A New Crocodylian from the Late Maastrichtian of Spain: Implications for the Initial Radiation of Crocodyloids. *PLoS ONE* 6 (6), e20011 2011: 12 p. Doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0020011
- Puértolas-Pascual E., Arenillas I., Arz J. A., Calvín P., Esquerro L., García-Vicente C., Pérezueyo M. P., Sánchez Moreno E. M., Villalain J. J. & Canudo J. L. 2018. Chronostratigraphy and new vertebrate sites from the upper Maastrichtian of Huesca (Spain), and their relation with the K/Pg boundary. *Cretaceous Research*, 89: 36–59. Doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2018.02.016
- Puértolas-Pascual E., Blanco A., Brochu Ch. A. & Canudo J.I. 2016. Review of the Late Cretaceous-early Palaeogene crocodylomorphs of Europe: Extinction patterns across the K-PG boundary. *Cretaceous Research*, 57: 565–590. Doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2015.08.002
- Puértolas-Pascual E., Canudo J. I. & Brochu C. A. 2014a. *Extinction patterns of continental European crocodylomorphs across the K-Pg boundary*. In: J. Marmi, O. Oms, B. Vila, A. Galobart, R. Estrada, & J. Dinarès-Turell (Eds.), *Paleontologia i Evolució, mem. especial núm. 7*, Field Trip Guide and Abstracts Book of “Reconstructing”.
- Puértolas-Pascual E., Canudo J. I. & Moreno-Azanza M. 2014b. The eusuchian crocodylomorph *Allodaposuchus subjuniperus* sp. nov., a new species from the latest Cretaceous (upper Maastrichtian) of Spain. *Historical Biology*, 26 (1): 91–109. Doi.org/10.1080/08912963.2012.763034
- Puértolas-Pascual E., Serrano-Martínez A., Pérez Pueyo M., Bádenas B. & Canudo J. L. 2022. New data on the euroanatomy of basal eusuchian crocodylomorphs (Allodaposuchidae) from the Upper Cretaceous of Spain. *Cretaceous Research*, 135: 65 p. Doi.org/10.1016/j.cretres.2022.105170.
- Rabi M. 2005. Alligatoroidea indet. from the Upper Cretaceous of Hungary (Csehbánya Formation). *Kaupia, Darmstädter Beiträge zur Naturgeschichte*, In: 3rd Annual Meeting of the European Association of Vertebrate Palaeontologists, Abstract volume, 14: 93A.
- Rabi M. & Botfalvai G. 2006. A new bothremydid (Chelonii: Pleurodira) fossil assemblage from the Late Cretaceous (Santonian) of Hungary — additional studies in the historical paleobiogeography of Late Cretaceous bothremydid. *Hantkeniana*, 5: 61–65.
- Rabi M. & Delfino M. 2012. *A Reassessment of the “Alligatoroid” Eusuchian from the Late Cretaceous of*

- Hungary and its Taxonomic Implications*. In: R. Royo-Torres, F. Gasco, & L. Alcalá (Eds.), ¡Fundamental!: 20. 10th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Vertebrate Paleontologists, EAVP Abstracts book: 203–206.
- Rabi M. & Sebok N. 2015. A revised Eurogondwana model: Late Cretaceous notosuchian crocodyliforms and other vertebrate taxa suggest the retention of episodic faunal links between Europe and Gondwana during most of the Cretaceous. *Gondwana Research*, 28(3) : 1197-1211. Doi.org/10.1016/j.gr.2014.09.015
- Rabi M. & Tong H. 2007. *Shell reconstruction of the bothremydid turtle (Testudines: Pleurodira) from the Late Cretaceous of Iharkút, Hungary*. In: 5th Meeting of the European Association of Vertebrate Palaeontologists, 12th European Workshop of Vertebrate Palaeontology, Carcassonne-Espéraza, May 15–19, 2007. EAVP Abstracts book: 49–50.
- Rabi M., Tong H. & Bótfalvai G. 2011. A new species of the side-necked turtle *Foxemys* (Pelomedusoides: Bothremyidae) from the Late Cretaceous of Hungary and the historical biogeography of the Bothremyidini. *Geological Magazine*: 1–13. Doi.org/10.1017/S0016756811000756
- Rabi M., Vremir M. & Tong H. 2013. *Preliminary overview of Late Cretaceous turtle diversity in Eastern Central Europe (Austria, Hungary, and Romania)*. In: D. B. Brinkman et al. (Eds.) Morphology and Evolution of Turtles, Vertebrate Paleobiology and Paleoanthropology. Doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4309-0_19, Springer Science+Business Media Dordrecht.
- Remin Z. 2015. The *Belemnitella* stratigraphy of the Upper Campanian: basal Maastrichtian of the Middle Vistula section, central Poland. *Geological Quarterly*, 59: 783–813.
- Répelin J. 1930. *Description géologique succincte du département des Bouches-du-Rhône*. Extrait du Tome 1er des Bouches-du-Rhône, Encyclopédie départementale. Sémaphore de Marseille, Marseille.
- Rio J. P. & Mannion P. D. 2021. Phylogenetic analysis of a new morphological dataset elucidates the evolutionary history of Crocodylia and resolves the long-standing gharial problem. *PeerJ* 9: e12094. Doi.org/10.7717/peerj.12094
- Russell D. E. & coll: Bonde N., Boné E., Broin F. de, Brunet M., Buffetaut E., Cordy J. M., Crochet J.-Y., Dineur H., Estes R., Ginsburg L., Godinot M., Groessens M. C., Gigase P., Harrison C. J. O., Hartenberger J.-L., Hoch, E., Hooker J. J., Insole A. N., Lange-Badré B., Louis P., Moody R., Rage J.-CL., Remy J., Rothausen K., Sigé B., Sigogneau-Russell D., Springhorn R., Sudre J., Tobien H., Vianey-Liaud M., Vinken R. & Walker C. A. 1982. Tetrapods of the Northwest European Tertiary Basin. IGCP, Project 124: the North-West European Tertiary Basin. *Geologische Jahrbuch*, A 60: 5-74.
- Saint-Martin J. P., Dutour Y., Ebbo L., Frau C., Didier Néraudeau D., Saint Martin S. & Valentin X. 2021. Reassessment of amber-bearing deposits of Provence, southeastern France. *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France* 192 (5) : 1-22. Doi.org/10.1051/bsgf/2020048
- Scott R. W. 2014. A Cretaceous chronostratigraphic database: Constructions and applications. *Carnets de Géologie*, 14 (2) : 15-37. Doi.10.4267/2042/53522.
- Solomon A. & Codrea V. 2015. Some Maastrichtian Vertebrates from fluvial channel fill deposits at Pui (Hațeg Basin) Muzeul Olteniei Craiova. Oltenia. *Studii și comunicări. Științele Naturii*, ISSN 1454–6914, 31 (2): 26–34.
- Steel R. 1973. *Handbuch der Paläoherpetologie*, Crocodylia, 16: 1–115. Gustav Fischer Verlag. Stuttgart.
- Tabuce R., Tortosa T., Vianey-Liaud M., Garcia G., Lebrun R., Godefroit P., Dutour Y., Berton S., Valentin X. & Cheylan G. 2013. New eutherian mammals from the Late Cretaceous of Aix-en-Provence Basin, south-eastern France. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 169: 653–672.
- Taquet Ph. 2001. Philippe Matheron et Paul Gervais : deux pionniers de la découverte et de l'étude des os et des œufs de dinosaures de Provence (France). *Geodiversitas* 23 (4) : 611-623. g2001n4a3-low.pdf
- Tong H., Gaffney E. S. & Buffetaut E. 1998. *Foxemys*, A New Side-Necked Turtle (Bothremyidae: Pelomedusoides) from the Late Cretaceous of France. *American Museum Novitates*, 3251: 19 p.
- Turin G. 2017. Description de deux espèces nouvelles du genre *Lychnus* (Mollusca, Gastropoda, Anadromidae) au Rognacien (Maastrichtien supérieur) de Vitrolles (Bouches-du-Rhône, France). *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France*. Earth Sciences, 188 (38): 7 p. Doi.org/10.1051/bsgf/2017204
- Vaillant L. 1872. Etude zoologique sur les crocodiliens fossiles tertiaires de Saint-Gérard-le-Puy. *Annales des Sciences géologiques*, 3 : 1-58.
- Vasse D. 1995. *Ischyrochampsia meridionalis* n. g. n. sp., un crocodilien d'affinité gondwanienne dans le Crétacé supérieur du Sud de la France. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Palaontologie*, 8: 501-512.
- Villot L. 1883. Etude sur le bassin de Fuveau et sur un grand travail à y exécuter. *Annales des Mines de Paris*, 3 (4) : 5-66.
- Vremir M. 2010. New faunal elements from the late Cretaceous (Maastrichtian) continental deposits of Sebeș area (Transylvania). Terra Sebus. *Acta Musei Sabasiensis*, 2: 635–684.
- Vremir M. & Codrea V. 2009. *Late Cretaceous turtle diversity in Transylvanian and Hațeg basins (Romania)*. The 7th International Symposium of Paleontology, Cluj-Napoca, Romania, Abstract Volume: 122–124.
- Westphal M. 1989. Magnétostratigraphie du Crétacé supérieur du bassin d'Aix en Provence. Etude préliminaire. La limite Crétacé-Tertiaire dans le synclinal de l'Arc 1. *Cahiers de la Réserve Géologique de Provence, Digne*, 1 : 28-33.
- Westphal M. & Durand J.-P. 1990. Magnétostratigraphie des séries continentales fluvio-lacustres du Crétacé supérieur dans le synclinal de l'Arc (région d'Aix-en-Provence, France). *Bulletin de la Société géologique de France*, 8 (6) : 609–620.
- Ziegler P. A. 1988. Evolution of the Arctic-North Atlantic and the Western Tethys. *Memories of the American Association of Petroleum Geologists*, 43: I-VIII + 198 p, fig-maps.